

Taxonomy and biostratigraphy of Kimmeridgian ammonites from the Kachchh Basin, western India

Dhirendra Kumar Pandey^{1*}, Matthias Alberti², Franz T. Fürsich³, Suraj Bhosale⁴, Ketan Chaskar⁵, Jitendra Kumar Sharma¹

¹ Department of Geology, University of Rajasthan, Jaipur 302004; dhirendrap@hotmail.com

² Geologisches und Mineralogisches Museum, Institut für Geowissenschaften, Christian-Albrechts-Universität zu Kiel, Ludewig-Meyn-Straße 12, 24118 Kiel, Germany

³ FG Paläoumwelt, GeoZentrum Nordbayern der Friedrich-Alexander-Universität Erlangen-Nürnberg, Loewenichstraße 28, 91054 Erlangen, Germany

⁴ Department of Earth Sciences, Indian Institute of Technology Bombay, Mumbai 400076, Maharashtra, India

⁵ Department of Earth and Environmental Science, K.S.K.V. Kachchh University, Bhuj, 370001, India

* Corresponding author

Abstract: A collection of 112 Kimmeridgian ammonites, collected bed-by-bed during detailed measurements of four Jurassic sections in the Kachchh Basin are described. They belong to 11 genera of the families Phylloceratidae, Oppediidae, Ataxioceratidae, and Aspidoceratidae. Some species are considered endemic to the Indo-East-African faunal province, such as *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen), *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, *Katroliceras katrolensis* (Waagen), and *Aspidoceras iphiceroideus* Waagen. A few ammonites, on the other hand, such as *Aspidoceras* cf. *acanthicum* (Oppel) and *Progeronia digitata* (Schneid), have also been recorded from the Mediterranean and/or Submediterranean faunal provinces. Dimorphic pairs in some of the endemic taxa, such as *T. alterneplicatus*, *T. alterneplicatus* morph neglecta, *T. intermedius*, *T. acuticostatus* Spath, *Katroliceras waageni* Spath, and *Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath have been recognised. The co-occurrence of north Tethyan guide ammonites with forms endemic to the Indo-East-African faunal province help in refining or corroborating the Kimmeridgian ammonite zonation delineated by earlier workers.

Key-words: Kimmeridgian, ammonites, taxonomy, biostratigraphy, Kachchh Basin, India

1. INTRODUCTION

The sedimentary succession of the Kachchh Basin, a pericratonic rift basin on the northwestern margin of the Indian Subcontinent (Fig. 1), has recorded several significant geological events at the southern margin of the Neotethys from Early Jurassic times (see Biswas, 1980, 2016a, b; Fürsich *et al.*, 2013, 2020; Krishna, 2017; Biswas *et al.*, 2022). The Jurassic strata are known for their diverse and rich fossil content, which together with the sedimentary facies allows precise palaeoenvironmental reconstructions for different time intervals. The litho- and biostratigraphic schemes of the Kachchh Basin (see Fig. 2) have been recently revised by Fürsich *et al.* (2023). The present article deals with ammonites of the Kimmeridgian stage, including species endemic to the Indo-East-African faunal province, as well as cosmopolitan species that migrated

from the west, particularly from the Mediterranean and Submediterranean faunal provinces (Geyer, 1961; Schlegelmilch, 1994; Cariou & Hantzpergue, 1997; Gygi, 2003; Schick, 2004; Scherzinger *et al.*, 2016; Hesselbo *et al.*, 2020). The sediments yielding these ammonites are predominantly siliciclastic, ranging from fine to coarse and from poorly to well-sorted, together with minor marly and carbonaceous intercalations. The depositional environments range from shallow marine storm-influenced to deltaic settings. All localities that yielded Kimmeridgian ammonites for the present study lie in the eastern part of the Mainland Subbasin (Fürsich *et al.*, 2023, fig. 85). In the present article, description and illustration of the bed-by-bed collection of 112 Kimmeridgian ammonites from four sections contribute to an improvement of the Kimmeridgian ammonite biostratigraphy of the Kachchh Basin.

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2. KIMMERIDGIAN STRATA IN THE KACHCHH BASIN

Kimmeridgian strata exposed at various localities of the Kachchh Basin are exclusively siliciclastic in nature, and sedimentary environments range from fully marine to marginal marine deltas. A detailed account of stacking patterns, lithology, sedimentary structures, thicknesses of beds and temporal distribution and diversity of fossils in the four studied sections (Fig. 3) has been published by Fürsich *et al.* (2023).

Jhuran River Section (coordinates 23°21'32.7" N, 69°59'48.4" E). The units 9, 10, 11, and 12 of the Jhuran

River Section have yielded most of the ammonites of the Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone. Units 13, 14, and 15 represent the Bathyplocus Zone. In this section, the Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone is thick. The boundary between the two zones would be within unit 12. It is for this reason that unit 12 has been assigned to the early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone to Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone in the chapter on systematic palaeontology. There are 56 ammonites forming 50% of the total collection, representing the families Opepliidae (12), Ataxioceratidae (42), and Aspidoceratidae (2). Lithostratigraphically, the section represents the Lothia Member of the Jhuran Formation (Fürsich *et al.*, 2023, fig. 63), see Figs 2, 3, and Table 1.

Fig. 1. A: Regions with marine Jurassic strata in the Indian Subcontinent (modified after Pathak, 2007; Fürsich *et al.*, 2021; Alberti *et al.*, 2022). B: Palaeogeography of the Late Jurassic world with the location of the Kachchh Basin marked (modified after Smith *et al.*, 1994; Fürsich *et al.*, 2023). C: Simplified geological map of the Kachchh Basin showing the location of measured sections with Kimmeridgian ammonites described in the present article: GD – Gangeswar Dome; LOD – Lodai; KH – Kas Hill; JH – Jhuran River; modified after Patel *et al.*, 2012; Fürsich *et al.*, 2013).

Gangeshwar Dome Section (coordinates 23°11'04.6"N, 69°43'24.9"E). Although occasional *T. alterneplicatus* and *T. intermedius* have been recorded from unit 14, the section has yielded more ammonites of the *Bathyplocus* (units 20 and 21) and *Katrolensis* (unit 35) zones. In this section, the *Bathyplocus* and *Katrolensis* zones are thick, whereas the underlying *Acanthicus/Intermedius* Zone is thin. The boundaries between these three are not clear. Out of 29 ammonites recorded from this section, 23 are species of *Indodichotomoceras*, *Pachysphinctes*, and *Katrolceras*. In addition, *Torquatisphinctes* (5) is common and there is one example of *A. iphiceroides*. Lithostratigraphically, this section represents the Shivparas and Tapkeshwari members of the Jhuran Formation, see Figs. 2, 3, and Table 1.

Lodai Section (coordinates 23°22'18"N, 69°53'33"E). This section is unique because of its coarse-quartz-

grain-bearing basal part of the Kimmeridgian succession overlying the Dhosa Conglomerate Bed (DCB), the concentration of *Mayaites* in the Oxfordian DCB (Alberti *et al.*, 2015), and the concentration of *Aspidoceras* in the Kimmeridgian strata. Within the Kimmeridgian part of the section, i.e. from unit 70 upwards as shown in Fig. 3, only unit 75 has yielded ammonites, 16 specimens. Out of these 16 ammonites, eight have been assigned to various species of *Aspidoceras*, including one to *A. cf. acanthicum* (Oppel, 1863), seven to *T. alterneplicatus*, and one to *Ptychophylloceras cf. ptychoicum* (Quenstedt, 1845). Lithostratigraphically, the Kimmeridgian part of the Lodai section represents a part of the Jhuran River Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone) of the Jhuran Formation (Fürsich *et al.*, 2023, fig. 60), see Figs. 2, 3, and Table 1.

Tethyan ammonite zones (TAZ)		Kachchh Mainland			Kachchh ammonite zones (KAZ)											
		west & central	east	southeast												
		Jara, Jumara	Lodai, Kas Hill, Jhuran River	Gangeshwar Dome, Ler												
Tithonian	Late	Jacobi	Bed III Green Ammonite Mb	Bhuj Formation	Bhuj Formation	Frequens	Tithonian									
	Early	Andraeai				Bed II		Jhuran Fm	Tapkeshwari Mb	Microcanthum						
		Microcanthum								Bed I	Jhuran Sandstone Mb	Denseplicatus				
		Ponti / Peroni	Hildoglochiceras Bed	Jhuran Fm	Semiforme											
		Fallauxi			Lower mb	Jhuran Fm	Virgatosphinctoides									
		Semiforme	Jhuran Sandstone Mb	Jhuran Fm			Katrolensis									
		Darwini			Lothia Mb	Jhuran Fm				Bathyplocus						
		Hybonotum	Jhuran River Mb	Jhuran Fm			Acanthicum									
	Beckeri	stratigraphic gap			Jhuran Fm	Alterneplicatus										
	Eudoxus / Cavouri		Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm			Jhuran Fm									
Acanthicum	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm			Jhuran Fm											
Divisum			Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm		Jhuran Fm										
Hypselocyclum	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm			Jhuran Fm											
Platynota			Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm		Jhuran Fm										
Planula	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm			Jhuran Fm											
Bimammatum			Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm		Jhuran Fm										
Kimmeridgian	Late	Beckeri			stratigraphic gap		Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Kimmeridgian						
	Early	Eudoxus / Cavouri	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm		Jhuran Fm										
		Acanthicum									Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm			
		Divisum												Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm
		Hypselocyclum														
Platynota	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm													
Planula				Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm										
Bimammatum							Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm	Jhuran Fm							
Oxfordian										Late	Hypselum	Dhosa Conglomerate Bed	Jumara Fm	Dhosa Oolite Mb	Oxfordian	
	M.	Bifurcatus	Dhosa Conglomerate Bed							Jumara Fm	Dhosa Oolite Mb					
		Transversarium		Dhosa Conglomerate Bed	Jumara Fm	Dhosa Oolite Mb										
		Plicatilis					Dhosa Conglomerate Bed	Jumara Fm	Dhosa Oolite Mb							
		Cordatum														Dhosa Conglomerate Bed
Early	Mariae	Dhosa Conglomerate Bed	Jumara Fm							Dhosa Oolite Mb						

Fig. 2. Litho- and chronostratigraphic framework of the Upper Jurassic strata of the Kachchh Mainland (modified from Fürsich *et al.*, 2023). The grey box highlights the Kimmeridgian. The corresponding Kachchh ammonite zones have been correlated with the Tethyan ammonite zonation (Scherzinger *et al.*, 2016; Hesselbo *et al.*, 2020).

Kas Hill Section (coordinates 23°22'08"N, 69°54'58"E and 23°22'23"N, 69°54'40"E). This section has yielded 11 ammonites, representing inner whorls of *Katrolceras* sp. (7), two small specimens of *Taramelliceras kachhensis* (Waagen, 1875), and a single specimen each of *Katrolceras lerense* Spath, 1931 and *Holcophylloceras cf. polyolcum* (Benecke, 1865).

Lithostratigraphically, the lower part of this section represents the Lothia Member of the Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian *Katrolensis* Zone, Fig. 2, Table 1). Due to outcrop conditions, it was not possible to measure a detailed section at Kas Hill. Consequently, this section has not been illustrated in Figure 3.

Fig. 3. Sections of the sampled Kimmeridgian strata at Jhuran River, Lodai, and Gangeshwar Dome sections in the eastern Kachchh Mainland (partly modified from Fürsich *et al.*, 2023). Note the range of Kimmeridgian ammonite zones recorded in the present work.

3. KIMMERIDGIAN AMMONITES IN THE KACHCHH BASIN

The distribution of fossils in the Kimmeridgian strata is patchy and most beds are devoid of macrobenthos. The most abundant fossils are ammonites and belemnites. The ammonites represent the families Phylloceratidae, Oppeliidae, Ataxioceratidae, and Aspidoceratidae. Despite their patchy distribution, members of the

subfamily Torquatisphinctinae (family Ataxioceratidae) are important guide fossils in biostratigraphy (Krishna & Pathak, 1993; Krishna *et al.*, 1996; Schweigert *et al.*, 1996; Krishna, 2017), defining in the present work the ammonite zonation shown in Fig. 3 (see also Fürsich *et al.*, 2023).

Oppeliids form the second-largest Kimmeridgian ammonite group in the Kachchh Basin after the Torquatisphinctinae. In the Jurassic of the Kachchh

Basin Waagen (1875, p. 47; see also Spath, 1928) recognized seven groups of oppeliids, represented by several species. Chronologically, they appeared in the Early Callovian, were most abundant in the Late Callovian, and were represented in the Kimmeridgian by five species: *Taramelliceras akher* Spath, 1928, *T. kachhense* (Waagen, 1875), *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen, 1875), *S. habyensensis* Spath, 1928, and *Metahaploceras pascoei* Spath, 1928. Waagen (1875) reported that certain forms of oppeliids in the Kachchh Basin are identical to those of Europe, i.e. Kachchh oppeliids include both endemic and European forms. In the present collection, they have been recorded from the lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), of the Jhuran River section, and from the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone) of the Kas Hill section near Lodai Dam.

Members of the subfamily Aspidoceratinae (family Aspidoceratidae), although generally not common in Kimmeridgian strata of the Kachchh Basin, form the third-largest group and are quite numerous in the basal part of the Kimmeridgian succession (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone) of the Lodai section. According to Krishna *et al.* (1994) their episodic presence is related to eustatic sea-level maxima. Lithostratigraphically, these *Aspidoceras*-yielding horizons are:

- (1) the so-called Belemnite Marls (= Jhuran River Member; Alterneplacatus Zone), along the Jhuran River section,
- (2) the Lower Katrol Member (= Lothia Member/Shivparas Member; Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), along the Katrol Range, Lodai section, north of the village Dhosa, sections east, southeast and west of the village Ler, Fakirwadi section, and Samatra section,
- (3) the middle Katrol Member (= Jhuran Sandstone Member/Tapkeshwari Member; Bathyplocus and Katrolensis zones) at Ler-Hamundra section, Charwar

Range, Katrol Range, north of the village Dhosa, Walakhawas section, and

(4) the upper Katrol Member (= Tapkeshwari Member; Katrolensis Zone) southeast of Ler, and the lowermost Berriasian horizon (Trigonia Sandstone Member; Berriasian) at the Mundhan Anticline (for references of the horizons and localities see Waagen, 1875; Spath, 1931; Krishna *et al.*, 1994; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b; Fürsich *et al.*, 2023).

The aspidoceratids recognised from the Lodai section are *A. cf. acanthicum* (Oppel, 1863), *A. aff. bispinosum* (Zieten, 1830), *A. asymmetricum* Spath, 1931, and *A. binodiferum* Waagen, 1875, whereas in the Jhuran River section *A. asymmetricum* Spath, 1931 and *A. binodiferum* Waagen, 1875 occur, and at the Gangeshwar Dome only *A. iphiceroides* Waagen, 1875. These aspidoceratids also include biostratigraphic zonal guide fossils, such as the *Aspidoceras cf. acanthicum* from the Lodai section and *A. iphiceroides* from the Gangeshwar Dome section that could represent the Acanthicum or Iphiceroides subzones, respectively, of the Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone (Cariou & Hantzpergue, 1997; Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009b, 2011). At Lodai, the units 75 to 77 (see Fig. 3) of the Jhuran River Member containing ammonites correspond to the lower part of the Lothia Member (= Lower Member of Biswas, 1980) at the Jhuran River section, which has yielded several *T. intermedius* (a guide fossil of the early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone). Also, the basal part of the Gangeshwar Dome section (Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation) above the Dhosa Conglomerate Bed corresponds to the Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone. Following the earlier records of *Aspidoceras* in the Kachchh Basin (Waagen, 1875; Spath, 1931), early Late Kimmeridgian sediments of the Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone at the Lodai section and at Gangeshwar Dome should also be present in the Katrol Range, north of the village Dhosa, in the sections east, southeast, and west of the village Ler, and in the Fakirwadi and Samatra sections.

Tabl. 1. Horizons and localities of Kimmeridgian ammonites recorded in the present work. Figure in parentheses indicate number of specimens.

		1	2	3	4	5	6	7	8
Locality, Horizon		Kas Hill section near Lodai Dam, Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone)	Lodai section, Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone)	Jhuran River section, lower part of Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone)	Jhuran River section, lower part of Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone to Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone)	Jhuran River section, lower part of Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone)	Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone)	Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone)	Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone)
Species, (Number of specimens) Collection number									
1	<i>Holcophylloceras cf. polyolcum</i> (Benecke)	(1) RUC2016 IKH 07							
2	<i>Ptychophylloceras cf. ptychoicum</i> (Quenstedt)		(1) RUC2016 IILOD 26						
3	<i>Taramelliceras</i>	(2) RUC2016							

	<i>kachhensis</i> (Waagen)	IKH 34, 52							
4	<i>Metahaploceras</i> cf. <i>paecoei</i> Spath			(4) RUC2015 JH 3, 19, 27, 28					
5	<i>Streblites plicodiscus</i> (Waagen)			(8) RUC2015 JH 4, 5, 6, 25, 33, 60, RUC2016 JH 1, 6					
6	<i>Progeronia digitatus</i> (Schneid)				(1) RUC2015 JH 20				
7	<i>Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus</i> (Waagen) [m] & [M]		[m] (1) RUC2016 ILOD 1	[m] (3) RUC2016 IJH 8, 23, RUC2015 JH 11 [M] (1) RUC2016 IJH 6					
8	<i>Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus</i> (Waagen) morph <i>neglecta</i> Spath [m] & [M]		[m] (6) RUC2016 ILOD 2-4, 14, 17, 18	[m] (5) RUC2015 JH 8, 16, 30, 42, 43A, [M] (1) RUC2015 JH 38	[m] (2) RUC2016 IJH 23, 25		[m] (2) RUC2016 GD 3, 4.		
9	<i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i> Spath [m] & [M]			[m] (8) RUC2016 IJH 15, RUC2015 JH 34, 35, 37, 40B, 44, 57 [M] RUC2016 IJH 9	[m] (2) RUC2016 IJH 7, 9		[m] (1) RUC2015 GD 31		
10	<i>Torquatisphinctes torquatus</i> (J. de C. Sowerby)						(1) RUC2017 IGD 7		
11	<i>Torquatisphinctes</i> cf. <i>jurunensis</i> Spath			(3) RUC2016 IJH 1, RUC2015 JH 10, 53			(1) RUC2017 IGD 9		
12	<i>Torquatisphinctes acuticostatus</i> Spath [m] & [M]			[m] (1) RUC2015 JH 49A [M] (2) RUC2015 JH 35A, 32					
13	<i>Torquatisphinctes</i> gr. <i>primus-similis</i> Spath			(8) RUC2016 IJH 2, 10, RUC2015 JH 24, 24A, 29, 40A, 41, 55					
14	<i>Indodichotomoceras</i> cf. <i>inversum</i> (Spath) [M]						(2) RUC2015 GD 23, 7		
15	<i>Indodichotomoceras inversum</i> (Spath) [m]						(1) RUC2015 GD 1		
16	<i>Indodichotomoceras predivisum</i> (Spath)						(1) RUC2017 IGD 2		
17	<i>Subdichotomoceras</i> cf. <i>lamplughi</i> (Spath)						(1) RUC2017 IGD 5		
18	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> cf. <i>robustus</i> Spath						(1) RUC2017 IGD 12		
19	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> sp. indet.						(1) RUC2015 GD 9		
20	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> sp.				(1) RUC2018 JH 2				
21	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> cf. <i>linguiferus</i> Spath						(1) RUC2017 IGD 18		
22	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> gr. <i>linguiferus</i> – <i>symmetricus</i> Spath						(1) RUC2017 IGD 13		
23	<i>Pachysphinctes symmetricus</i> Spath						(1) RUC2013 GD 1		
24	<i>Pachysphinctes major</i> Spath						(2) RUC2017 IGD 182, 183		
25	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> cf. <i>major</i> Spath					(2) RUC2015 JH 17, RUC2016 IJH 11	(1) RUC2015 GD 41		
26	<i>Pachysphinctes</i> aff. <i>major</i> Spath [M]					(2) RUC2018 JH 1, RUC2015 JH 14			
27	<i>Katroliceras katrolensis</i> (Waagen)								(2) RUC2015 GD 15, 28
28	<i>Katroliceras subkatrolensis</i> var.								(4) RUC2015 GD 4, 23A,

	<i>splendens</i> Spath								42, RUC2017 IGD 15
29	<i>Katrolicerias waageni</i> Spath [m] & [M]								[m] (1) RUC2017 IGD 11, [M] (1) RUC2017 IGD 14
30	<i>Katrolicerias sowerbyi</i> Spath								(2) RUC2015 GD 20, RUC2017 IGD 17
31	<i>Katrolicerias lerense</i> Spath	(1) RUC2016 IKH 01							
32	<i>Katrolicerias</i> sp.	(7) RUC2016 IKH 01-06, 51							
33	<i>Aspidoceras</i> aff. <i>acanthicum</i> (Oppel)		(1) RUC2016 ILOD 8						
34	<i>Aspidoceras</i> aff. <i>bispinosum</i> (Zieten)		(1) RUC2016 ILOD 16						
35	<i>Aspidoceras asymmetricum</i> Spath [m] & [M]		[m] (1) RUC2016 ILOD 5		[M] (1) RUC2015 JH, 26				
36	<i>Aspidoceras binodiferum</i> Waagen		(5) RUC2016 ILOD 6, 7, 15, 20, 25		(1) RUC2015 JH 18				
37	<i>Aspidoceras iphiceroides</i> Waagen						(1) RUC2017 IGD 1		
	Total taxa (specimens)	4 (11)	7 (16)	12 (46)	4 (6)	2 (4)	6 (7)	10 (12)	4 (10)

4. KIMMERIDGIAN AMMONITE ZONATIONS OF THE KACHCHH BASIN

The Kimmeridgian strata of the Kachchh Basin have yielded diverse groups of ammonites, such as Torquatisphinctinae, Aspidoceratinae, Hybonoticeratinae, Taramelliceratinae, Streblitinae and Calliphylloceratinae. Based on their first occurrence and on the abundance of Torquatisphinctinae, four Kimmeridgian ammonite zones, ranging from late Early Kimmeridgian to Late Kimmeridgian, have been proposed for the Kachchh Basin (Krishna & Pathak, 1993; Krishna *et al.*, 1996; Schweigert *et al.*, 1996; Krishna, 2017). Unfortunately, hitherto the early Early Kimmeridgian has not been recorded in the Mainland part of the Kachchh Basin. In fact, a major stratigraphic gap from the Late Oxfordian to early Early Kimmeridgian exists in the Kachchh Mainland (Krishna, 2017; Fürsich *et al.*, 2023, table 6), see Fig. 2. In total, four Kimmeridgian ammonite zones, i.e. the *Alterneplacatus*, *Intermedius*, *Bathyplocus*, and *Katrolensis* zones, have been recognised in the Mainland part of the Kachchh Basin based on first or last appearance and the abundance of endemic Torquatisphinctinae species, such as *T. alterneplacatus*, *T. intermedius*, *Pachysphinctes bathyplocus*, and *Katrolicerias katrolensis* (Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009, 2011; Krishna & Pathak, 1991, 1993; Krishna, 2017). In addition, Schweigert *et al.* (1996) reported the presence of the Late Kimmeridgian Infundibulum Zone above the *Katrolensis* Zone (Table 2) based on the occurrence of the association of *Hybonoticerias ornatum* (Spath, 1931) and *Aulacosphinctoides infundibulum* (Uhlig, 1910). Krishna (2017, p. 117) revised the *Katrolensis* Zone (Krishna & Pathak, 1991) to include the Infundibulum Zone in it as a subzone. Interestingly, in the Spiti region of the Indian Himalayas *A. infundibulum* indicates an Early Tithonian age (Énay, 2009; Énay & Howarth,

2019). These Kimmeridgian ammonite zones have been correlated with Tethyan Kimmeridgian ammonite zones *Divisum*, *Acanthicum*, *Eudoxus/Cavouri*, and *Beckeri* (Scherzinger *et al.*, 2016; Hesselbo *et al.*, 2020). The Infundibulum Zone/Subzone corresponds to the upper part of the *Beckeri* Zone (Schweigert *et al.*, 1996; Krishna, 2017).

Furthermore, the lower four Kimmeridgian Tethyan ammonite zones *Bimammatum*, *Planula*, *Platynota*, and *Hypselocyclum*, have not been recorded in the Kachchh Mainland, perhaps due to the stratigraphic gap mentioned above. Interestingly, the *Bimammatum* Zone has been recognized in the Kantkote Sandstone of the Wagad Uplift in eastern Kachchh (Spath, 1933, p. 873; Krishna *et al.*, 2011; Pandey *et al.*, 2012). In fact, there are also indications of other Early Kimmeridgian Tethyan ammonite zones in the eastern part of the Kachchh Basin. For example, the *Planula*, *Platynota* and *Hypselocyclum* zones have been indicated by Krishna *et al.* (2009, 2011), albeit without any evidence of guide ammonites (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b). The record of *Orthosphinctes*, *Subnebrodites*, and *Ataxioceras*, and the assumption of a *Bimammatum* to *Hypselocyclum* age for the Adhoi Member in the Wagad Uplift of eastern Kachchh (Krishna *et al.*, 2009) is worth reinvestigating (also see Alberti *et al.*, 2019).

Orthosphinctes in the Kachchh Basin represents the Early Kimmeridgian (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b).

The genus *Aspidoceras* Zittel, 1868 ranges from the Early Kimmeridgian *Bimammatum* Zone to the Early Berriasian *Jacobi* Zone (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b) with its maximum development in the early Late Kimmeridgian *Intermedius* Zone. In contrast, the association of *A. acanthicum* and *A. iphiceroides* has been used to correlate the *Intermedius* Zone (Krishna & Pathak, 1991) of the southern Tethyan margin (Kachchh) with the *Acanthicum* Zone of the northern Tethyan margin (Fig. 2).

Tabl. 2. Kimmeridgian ammonite biostratigraphy for the Kachchh Basin (proposed by Krishna and Pathak, 1991; Krishna et al., 1996, 2011; Schweigert et al., 1996; Pandey et al., 2010; Krishna, 2017).

	Horizons and subzones	Kachchh ammonite zones (proposed from Ler and Bharodia sections)	Tethyan Zone
<i>Hybonoticeras ornatum</i>	K-VIII Infundibulum The horizon is marked by first occurrence of <i>Hybonoticeras ornatum</i>	<p>Katrolensis Zone (Krishna and Pathak 1991) is overlain by the Infundibulum Zone in Kachchh (in Schweigert et al. 1996) but included in Katrolensis Zone in Krishna et al. 1996. Pandey et al. 2010; Krishna 2017).</p> <p>Katrolensis and Pressulum subzones start with the first appearance of the successive four transient morphs (morphs I to IV) of <i>K. katrolensis</i> (Waagen) (m). These morphs are based on the position of the first appearance of the abruptly modified (cuniformal, wedge-shaped) primary ribs from the last quarter to the start of the body chamber in the successively younging morphs. In addition, size increase is also observed in the successively younging morphs I to IV. In Spiti, it is Early Tithonian (Énay 2009; Énay and Howarth 2019).</p>	The Infundibulum Zone correspond to upper part of the Beckeri Zone (Schweigert et al., 1996).
<i>Aulacosphinctoides infundibulum</i>	K-VII Infundibulum The horizon is marked by first occurrence of <i>Aulacosphinctoides infundibulum</i>		<p>Beckeri</p>
devoid of determinable ammonoids although fossil wood and belemnoids are present. <i>K. katrolensis</i> (Waagen) seems to have become extinct. scarce indeterminate virgatosphinctin ammonoids	K-VI unnamed K-VI Horizon is marked by the occurrence of scarce indeterminate virgatosphinctines		
First appearance <i>Indodichotomoceras inversum</i> m Continue from below <i>K. katrolensis</i> (but small size)	K-V Inversum K-V Horizon is based on the sudden reduction in size of <i>K. katrolensis</i> and marked by first occurrence of <i>Indodichotomoceras inversum</i> m		
First appearance <i>Hybonoticeras pressulum</i> <i>K. katrolensis</i> morph III and IV <i>K. spathi</i> , <i>Hybonoticeras knopi</i> (K-III Horizon) Continue from below: <i>Hybonoticeras kachhensis</i> Recorded from this subzone: <i>Pseudowaagenia carpathica</i> Spath (Krishna and Pathak 1991)	K-III to K-IV Pressulum marked by first occurrence of <i>Hybonoticeras pressulum</i> <i>Size increase in successively morphs K-I to K-IV of K. katrolensis.</i> K-IV Horizon is marked by the appearance of morph IV of <i>K. katrolensis</i> , i.e., first abruptly modified rib between the start and the middle of the first quarter of the body chamber. K-III Horizon is marked by the appearance of morph III of <i>K. katrolensis</i> , i.e. the first abruptly modified rib in the beginning of the second or at the end of the first quarter of the body chamber		
First appearance <i>K. katrolensis</i> morphs I and II <i>Hybonoticeras kachhensis</i> = <i>Hybonoticeras knopi</i> (Schweigert et al. 1996), <i>Katrolceras giganteus</i> (Krishna et al. 1996) <i>Hybonoticeras kachhensis</i> or from below (see Krishna et al 1996).	K-I and K-II Katrolensis K-II Horizon is marked by the first appearance of morph II of <i>K. katrolensis</i> , i.e., the first abruptly modified primary rib appears in the middle of the second quarter of the body chamber. K-I Horizon is marked by the first appearance of morph I of <i>K. katrolensis</i> , i.e., the first abruptly modified (cuniformal) primary rib appears in the last quarter of the body chamber.	<p>Bathyplocus Zone (Krishna and Pathak 1991) Four Horizons: B-I to B-IV Horizons. These Horizons are based on the four successive transient morphs (morph I, morph II, morph III and morph IV) within the stratigraphic range of <i>T. bathyplocus</i>. They are based on position of the start of triplicate ribbing on the body chamber from the last quarter to near the start of the body chamber.</p> <p>Eudoxus</p>	
First appearance <i>T. bathyplocus</i> morphs III and IV <i>Pachysphinctes linguiferus</i> <i>Pachysphinctes major</i> <i>Torquatisphinctes jurunensis</i> <i>Indodichotomoceras inversum</i> <i>Aspidoceras wynnei</i> <i>Taramelliceras transitorius</i> Continue from below. <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i> , <i>Torquatisphinctes torquatus</i> <i>Pachysphinctes granti</i> <i>Indodichotomoceras</i> cf. <i>zitteli</i> <i>Aspidoceras caroli</i> <i>Aspidoceras lerensis</i> <i>Streblites leptodiscus</i> <i>Streblites plicodiscus</i> <i>Taramelliceras kachhensis</i> <i>Holcophylloceras mesolcum</i> , <i>Subnebrodites</i> sp.	B-III and B-IV Horizons Linguiferus B-IV Horizon is marked by the first appearance of <i>Taramelliceras transitorius</i> , as also of morph IV of <i>T. bathyplocus</i> in which the first triplicate rib appears in the first quarter of the body chamber. B-III Horizon <i>P. major</i> , <i>T. jurunensis</i> I. <i>inversum</i> , <i>A. wynnei</i> first appearance, as also of morph III of <i>T. bathyplocus</i> , in which the first triplicate rib appears in the beginning of the second quarter of the body chamber.		
First appearance <i>Torquatisphinctes bathyplocus</i> morphs I and II <i>Indodichotomoceras</i> cf. <i>zitteli</i> , <i>Aspidoceras lerensis</i> Continue from below <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i> , <i>T. torbuatus</i> , <i>Pachysphinctes granti</i> , <i>Taramelliceras kachhensis</i> , <i>Streblites plicodiscus</i> , <i>S. leptodiscus</i> <i>Aspidoceras acanthicum</i> , <i>A. iphiceroides</i> , <i>A. caroli</i> <i>Holcophylloceras mesolcum</i> Recorded from this zone <i>Subnebrodites</i> sp. (Krishna 2017), <i>Ptychophylloceras ptychoicum</i> (Quenstedt) (Krishna and Pathak 1991)	B-I and B-II Horizons Bathyplocus B-II Horizon is marked by the first appearance of morph II of <i>T. bathyplocus</i> , in which the first triplicate rib appears in the end of the second quarter of the body chamber. <i>Aspidoceras lerensis</i> Spath also starts in this horizon. B-I Horizon is marked by the first appearance of morph I of <i>T. bathyplocus</i> , in which the first triplicate rib appears in the last quarter of the body chamber.		
First appearance <i>Aspidoceras iphiceroides</i> <i>Streblites plicodiscus</i>	I-II to I-V Horizons Iphiceroides I-V Horizon is marked by the first appearance	Intermedius Zone (Krishna and Pathak 1991)	Acanthicum

<i>Streblites leptodiscus</i> <i>Torquatisphinctes torquatus</i> <i>Pachysphinctes granti</i> Continue from below <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i> <i>Aspidoceras acanthicum</i>	of <i>Pachysphinctes granti</i> . I-IV Horizon is marked by the first appearance of <i>Torquatisphinctes torquatus</i> I-III Horizon is indicated by the first appearance of <i>Streblites leptodiscus</i> I-II Horizon is marked by the first appearance of <i>Aspidoceras iphiceroides</i> and <i>Streblites plicodiscus</i>	Here it is proposed Acanthicum Zone because <i>A. acanthicum</i> shows first appearance in this zone whereas <i>T. intermedius</i> continue from below but found more in number	
First appearance <i>Aspidoceras acanthicum</i> Continue from below <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i>	I-I Horizon Acanthicum is marked by the first appearance of <i>Aspidoceras acanthicum</i>		
First appearance <i>Taramelliceras kachhensis</i> Continue from below <i>Torquatisphinctes alternepticatus</i> <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i>	A-II Horizon Kachhensis is marked by the first appearance of <i>Taramelliceras kachhensis</i>	Alternepticatus Zone (Krishna and Pathak 1991)	Divisum
First appearance <i>Torquatisphinctes alternepticatus</i> (Pandey et al 2010) <i>Torquatisphinctes intermedius</i>	A-I Horizon Alternepticatus is marked by the first appearance of the index <i>Torquatisphinctes alternepticatus</i>		
	These three Tethyan zones were first proposed from the Adhoi Member of Bharodia section of Wagad for the Kachchh Basin. These correspond to first appearance of <i>Orthosphinctes</i> (Bimammatum Subzone and Hauffianum Subzone in the lower part of Adhoi member, overlain by ca. 10 m apart two ammonoid levels in the upper part of Adhoi Member : (i) <i>Lithoceras</i> and (ii) <i>Ataxioceras</i> (Platynota Zone to Hypselocyclum Zone (Krishna et al. 2011: 149)	Giganticus Zone (Krishna 2017, Figs. 3.32-3.33) from Bharodia	Hypselocyclum Platynota
First appearance <i>Orthosphinctes kachhensis</i> <i>Wegelea</i> aff. <i>gredingensis</i> (Wegele) and <i>Subnebrodites</i> cf. <i>minutum</i> (Dietrich) (Krishna 2017: 115)		Kachchhensis Zone (Krishna 2017: 115)	Planula

5. SYSTEMATIC PALAEOLOGY

The dimensions measured are illustrated in Fig. 4. Figures between brackets are percentual ratios of *H*, *W*, and *U* to *D*. Measurements of the ammonites are presented in the Appendix 1. Macroconch abbreviated with [M], and microconch with [m]. The figured ammonites are housed in the collections of the Department of Geology, University of Rajasthan, under the prefixes RUC2015, RUC2016, RUC2017 and RUC2018. The year of collection of the specimens is indicated, sometimes followed by roman letters I or II to indicate the first or second field survey in that year. Additional abbreviations: RUC - Rajasthan University Collection, KH - Kas Hill section, LOD - Lodai section, JH - Jhuran River section, GD - Gangeshwar Dome section.

Fig. 4. Measured dimensions and used abbreviations (modified from Alberti *et al.*, 2011).

Class Cephalopoda Cuvier, 1797
Order Ammonitida Haeckel, 1866
Suborder Phylloceratina Arkell, 1950
Superfamily Phylloceratoidea Zittel, 1884
Family Phylloceratidae Zittel, 1884
Subfamily Calliphylloceratinae Spath, 1927
Genus *Holcophylloceras* Spath, 1927

Type species: *Phylloceras mediterraneum* Neumayr, 1871a.

***Holcophylloceras* cf. *polyolcum* (Benecke, 1865)**
Pl. I, figs 1-3

- cf. 1865. *Ammonites polyolcus* Benecke, p. 182, pl. 7.
- cf. ?1871. *Phylloceras polyolcum* Benecke – Neumayr, p. 341, pl. 17, figs. 6-7.
- cf. 1927. *Holcophylloceras* aff. *polyolcum* (Benecke) – Spath, p. 60, pl. 6, figs. 1-2, pl. 7, fig. 5 (extensive synonymy).
- cf. 2000. *Holcophylloceras polyolcum* (Benecke) – Joly, p. 101, pl. 25, fig. 4; Fig. 208.

Material: One specimen (RUC2016 IKH 07) from the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Upper Kimmeridgian, Katrolensis Zone) of the Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

Description: Phragmocone involute, whorl section compressed, oval with acutely rounded ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of very fine, thread-like ribs and prominent, deep, strongly curved, angled

constrictions. Constrictions numbering six on outer preserved whorl of the phragmocone, prorsiradiate on inner half, sharply turning rursiradiate, running with slight forward-directed concavity on outer lateral half and crossing ventral region. Umbilical wall steep but low.

Remarks: The six constrictions in the present specimen distinctly differentiates it from *Holcophylloceras mediterraneum* (Neumayr) illustrated by Spath (1927, p. 58, pl. 5, fig. 1) with 9 to 10 constrictions and matches *H. aff. polyolcum* (Benecke) recorded by Spath (1927, p. 60, pl. 6, figs. 1-2, pl. 7, fig. 5) from the Katrol beds of the Kachchh Basin and *H. zignodianum* (d'Orbigny, 1848) recorded by Seyed-Emami (2013, p. 45, fig. 4a-b) from the Dalichai Formation west of Shahrud, North Iran. The *Holcophylloceras mediterraneum* described by Neumayr (1871, p. 340, pl. 17, fig. 2) shows seven constrictions and lacks the angularity between the inner and outer parts of the constrictions. The umbilical diameter at a comparable shell diameter in *H. mediterraneum* is larger (18% with respect to diameter) than in the present specimen (13%). In contrast, the umbilical diameter of *H. zignodianum* (d'Orbigny, 1848) is small (only 10%). The umbilical diameter in the present specimen is similar to that in *H. aff. polyolcum* (Benecke) discussed by Spath that ranges from 12% to 14%. According to Spath (1927, p. 60) the number of constrictions at a lower diameter (e.g., 50 mm) in both species varies from 5 to 7, and there are also several examples of *H. polyolcum*, recorded by Neumayr from the Acanthicum Zone (Spath, 1927, p. 60) showing eleven to twelve constrictions at a diameter of 100 mm. In lack of information on the number of constrictions even on the outer whorl of the adult phragmocone, it is difficult to precisely identify the present specimen.

Provenance: Neumayr (1871a, p. 341) recorded the species from the Acanthicum Zone (Spath, 1927, p. 60). Spath (1927) recorded 35 specimens of this species from the Katrol beds (= Jhuran Formation). He tentatively mentioned the species to range from the "Argovian" (Oxfordian) "to Tithonian?"

Subfamily Ptychophylloceratinae Collignon, 1956
Genus *Ptychophylloceras* Spath, 1927

Type species: *Phylloceras feddeni* Waagen, 1875.

***Ptychophylloceras cf. ptychoicum* (Quenstedt, 1845)**
Pl. I, figs 4-6

cf. 1845. *Ammonites ptychoicus* Quenstedt, p. 219, pl. 17, fig. 12.

cf. 1875. *Phylloceras ptychoicum* (Quenstedt) – Waagen, p. 30, pl. 7, fig. 2a-c.

cf. 2013b. *Ptychophylloceras ptychoicum* (Quenstedt) – Pandey *et al.*, p. 142, pl. 1, fig. 2; fig. 4B.

Material: One specimen (RUC2016 ILOD 26) from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, involute, compressed. Whorl section suboval to subrounded with broad, convex venter and steep undercut umbilical slope. Shell smooth except for 9-10 widely spaced rib-like ridges confined to the venter at regular intervals.

Remarks: The shell is poorly preserved, and the umbilical wall has been widened during preparation. As suture lines are not visible, the last whorl may represent the body chamber. The whorl section and the nine to ten widely and regularly spaced rib-like ridges confined to the ventral region match *Ptychophylloceras* Spath, 1927. The dimensional proportions are close to *P. ptychoicum* (Quenstedt, 1845). The umbilical diameter is slightly larger than that of *P. ptychoicum* and the H/W ratio is lower, hence the assignment is with qualification.

Provenance: Waagen (1875, p. 30) recorded the species from the Katrol Group east of Ler. Spath (1927, p. 46) recorded this species from the Late Kimmeridgian Beckeri Zone (see also Krishna & Pathak, 1991). In fact, the species is long ranging, well-known from Tithonian to Lower Cretaceous strata of Europe (e.g., Joly, 2000; Lukeneder, 2004, 2005). Pandey *et al.* (2013a, p. 142) recorded it from the Late Oxfordian upper Bifurcatus Zone in the eastern Kachchh Basin.

Suborder Ammonitina Fischer, 1882
Superfamily Haploceratoidea Zittel, 1884
Family Oppeliidae Bonarelli, 1894
Subfamily Taramelliceratinae Spath, 1925
Genus *Taramelliceras* Del Campana, 1904

Type species: *Ammonites trachinotus* Oppel, 1863

***Taramelliceras kachhensis* (Waagen, 1875)**
Pl. II, figs 1-6

1875. *Oppelia kachhensis* Waagen, p. 55, pl. 10, fig. 4, a, b.

1928. *Taramelliceras kachhensis* (Waagen) – Spath, p. 134, pl. 8, figs. 2a, b, 4, pl. 14, figs. 6, 12, 13, pl. 17, fig. 3a, b, pl. 18, figs. 1a, b, 6.

2021. *Taramelliceras kachhense* (Waagen) – Roy *et al.*, p. 273, Figs. 2-6.

Material: Two specimens (RUC2016 IKH 34, 52) from the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

Description: Shell involute, compressed, whorl section oval with broad dome-shaped venter. Strong ventrolateral tubercles on both sides of median ventral row of smaller nodes. Ornamentation consisting of

moderately thick falcoid ribs bifurcating slightly below mid-lateral height. Primary ribs prorsiradiate, turning rursiradiate at branching points. Secondary ribs with slight forward-directed concavity on upper half of flank, alternately terminating at ventrolateral shoulder with strong tubercles.

Remarks: The present specimens represent inner whorls, smaller than those of *Taramelliceras kachhensis* in Waagen (1875, pl. 10, fig. 4, a, b) and Spath (1928, pl. 14, fig. 6, pl. 18, fig. 6). The other specimens illustrated by Spath are larger in diameter and mostly smooth or exhibit a very feeble ornamentation on the inner whorls. The dimensional proportions, ornamentation of the inner whorls, and the whorl section of our two specimens closely match the species. The thick falcoid ribs and secondary ribs alternately terminating at the ventrolateral shoulder with strong tubercles on the inner whorls distinguish *T. kachhensis* from all other species of *Taramelliceras* such as *T. compsum* (Oppel, 1863, p. 215, pl. 57, fig. 1a, b; see also Baudouin *et al.*, 2011; Bujtor *et al.*, 2021, p. 275, fig. 6A1-A3), which is morphologically close (Spath, 1928; Pandey *et al.*, 2022).

In contrast, Roy *et al.* (2021), based on morphometric analysis using multivariate data from the specimens of *Taramelliceras* in collection of Geological Survey of India, Kolkata and the specimens collected by them from the Kimmeridgian of the Kachchh Basin concluded similarity in all the species described by Spath (1927) and also between *T. kachhense* and the Sub-Mediterranean *T. compsum* figured by Baudouin *et al.* (2011). Further, they inferred that *T. kachhensis* is only a geographic variant of *T. compsum*.

Provenance: The specimen of Waagen (1875) came from north of Ler, whereas the material of Spath is from the Late Kimmeridgian Eudoxus (and Beckeri ?) Zone of the eastern part of the basin.

Genus *Metahaploceras* Spath, 1925

Type species: *Metahaploceras strombecki* Oppel, 1858.

Metahaploceras cf. pascoei Spath, 1928

Pl. II, figs 7-13

cf. 1928. *Metahaploceras pascoei* Spath, p. 147, pl. 8, fig. 3a, b.

Material: Four specimens (RUC2015 JH 3, 19, 27, 28) from units 9 and 10 of the Jhuran River section, i.e. the lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (coordinates 23°21'32.7"N, 69°59'48.4"E); early Late Kimmeridgian (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone). This part of the section is overlying the Belemnite Marls of the Jhuran river section mentioned in Spath (1928).

Description: Shell compressed and involute. Whorl section oval with moderately rounded ventral region. Umbilicus small with steep umbilical wall.

Phragmocone ornamented with fine ribs with forward-directed sinuosity at ventral region. Body chamber smooth, with pairs of ventrolateral tubercles and feeble ribs showing forward-directed sinuosity.

Remarks: The specimen RUC2015 JH 3 is almost complete, the other three specimens are represented only by part of the body chamber. Due to the poor state of preservation the ornamentation pattern of the phragmocone is not discernible. The ventral region of the phragmocone is acute and not arched as in *Metahaploceras pascoei* Spath, 1928 (pl. 8, fig. 3a, b). This may be due to compaction or intraspecific variation. The three fragmentary specimens (RUC2015 JH 19, 27, 28) match *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen, 1875) in whorl section (described below), but the presence of pairs of ventrolateral tubercles easily differentiate them from the genus *Streblites* Hyatt, 1900. In one of these specimens (RUC2015 JH 27) ribs bifurcate and the branches display a forward-directed sinuosity. This feature has not been reported by Spath (1928). The ventrolateral tubercles in the present fragmentary specimens of the body chamber can be easily confused with the outer part of the body chamber of *T. kachhensis* (Waagen, 1875, pl. 10, fig. 4; Spath, 1928, pl. 8, figs. 2a, b, 4; pl. 14, fig. 12). However, the tubercles in *M. pascoei* are small, elongated and forwardly inclined, whereas in *T. kachhensis* they are large and circular in the base.

Provenance: Spath (1928) recorded this species from the Belemnite Marls of the Jhuran River section, the oldest Kimmeridgian horizon of the Kachchh Basin, and assigned it to the Tenuilobatus Zone (Early Kimmeridgian).

Subfamily Streblitinae Spath, 1925

Genus *Streblites* Hyatt, 1900

Type species: *Ammonites tenuilobatus* Oppel, 1862

Streblites plicodiscus (Waagen, 1875)

Pl. II, figs 14-15, Pl. III, figs 1-6

1875. *Oppelia plicodiscus* Waagen, p. 56, pl. 10, fig. 5.

1903. *Oppelia (Streblites) plicodiscus* Waagen – Uhlig, p. 38.

1928. *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen) – Spath, p. 148, pl. 16, fig. 2, pl. 17, fig. 1.

1928. *Streblites leptodiscus* Spath, p. 150, pl. 16, fig. 1.

1959. *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen) – Collignon, pl. 111, figs 409, 410.

1959. *Streblites habyensis* Spath – Collignon, pl. 111, fig. 411.

1984. *Streblites habyensis* Spath – Verma & Westermann, p. 36, pl. 3, fig. 3.

2013b. *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen) – Pandey *et al.*, p. 101, pl. 1, fig. 1a–c, fig. 4A.

Material: Eight specimens (RUC2015 JH 4-6, 25, 33, 60, RUC2016 JH 1, 6), from units 9 and 10 of the

Jhuran River section, (early Late Kimmeridgian, Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Oxyconic with acutely rounded ventral region. Flanks gently sloping towards venter, ornamented with wide, faint falcoid ribs bifurcating from mid-flank. Mid-ventral line with serrated keel. Suture consisting of wide median saddle, wide and deep lateral lobe, and four or five umbilical lobes of diminishing depth.

Remarks: The specimens are moderately well preserved, incomplete with small part of the body chamber or phragmocones or body chambers. However, the flat spiral furrow on the middle of the flank, mentioned by Waagen (1875, p. 56) is not seen in any of the specimens of the present collection. One of the specimens (RUC2015 JH 60) shows an ornamentation rather similar to that of *Uhligites* Kilian, 1907. Only in this specimen, the early part of the whorl shows a serrated keel.

Streblites plicodiscus has not been adequately described and illustrated. The specimen described by Waagen (1875, pl. 10, fig. 5, 5a) from south of Madapur ("Madapoor" between Hamundra and Ler) is very small (diameter approximately 30 mm). The specimens examined by Spath (1928, p. 148), from Kimmeridgian strata of the Kachchh Basin, show much better the morphological characters, and accordingly *S. plicodiscus* also includes shells feebly ornamented or smooth. *S. habyensis* Spath, 1928 (p. 151, pl. 8, fig. 1) is characterised by its slightly stronger ribs. Six of the specimens from the same horizon and locality (RUC2015 JH 4, 5, 25, 33, RUC2016 JH 1) display an oxyconic form, narrow acutely rounded venter, occasionally forward-inclined secondary ribs at the periphery and a serrated keel similar to *S. plicodiscus* (Waagen), but the lower and middle parts of the flanks of the outer whorls are smooth. Occasionally, the shell is more inflate in the inner part of the whorl and less so, perhaps due to compaction, in the outer part of the whorl. These specimens match more closely *Streblites leptodiscus* Spath, 1928. Considering that the feeble ornamentation of part of the shell could have been obliterated during fossilization, and based on the similarity of other morphological features, such as oxyconic form, narrow acutely rounded venter, small umbilicus, presence of secondary ribs along the periphery, and serrated keel, *S. leptodiscus* has been merged with *S. plicodiscus*. The outer whorls of *S. plicodiscus* can be confused with *Metahaploceras* (discussed above) but the absence of ventro-lateral tubercles in *S. plicodiscus* easily differentiates it from *Metahaploceras*.

According to Waagen (1875, p. 56), the closest comparable taxon is the Late Kimmeridgian *Oppelia tenuilobata* (Oppel, 1862). *Streblites plicodiscus* of the Kachchh Basin and *Oppelia tenuilobata* (Oppel, 1862) belong to the group of *Oppelia subtililobata* (Waagen 1869, p. 226) according to Waagen (1875, p. 47).

According to Neumayr (1873, p. 163) and Waagen (1875, p. 56), *O. tenuilobata* is a descendent of the Callovian *O. subtililobata* (see also Uhlig, 1903, p. 38). This implies that the phylogenetic lineage ranges from the Late Callovian up to the Tithonian.

Provenance: Spath (1928, p. 150) recorded *S. plicodiscus* from the Eudoxus Zone (middle Late Kimmeridgian) of Fakirwadi, Walakhavas and Katrol Hill. It is one of the guide species of the Iphiceroides Subzone of the Intermedius Zone of Krishna & Pathak (1991) and Krishna *et al.* (1996), here considered correlated with the Acanthicum Zone of the North Tethys margin (Cariou & Hantzpergue 1997). Krishna (2017, p. 117) revised his earlier assumption and stated that *S. plicodiscus* made its first appearance at the base of the Bathyplocus Zone (= Eudoxus Zone). The species has also been recorded from the Hybonotum and the Acanthicum zones of Madagascar (Collignon, 1959), the Hybonotum Zone of Kenya (Verma & Westermann, 1984), and from Kimmeridgian to Early Tithonian? strata of the Freretown clay pit of Mombasa, Kenya (Schweigert *et al.*, 2012).

Superfamily Perisphinctoidea Steinmann, in Steinmann & Döderlein, 1890

Family Ataxioceratidae Buckman, 1921

Subfamily Ataxioceratinae Buckman, 1921

Genus Progeronia Arkell, 1953

[= *Hugueninsphinctes* Atrops (1982), type species: *Ammonites breviceps* Quenstedt, 1887; OD]

Type species: *Perisphinctes progeron* von Ammon, 1875; OD

***Progeronia digitata* (Schneid, 1915)**

Pl. III, figs 7-10

1915. *Perisphinctes digitatus* Schneid, p. 94, pl. 3, fig. 1.

1994. *Progeronia digitatus* (Schneid) – Schlegelmilch, p. 77, pl. 30, fig. 1.

Material: One specimen (RUC2015 JH 20) from unit 12 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell large, evolute, whorl section oval, compressed with acutely arched ventral region. Ornamentation on outer whorl consisting of thick, distantly placed, prorsiradiate primary ribs, irregularly bi- or trifurcating, or polygyrate. Secondary ribs start slightly below mid-lateral height, long, fasciculate with at least one free intercalatory rib between two adjacent branching primary ribs. Primary ribs starting thin, rursiradiate and turning thick, prorsiradiate at the umbilical shoulder with slight forward-directed concavity. Secondary ribs thinner, crossing ventral region with forward-directed sinuosity.

Remarks: The fragmentary specimen is part of the body chamber. The ornamentation matches that of the genus *Progeronia* (Énay & Howarth, 2019, p. 118). Geyer (1961) illustrated several species of *Progeronia* from the lower Lower Kimmeridgian of southern Germany, but all of them show longer and denser primary ribs, similar to the example described and illustrated by Gygi (2003, p. 87, fig. 94) as *Progeronia* (*Hugueninsphinctes*) sp. from the Lower Kimmeridgian (Hypsolocyclum Zone) of northern Switzerland. Fözy *et al.* (2022) illustrated a few species of *Progeronia* from Páskom Hill (Bakony Mountains, Hungary), but these differ in higher points of branching and finer ornamentation (Fözy *et al.*, 2022, pl. 30, figs. 1, 3, 4, 6). Fözy *et al.* (2022, p. 262) also mentioned that there is a group of coarse-ribbed perisphinctids (e.g., *Perisphinctes digitatus*) in the Submediterranean Faunal Province that was tentatively assigned to *Progeronia* by Schlegelmilch (1994, p. 77, pl. 30, fig. 1). The present specimen with comparatively coarse ribs matches *Progeronia digitata* (Schneid). According to Fözy *et al.* (2022, p. 262) *P. digitata* should belong to a different genus, but the morphology of the present specimen, particularly coiling, whorl section and ornamentation, corresponds to *Progeronia* Arkell.

Provenance: Late Early Kimmeridgian Divisum Zone (= *Alterneplicatus* Zone) to Late Kimmeridgian Acanthicum Zone (= *Intermedius* Zone). This is the first record of the genus from the Indian Subcontinent. In southern Germany it starts in the Hypselocyclum Zone, but its acme is in the Divisum to Acanthicum Zone (Geyer, 1961; Cariou & Hantzpergue 1997; Gygi, 2003; Schick, 2004; also, personal communication from Günter Schweigert, 2024). Schick (2004) also introduced a lithostratigraphic term “Progeronienschichten” for this interval.

Subfamily Torquatisphinctinae Tavera, 1985

Genus *Torquatisphinctes* Spath, 1924

Type species: *Ammonites torquatus* J. de C. Sowerby, 1840

Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus (Waagen, 1875) [m] & [M]

Pl. IV, figs 1-6, Pl. V, figs 1-6

1875. *Perisphinctes alterneplicatus* Waagen, p. 199, pl. 50, fig. 2a, b.

1931. *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen) – Spath, p. 477, pl. 87, fig. 1a, b.

2013b. *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen) – Pandey *et al.*, p. 112, pl. 4, fig. 2a, b; fig. 7A–E; Tabl. 1

Material: Four microconchs (RUC2016 IJH 23, RUC2016 IILOD 1, RUC2016 IIJH 8, RUC2015 JH 11) and one macroconch (RUC2016 IJH 6) from units 9 and 10 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the

Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation; and from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Microconch - Shell small, wholly septate, evolute. Whorl section slightly depressed, subquadrangular in outline with flat to slightly arched flanks merging into feebly convex venter with obtusely rounded ventrolateral shoulder. Ornamentation consisting of fine, sharp, dense, varicostate ribs. Primary ribs originating close to umbilical suture, running rursiradially over low but steep umbilical wall, bending prorsiradially with broad curve just above umbilical shoulder and bifurcating slightly below the ventrolateral shoulder into secondary ribs. Commonly, after one, two or three branching pairs, single, undivided primary ribs on one side joining secondary ribs on other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern of ribs. Secondary ribs crossing the venter either with slight forward-directed sinuosity or without any sinuosity. Constrictions moderately distinct, at least two per whorls, slightly more inclined than the preceding ribs, subsequent ribs running parallel to constrictions.

Macroconch - Shell large, septate, whorl section subtrapezoidal, suboval to subtriangular with high, slightly arched umbilical wall, moderately distinct umbilical shoulder, slightly arched to almost flat flanks merging smoothly with convex, moderately broad ventral region. Ventral region at outermost preserved whorl narrower than in inner whorls. Ornamentation consisting of very fine, closely spaced, prorsiradial primary ribs, increasingly thicker and more distant with increasing diameter, branching just above mid-lateral height. Single primary ribs common on inner whorls, almost after each bifurcating pair of ribs continuing as single rib on other side. Primary ribs on outer part of phragmocone thick, distant and with additional free secondary ribs between each two pairs of branching ribs. Rarely, third secondary rib starting quite close to paired one and appearing triplicate (or “sub-triplets”, sensu Spath, 1931, p. 488). Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight or without forward-directed convexity. Outermost preserved part of phragmocone (at diameter ~230 mm) exhibiting thick, forward-inclined, distant folds with traces of suture lines. Number of ribs 60 for half whorl at 170 mm diameter. Constrictions distinct, moderately deep.

Remarks: The four smaller specimens (RUC2016 IJH 23, RUC2016 IILOD 1, RUC2016 IIJH 8, RUC2015 JH 11) represent parts of phragmocones. The size, dimensional proportions, whorl section and ornamentation match *T. alterneplicatus* and suggest they are microconchs. *T. alterneplicatus* is a commonly occurring guide ammonite with an early Late Kimmeridgian age in the Kachchh Basin. *T. intermedius* Spath, 1931, another guide ammonite of the Kachchh Kimmeridgian can be easily differentiated from the precursor zonal species *T. alterneplicatus* on the bases

of rib density and whorl thickness. The ornamentation and the umbilical diameter of inner whorls of *T. tenuistriatus* Spath, 1931 are quite like those in one of the specimens (RUC2016 IJH 23), but *T. tenuistriatus* is more depressed and there are “about four flexiradiate constrictions” in *T. tenuistriatus*, which are straight in the present specimen.

The fifth example (RUC2016 IJH 6) representing a major part of a phragmocone is a large specimen. The outermost whorl, showing traces of distinct suture lines, is poorly preserved and slightly distorted. The traces of the succeeding whorl on the last preserved part of the phragmocone show rapid uncoiling of the shell. If reconstructed, the total size of this specimen would be approximately 300 mm. The large size, whorl section including high umbilical wall, dimensional proportions, and alternate branching and single primary ribs match *T. alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875, p. 199, pl. 50, 2a, b; Spath, 1931, p. 477, pl. 87, 1a, b; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b, p. 112, pl. 4, fig. 2a, b; fig. 7A–E; Tabl. 1) and suggest a macroconch. Another large specimen (RUC2016 IJH 9) described below as macroconch of *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, 1931 exhibits finer and less distant ribs. *T. torquatus* is another comparable species in respect of whorl section including high umbilical wall and dimensional proportions but differs in ornamentation. All previously described specimens of *T. alterneplicatus* and *T. torquatus* from the Kachchh Basin are small (ranging from 57–115 mm in diameter) compared to the present specimen. The holotype of *T. alterneplicatus* (Spath, 1931, p. 477) also contains the body chamber despite its small size, whereas the present large specimen represents only the phragmocone. Waagen (1875, p. 199) mentioned that “in large specimens, contractions of the shell are very scarce and very indistinct” (Waagen, 1875, pl. 50, fig. 2).

The large species from the same locality as the present large specimen, described by Spath as *T. jurunensis* Spath (1931, pl. 76, figs. 1a, b), differs in having a compressed whorl section, large umbilical diameter and rectiradiate ribs, particularly those of the inner whorls. The specimen of *T. jurunensis* recorded by Spath is nearly complete with body chamber, whereas the present specimen, at a similar diameter, is still septate. In addition, in *T. jurunensis*, a third intercalated secondary rib first appears on the body chamber, whereas this is quite common on the outer whorl of the phragmocone in the present specimen.

Thick, forward-inclined, distant folds with traces of distinct suture lines on the outermost preserved part of the phragmocone (at a diameter of ~230 mm) are recorded here for the first time.

***Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) [m]
& [M]**

morph neglecta (in Spath, 1931)

Pl. VI, figs 1–6, Pl. VI, figs 7–10

1931. *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen) var. neglecta Spath, p. 478, pl. 84, fig. 3.

Material: 15 microconchs (RUC2015 JH 8, 16, 30, 42, 43A, RUC2016 IJH 23, 25, RUC2016 ILOD 2-4, 14, 17, 18, RUC2016 GD 3, 4) and one macroconch (RUC2015 JH 38) from units 9, 10 and 12 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation; from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation; and from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Microconch - Shell small, incomplete, evolute and depressed. Whorl section subrounded in outline becoming subquadrangular. Flanks feebly arched, merging smoothly into a feebly convex venter. Ornamentation consisting of fine, sharp, dense, varicostate ribs. Primary ribs originating near umbilical suture, running rursiradially across low umbilical wall, bending prorsiradially with broad curve just above latero-umbilical shoulder, then running straight and bifurcating below ventrolateral shoulder into two secondary ribs. Commonly, after two to three branching pairs, single, undivided primary ribs on one side join secondary ribs on other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern of ribs on ventral region. Secondary ribs crossing venter straight or with slight forward directed sinuosity. Constrictions distinct, at least two per whorls, either parallel to ribs or slightly more inclined than preceding ribs; ribs following constrictions arranged parallel to them.

Macroconch - Shell large, incomplete, evolute and slightly depressed. Whorl section suboval with increasing diameter. Flanks feebly arched to flat, merging smoothly into a convex venter. Ornamentation consisting of fine, sharp, dense, varicostate ribs. Primary ribs originating near umbilical shoulder, running prorsiradially with forward-directed concavity leaving most part of umbilical wall smooth. Commonly, after two to three branching pairs, a single, undivided primary rib on one side joining a secondary rib on other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern of ribs. Similarly, one of the secondary ribs of a primary rib on one side becoming a secondary rib of adjacent bifurcating primary rib on other side. Secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with slight forward-directed sinuosity. Constrictions distinct, at least two per whorls, either parallel to ribs or slightly forwardly inclined.

Remarks: Out of 16 specimens, 15 are small and poorly preserved. Some are wholly septate and others contain a small portion of the body chamber. The dimensional proportions, whorl sections and ornamentation match *T. alterneplicatus* var. neglecta (Spath, 1931, pl. 84, fig. 3) and suggest it would be a microconch. The dimensional proportions change with increasing diameter. In comparison to *T. alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875, pl. 50, fig. 2; Spath, 1931, pl. 87, fig. 1a, b), the whorl section is rounded at a smaller

diameter, the ribs are slightly coarser, the primary ribs are shorter, and constrictions are more distinct.

The sixteenth specimen (RUC2015 JH 38) is large and poorly preserved. It contains a large part of the body chamber. The diameter of the phragmocone is 120 mm. Nevertheless, the dimensional proportions, whorl section, and ornamentation match *T. alterneplicatus* var. *neglecta*. The density of ribs in this large specimen is close to that in *T. acuticostatus* (described below), but the primary ribs in *T. acuticostatus* are long and straight, whereas in RUC2015 JH 38 they are comparatively short, slightly flexuous and broadly concave forward-directed. Based on the variation in the morphological features and their similarity with *T. alterneplicatus*, they all can be considered as variants (morphotypes) of a single species (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b, p. 112). The specimens have been recorded from the same horizon as the specimens assigned to *T. alterneplicatus*.

Provenance: The specimens described here suggest the early Late Kimmeridgian Acanthicum Zone. The specimen figured by Spath (1931, pl. 84, fig. 3) assigned to *T. alterneplicatus* var. *neglecta* come from the Kimmeridgian (Katrol beds), east of Ler. Some other specimens of the collection of Smith, from the Lower Katrol Beds at Fakirwadi, Ler and east of Ler, may also be referred to the *T. alterneplicatus* var. *neglecta* (Spath, 1931, p. 479).

***Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**
Pl. VII, figs 1-8, Pl. VIII, figs 1-2

1931. *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, p. 482, pl. 81, fig. 3, pl. 82, fig. 6.

Material: 10 microconchs (RUC2016 IJH 15, RUC2015 JH 34, 35, 37, 40B, 44, 57, RUC2016 IJH 7, 9, RUC2015 GD 31) and one macroconch (RUC2016 IJH 9) from units 9, 10, and 12 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation; and from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section; Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shells large (M) and moderately large (m), evolute, inner whorls depressed, outer whorls gradually becoming more compressed. Whorl section of inner whorls subquadrate to subrounded, those of outer whorl with slightly arched flanks merging with broadly rounded ventrolateral shoulder into broadly arched venter. Umbilical wall low, slightly convex. Ornamentation consisting of sharp, varicostate, long primary ribs, which originate near umbilical suture rursiradially, turn prorsiradial at umbilical shoulder, running consistently forward with a slight concavity on flanks. Primary ribs regularly branching into secondary ribs just below ventrolateral shoulder or slightly below umbilical suture for succeeding whorl. Single primary ribs after one, two, three or four branching ribs.

Commonly, after two to three branching pairs, a single, undivided primary rib on one side joining as secondary rib on other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern of ribs. Occasionally two adjacent parallel ribs following constrictions or occurring without constriction. Outer part of phragmocone either with free intercalatory secondary ribs (or “sub-triplets” sensu Spath, 1931: 488) or with a trifurcating rib. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight or no forward-directed sinuosity. Anterior secondary ribs, when approaching constriction, showing more pronounced forward-directed inclination and sinuosity. Constrictions well-developed, up to six per whorl.

Remarks: The specimens are well preserved. The larger specimen (e.g., RUC2015 JH 9) is incomplete, without body chamber. The moderately large specimens RUC2015 JH 34, 35 are almost complete, but the peristome is not well preserved. The specimen RUC2016 IJH 7 is somewhat similar to *Torquatisphinctes* gr. *primus-similis* Spath, 1931 (described below) with respect to its compressed whorl section at the corresponding diameter, but the ornamentation, including the number of ribs at the periphery, match *T. intermedius* Spath. There is no strict regularity in the intervals of constrictions in the specimens of the present collection. All the specimens are preserved with shell. Suture lines are well-preserved. The dimensional proportions and ornamentation of these specimens match *T. intermedius* Spath. The specimen RUC2015 JH 37 apparently exhibits thicker ribs on the inner whorls, but the ornamentation on the outer whorls and the dimensional proportions are exactly as those of the specimens RUC2015 JH 34 and 35. The thickness of ribs in such cases may be a preservational feature. In the present material, two categories of ammonites can be distinguished: (1) those with a large diameter, still septate at 215 mm (RUC2016 IJH 9; macroconch), but with a decrease in the number of primary ribs at approximately 170 mm, and (2) those with a small diameter (microconch), septate until 120 mm, two-thirds of the last whorl representing the body chamber and showing an increase in the number of primary ribs at least up to 185 mm diameter.

The small specimen RUC2015 GD 31 from Gangeshwar Dome consists of the phragmocone and a small part of the body chamber. It has prorsiradial, varicostate ribs (thin, closely spaced on inner whorls, gradually becoming thicker and distant on the outer whorl), bifurcating above mid-lateral height, occasionally single ribs, secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with broad forward-directed sinuosity, and constrictions. It represents a microconch.

T. alterneplicatus var. *neglecta* is also similar in whorl section and ornamentation but has a smaller umbilical diameter than *T. intermedius*, a guide fossil of the Kachchh Kimmeridgian Intermedius Zone (Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009, 2011). *T. intermedius* can be easily differentiated from the precursor zonal species *T.*

alterneplicatus based on its increased whorl thickness as compared to the whorl height. The whorl section is sub-quadrangle with a wider and more flattened ventral region. The holotype of *T. alterneplicatus* is 115 mm in diameter with two-thirds of the last whorl being the body chamber. At this diameter, the number of primary ribs is 45 per half whorl, whereas in the present specimens, there are 10 to 15 fewer primary ribs at the corresponding diameter. Consequently, *T. alterneplicatus* is more densely ribbed than *T. intermedius*.

***Torquatisphinctes torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby, 1840)**

Pl. VIII, figs 3-5

1840. *Ammonites torquatus* J. de C. Sowerby, p. 719, pl. 61, fig. 12 and explanation.

1931. *Torquatisphinctes torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby) – Spath, p. 475, pl. 76, fig. 4a, b.

2019. *Torquatisphinctes torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby) – Énay & Howarth, p. 132, Fig. 90.1 (refigured from Spath, 1931, pl. 76, fig. 4a, b).

Material: One specimen (RUC2017 IGD 7) from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Specimen consisting of inner part of phragmocone, evolute, depressed, whorl section subquadrangular with short, steeply inclined umbilical wall, moderately distinct umbilical shoulder, and slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with convex, moderately broad ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of very fine, closely spaced, prorsiradiate primary ribs, increasingly thicker and distant with increasing diameter, branching above mid-lateral height and below ventrolateral shoulder. Single primaries after two, three or four bifurcating ribs, continuing as single ribs on other side, joining secondary ribs on other side, or fading out. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with no or slight forward-directed convexity. Number of ribs per whorl varying from 56 at 31 mm diameter to 87 at 98 mm diameter. Constrictions shallow.

Remarks: The ornamentation, whorl section and dimensional proportions best match *T. torquatus* (Spath, 1931, pl. 76, fig. 4a, b), but the umbilical wall appears lower in the present specimen. The number of ribs per whorls as mentioned by Spath (1931, p. 475) is also within the range.

***Torquatisphinctes cf. jurunensis* Spath, 1931**

Pl. IX, figs 8-10

cf. 1931. *Torquatisphinctes jurunensis* Spath, p. 488, pl. 76, fig. 1a, b.

Material: Four specimens (RUC2016 IJH 1, RUC2015 JH 10, 53, RUC2017 IGD 9) from units 9 and 10 of the

Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation; and from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Specimens moderately large, evolute, depressed, whorl section subquadrangle with high, steep umbilical wall, moderately distinct umbilical shoulder, and flattened to slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with convex, moderately broad ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of varicostate, rectiradiate to prorsiradiate, sharp, closely spaced primary ribs, increasingly thicker and distant with increasing diameter, branching below ventro-lateral shoulder. Single primary ribs common on phragmocone after one, two or three bifurcating pairs of ribs. Single primary ribs on one side commonly corresponding to bifurcating ribs on other side, a few intercalatory secondary ribs on body chamber. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with obvious forward-directed convexity or straight. Number of ribs on the ventral region 57 per half whorl at 133 mm diameter (phragmocone). Constrictions distinct, moderately deep, oblique to preceding ribs.

Remarks: The specimen RUC2016 IJH 1 represents a phragmocone, whereas RUC2015 IJH 10 and RUC2017 IGD 9 are fragments of the body chamber. The ribs are sharper, partially rectiradiate, coarser and more distant, without obvious forward-directed convexity and the umbilicus is slightly larger in the present specimens than in the large specimen described here as macroconch of *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875). The thickness of ribs on the inner whorls is like that of *T. torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby). The ornamentation, i.e. ribs lacking obvious forward-directed convexity at the venter, intercalated secondary ribs (Spath, 1931, p. 488, termed this pattern as subtrifid) on the body chamber, and dimensional proportions are as in *T. jurunensis* Spath (1931, pl. 76, fig. 1a, b), but at a smaller diameter the shells RUC2016 IJH 1, RUC2017 IGD 9 are slightly depressed. The two large fragments of body chamber (RUC2015 IJH 10 and RUC2017 IGD 9) show some affinity to *T. acuticostatus* Spath (1931, pl. 88, figs. 2a, b, 10a-c) with respect to the sharp, long, occasionally flexuous primary ribs and straight secondary ribs on the ventral region but differ in having higher and wider whorl sections at the end of the phragmocone/beginning of body chamber, slightly more distant ribs and a slightly larger umbilical diameter. In lack of any further information, the present specimens are assigned to *T. jurunensis* Spath with qualification.

In cases of overall similarity between two morphospecies that have only minor differences in dimensions, sympatric speciation may have occurred due to differences in niche occupation. The width of the umbilicus is a function of tightness of coiling and rate of increase of diameter of the whorl. These parameters may change in niches that differ with respect to hydrostatic pressure, water energy, and/or prey

(necessity to be very active or fast swimmer), see Ebbighausen & Korn (2007) and Lukeneder (2015).

***Torquatisphinctes acuticostatus* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**

Pl. IX, figs 1-7

1931. *Torquatisphinctes acuticostatus* Spath, p. 480, pl. 88, figs 2a, b, 10a-c.

Material: One microconch (RUC2015 JH 49A) and two macroconchs (RUC2015 JH 32, 35A) from units 9 and 10 of the Jhuran River section, i.e. the lower part of the Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: The best specimen is large, including two-thirds of whorl of body chamber, evolute. Inner whorls depressed, outer whorls compressed. Whorl section suboval with slightly arched umbilical wall, moderately distinct umbilical shoulder, slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with convex ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of varicostate, prorsiradiate, thin, sharp, closely spaced, long, occasionally faintly flexuous primary ribs on inner whorls, becoming thicker and more distant with increasing diameter, branching just below ventro-lateral shoulder. Single primary ribs after one, two, three or more branching pairs, mostly corresponding to bifurcating ribs on other side, those following constrictions continuing on other side. No change in pattern of ornamentation on body chamber. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with faint, occasionally obvious forward-directed convexity. Number of ribs approximately 95 on the venter of inner whorl at a diameter of 75 mm and 126 on the venter of outer whorl at a diameter of 178 mm. Constrictions, shallow, faintly oblique.

Remarks: The specimen RUC2015 JH 32 is laterally compressed/crushed. Perhaps the last 50 mm part of the body chamber is missing. The smaller specimen RUC2015 JH 49A consists only of the body chamber and has a slightly smaller umbilical diameter than the other specimens but still within the range of variation (when compared with smaller specimens figured by Spath, 1931). The faintly flexuous primary ribs are only occasionally obvious and the forward-directed convexity on the venter is occasionally not obvious. The ornamentation is like in *T. acuticostatus* (Spath 1931, pl. 88, figs. 2a-b, 10a-c). *T. lunulatoplicatus* Spath (1931, pl. 95, fig. 9a, b) is another comparable species having *T. torquatus*-like inner whorls with a pronounced bend forward at the umbilical end, a slightly compressed, oval whorl section, but differs in having more forward concavity of ribs on the flank, maximum whorl thickness in the lower lateral half and more oblique constrictions. The two larger specimens (RUC2015 JH 32, 35A) represent macroconchs of *T. acuticostatus* (Pl. IX, Figs. 5-7), whereas the smaller one (RUC2015 JH 49A) is a microconch (Pl. IX, Figs.

1-4). Occasional straight secondary ribs on the ventral region of the specimen RUC2015 JH 35A resemble *T. jurunensis*. *T. acuticostatus* was considered conspecific with *T. primus* Spath, 1931 by Pathak (1993; see also Pandey *et al.*, 2013b), but long, flexuous primary ribs characteristic of *T. acuticostatus* Spath are not present in *T. primus* Spath, 1931.

***Torquatisphinctes* gr. *primus-similis* Spath, 1931**

Pl. X, figs 1-6

Material: Eight specimens (RUC2015 JH 24, 24A, 29, 40A, 41, 55, RUC2016 IJH 2, 10) from units 9, 10, and lower part of unit 12 of the Jhuran River section, lower Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, evolute, inner whorls depressed, outer whorls with whorl height to thickness ratio equal to 1 or more compressed. Whorl section subrectangular to suboval with steep umbilical wall, passing smoothly to the curved umbilical shoulder. Flanks slightly arched, converging smoothly to the convex ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of prorsiradiate, thin, sharp, long primary ribs originating from below umbilical shoulder region, leaving umbilical wall smooth, becoming increasingly thicker and distant with increasing diameter and branching just below ventrolateral shoulder. Single primary ribs after one, two, or four branching pairs, corresponding to bifurcating ribs on other side, those following constrictions continue on other side. There is no change in ornamentation pattern on body chamber. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with no or slight forward-directed convexity. With 53-54 ribs per half whorl at a diameter of 81 mm. Constrictions slightly more forwardly inclined than preceding ornamentation, followed by one or two single ribs.

Remarks: The specimens are well-preserved, with both phragmocone and half to three-quarters whorl of body chamber. The ornamentation consisting of forwardly inclined secondary ribs and the whorl section of the inner whorls are like in *T. primus* Spath (1931, pl. 88, fig. 6a, b). The shell proportions, particularly the umbilical width, match those of *T. similis* Spath (1931, pl. 78, fig. 3). *T. similis* has fewer forward-inclined secondary ribs and much fewer ribs per half whorl than in the present specimens (39 per half whorl at a diameter of 85 mm and 47 per half whorl at 97 mm compared to 53-59 per half whorl at a diameter of 81 mm in the present specimens). In this respect, the present specimens are like *T. primus* (more than 48 per half whorl at a diameter of 88 mm).

According to Spath (1931, p. 480) there are two single ribs following constriction preceded by trifid ribs on the body chamber of the paratype of *T. primus*. The trifid ribs are not a character of *Torquatisphinctes*, except in very large specimens (see above) of *T. jurunensis* Spath (1931, pl. 76, fig. 1a, b). In this case it should be

investigated whether these are intercalated free secondary or trifid ribs. In the case of trifid ribs, the species should be reassigned to *Pachysphinctes*. Additionally, we have not observed a single case of more than one single rib following a constriction. After having seen the irregular distribution of single primary ribs in many specimens of *Torquatisphinctes*, it seems more logical to conclude that the distribution of single primary ribs is an ecophenotypic character.

Genus *Indodichotomoceras* Krishna & Pathak, 1993

Type species: *Subdichotomoceras inversum* Spath, 1931

Remarks: Énay (1972, p. 374) and Verma & Westermann (1984, p. 38) considered that *Subdichotomoceras* Spath, 1925 is an ammonite restricted to the Boreal Faunal Realm, and that the records from the Kachchh Basin by Spath (1931) correspond to a homeomorph. Krishna & Pathak (1993, p. 232) introduced *Indodichotomoceras* for such ammonites from the Indo-East-African Province. Krishna & Pathak (1993, p. 232) further assumed the similarity to be a case of homeomorphic convergence, and distinguished the boreal *Subdichotomoceras* with distinctly sparser ribbing in inner whorls and slightly larger divergence of the secondary ribs from the Indo-East-African species with comparatively densely ornamented inner whorls and a moderate divergence of the secondary ribs. In addition, constrictions in *Indodichotomoceras*, as described here, are not so evident. In the Kachchh Basin *Indodichotomoceras inversum* (Spath, 1931) first appeared in the Bathyplocus Zone (Krishna & Pathak 1991). Hitherto, the palaeogeographic distribution of *Subdichotomoceras* and *Indodichotomoceras* was very clear, but repeated records of *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath, 1925 (see below) from Somalia and Kachchh (Indo-East-African Province) suggests a wider distribution of *Subdichotomoceras* (Spath, 1925, 1931; Énay *et al.*, 2014).

***Indodichotomoceras cf. inversum* (Spath, 1931) [M]**

Pl. XI, figs 4, 8-10

Material: Two specimens (RUC2015 GD 23, 7) from units 20 and 21 of the Gangeswar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, whorl section sub-trigonal with flattened flanks and convex ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of strong, sharp, varicostate, regularly biplicate ribs with occasional single ribs after every two or three pairs of ribs, secondary ribs occasionally galloping (see Pandey *et al.*, 2012, p. 487, fig. 5). Primary ribs starting near the umbilical suture rursiradially, bending prorsiradially on the rounded umbilical shoulder region, and bifurcating at or slightly above mid-lateral height. Secondary ribs equally thick,

crossing ventral region with slight forward-directed sinuosity. Constrictions feeble. Umbilical wall low, steeply inclined.

Remarks: Both specimens preserve the body chamber. The specimen RUC2015 GD 23 is almost complete but slightly crushed and compressed on one side, therefore the thickness of the whorl cannot be measured. The other specimen RUC2015 GD 7 is poorly preserved. The ornamentation, umbilical diameter, and whorl height-shell diameter match *S. inversum* Spath (1931, pl. 84, fig. 7a, pl. 85, fig. 4), but due to its crushed condition and poor preservation the present specimens are assigned to *I. inversum* with qualification. *S. simplex* Spath (1931, pl. 83, fig. 8a, b) is the closest comparable species but differs in having a larger umbilical diameter. *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath, 1925 (Spath, 1931, p. 523, pl. 92, fig. 9; see also Arkell *et al.*, 1957, p. L328, fig. 422; Énay *et al.*, 2014, p. 330, pl. 10, figs. 1, 2, text-fig. 18) is more sparsely ribbed on the inner whorls.

***Indodichotomoceras inversum* (Spath, 1931) [m]**

Pl. XI, figs 1-3

1931. *Subdichotomoceras inversum* Spath, p. 521, pl. 84, fig. 7a, b, pl. 85, fig. 4.

Material: One specimen (RUC2015 GD 1) from unit 20 of the Gangeswar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell small, evolute, whorl section subcircular with slightly arched flanks and acutely arched ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of strong, sharp, varicostate, regularly biplicate ribs with several single ribs after every one to three pairs of ribs, secondary ribs occasionally galloping. Primary ribs rursiradial on umbilical wall bending at umbilical edge slightly prorsiradially and bifurcating at or above mid-lateral height. Secondary ribs of equal thickness, crossing ventral region with forward-directed sinuosity. Umbilical wall low, steeply inclined.

Remarks: The shell is nearly complete with the last whorl being the body chamber. The ornamentation and shell proportions match *S. inversum*, but the present specimen, despite being nearly complete, is smaller. The umbilical diameter is closer to *S. simplex* Spath (1931, pl. 83, fig. 8a, b). *S. inversum*, *S. simplex*, and the present specimen may represent intraspecific variants of the same species. Its morphology similar to the macroconch assigned to *I. cf. inversum* and the small size suggest it is a microconch.

***Indodichotomoceras predivisum* (Spath, 1931)**

Pl. XII, figs 6-7

1931. *Dichotomoceras predivisum* Spath, p. 422, pl. 88, fig. 4, a, b, pl. 97, fig. 2, pl. 98, fig. 2, pl. 100, fig. 4.

Material: One specimen (RUC2017 IGD 2) from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member (Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, almost complete with body chamber forming more than three-fourth of last whorl, evolute. Whorl section subquadrangular with flat to feebly arched flanks merging smoothly with convex ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of varicostate ribs; thin, sharp, closely spaced on the inner whorls and sharp and moderately thick with gradually increasing inter-rib spaces on the out whorl. Inter-rib space near the peristome suddenly increases to double. Primary ribs originate near umbilical suture, run rursiradially over low umbilical wall, slightly bend prorsiradially with small curve just above latero-umbilical shoulder and bifurcating consistently at ventrolateral shoulder. Commonly, after two to five branching pairs, single, undivided primary ribs on one side join secondary ribs on other side. Occasionally, single rib remains single on both the sides. Secondary ribs cross the venter straight to slight forward-directed sinuosity. Constrictions indistinct. Umbilical wall low, convex.

Remarks: The peristomal part is not preserved in the specimen. The dimensional proportions, subquadrate whorl section (i.e., with almost parallel sides and a broadly arched venter), sharp, varicostate, regularly bifurcating ribs, and the occasional presence of single ribs in the present specimen closely match *Indodichotomoceras predivisum* Spath, 1931. Spath (1931) recorded the species from the Kimmeridgian Lower Katrol beds (= Shivparas Member of the Jhuran Formation), Walakhavas, south of Bhuj, Kachchh Basin. The dimensional proportions of some ammonites from the Middle Katrol beds, such as *Pachysphinctes symmetricus* Spath (1931, pl. 101, fig. 7a, b) (D: 122, H/D: 0.25, T/D: 0.28, U/D: 0.53) and *S. simplex* Spath (1931, pl. 83, fig. 8a, b) (D: 117, H/D: 0.26, T/D: 0.3, U/D: 0.53) are also like those of the present specimen. The ribs are in general, however, coarser in *P. symmetricus* and secondary ribs on the two lateral sides do not form mirror images but rather create a zigzag pattern. In *S. simplex* the point of bifurcation of primary ribs is low. The present species has slightly denser ribs than all *Indodichotomoceras* species described above. The species has some affinity with the more densely ribbed *T. primus* and *T. acuticostatus* of the Acanthicum/Intermedius Zone.

Genus *Subdichotomoceras* Spath, 1925

Type species: *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath, 1925.

Subdichotomoceras cf. *lamplughii* Spath, 1925

Pl. XI, figs 5-7

- cf. 1925. *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath, p. 119.
 cf. 1931. *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath, p. 523, pl. 92, fig. 9.
 cf. 1957. *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii* Spath – Arkell, p. L328, fig. 422.
 cf. 2014. *Subdichotomoceras lamplughii lamplughii* Spath (m + M) – Énay *et al.*, p. 330, pl. 10, figs. 1-2 (with additional synonymy).

Material: One fragmentary specimen (RUC2017 IGD 5) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, planulate, slightly depressed, whorl section subquadrate with flattened flanks and broadly arched ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of distantly spaced, strong, sharp, regularly bifurcating ribs. Primary ribs slightly rursiradiate just below rounded umbilical shoulder, bending straight to prorsiradially on flank and bifurcating slightly below ventro-lateral shoulder. Occasional single ribs present. Secondary ribs of equal thickness, anterior secondary rib with more forward-directed convexity than posterior secondary rib. Umbilical wall low, slightly arched, middle part nearly smooth.

Remarks: The fragment contains a part of the body chamber. The innermost whorls are not preserved. The pattern of ornamentation on the outer whorl, whorl-height, and thickness ratio are as in *Subdichotomoceras inversum* Spath, 1931 (p. 521, pl. 84, fig. 7a, pl. 85, fig. 4) but the present specimen is more sparsely ribbed. The whorl section and ornamentation are comparable to *Subdichotomoceras simplex* Spath, 1931 (p. 522, pl. 83, fig. 8a, b) but inner whorls of the present specimen are more sparsely ribbed. Spath (1931: 522) differentiated *S. inversum* from *S. simplex* based on the large umbilicus and smaller whorl height of the latter. With respect to its small whorl height and distant ribbing it matches *S. lamplughii*. Due to its fragmentary condition the specimen has been assigned to *S. lamplughii* Spath with qualification. However, according to earlier workers (Énay, 1972: 374; Verma & Westermann, 1984, p. 38; Krishna & Pathak, 1993, p. 232; see also Énay *et al.*, 2014, p. 330) *S. lamplughii* Spath has been considered to be restricted to the Boreal Faunal Realm (see above).

In contrast to species assigned to *Indodichotomoceras*, the present specimen distinctly exhibits sparser ribbing in inner whorls and slightly wider splaying of the secondary ribs. These are distinctly the features of *Subdichotomoceras* and therefore has been assigned to this genus. Contextually, *Subdichotomoceras* Spath, 1925 does not show any palaeogeographic restriction.

Genus *Pachysphinctes* Dietrich, 1925

Type species: *Perisphinctes* (*P.*) *africogermanus* Dietrich, 1925

***Pachysphinctes* cf. *robustus* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XII, figs 1-3

cf. 1931. *Pachysphinctes robustus* Spath, p. 491, pl. 84, fig. 5, pl. 93, fig. 10a, b.

Material: One specimen (RUC2017 IGD 12) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, whorl section subquadrangular with arched flanks passing smoothly into the broadly arched ventral region. Maximum thickness just above umbilical shoulder. Ornamentation consisting of thick, distant ribs. Primary ribs prorsiradiate, bifurcating at mid-whorl height on early part of body chamber and virgatotome triplicate towards end of outer whorl. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, with uniform bifurcation without any galloping, crossing the ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

Remarks: The specimen is a fragment of body chamber of a specimen more than 132 mm in diameter. The ornamentation and whorl section closely match *Pachysphinctes robustus* Spath, 1931 (p. 491, pl. 93, fig. 10a, b), but lacking information about inner whorls it is referred to this species only tentatively.

***Pachysphinctes* sp.**

Pl. XII, figs 4-5

Material: One specimen (RUC2015 GD 9) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, i.e. the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Remarks: The fragment represents part of the phragmocone of a large specimen. The suture lines are poorly preserved. The large size, subcircular whorl section, ornamentation and suture lines match *Pachysphinctes linguiferus* Spath, 1931 (p. 496, pl. 97, fig. 1, pl. 98, fig. 5). The ornamentation of the specimen assigned by Spath to *P.* cf. *major* (see above) is also quite similar, but the ribs are slightly thinner and denser in the present specimen, which may be just an intraspecific variation. Until more and better preserved material is available, the present specimen has been assigned as indeterminate.

***Pachysphinctes* sp.**

Pl. XIII, figs 1-2

Material: One specimen (RUC2018 JH 2) from unit 12 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Phragmocone evolute and depressed, whorl section elliptical with slightly convex, broad ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of moderately thick, dense, strongly prorsiradiate, regularly biplicate and simple ribs. Branching of ribs at ventro-lateral shoulder. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, crossing ventral region with feeble forward-directed convexity. Constrictions inclined, at least three per whorl.

Remarks: The specimen represents inner whorls. The suture lines are poorly preserved. The whorl section and ornamentation match the inner whorls of *Pachysphinctes linguiferus* Spath, 1931 (p. 496, pl. 97, fig. 1). The whorl section also matches that of *Pachyplanulites irregularis* Spath, 1931 (p. 433, pl. 95, fig. 8a, b) from the Kimmeridgian Lower Katrol Beds at Fakirwadi and Ler. There are forms intermediate between *P. irregularis* and *Katrolliceras* sp. juv. from the Kimmeridgian Katrol Group (= Jhuran Formation) (Spath, 1931, p. 513, pl. 93, fig. 4a, b) at Fakirwadi. The latter is very close to the present specimen with respect to the whorl section and ornamentation. *Pachyplanulites* Spath, 1930 has been doubtfully merged with *Kranaosphinctes* Buckman, an Oxfordian genus (Arkell *et al.*, 1957, p. L321; Énay & Howarth, 2019, p. 33). Spath (1930, p. 44) recorded three taxa of *Pachyplanulites* from Lower or lowest Kimmeridgian sediments of Mombasa (Kenya). Of these, *P. (K.) subevolutus* Waagen, 1875 (Pandey *et al.*, 2012, p. 494) and *P. (Arisphinctes) cf. subcolubrinus* Waagen, 1875 (Pandey *et al.*, 2012, p. 506) have been recorded either from Dhosa Oolite or Dhosa Conglomerate Beds of Oxfordian (Waagen, 1875, p. 180 and Spath, 1931, p. 432). Gygi (2003) suggested that since *Pachyplanulites* Spath (1930, p. 44) is an Early? Kimmeridgian ammonite, it is best to introduce a new generic name for forms such as *Pachyplanulites irregularis* Spath (1931, p. 433). Énay (2009, p. 119) assigned *P. irregularis* Spath (in Collignon, 1959: pl. 101) to *Pachysphinctes*. The morphological features in the present small specimen representing only inner whorls, collected from Kimmeridgian strata, confirm its generic assignment to *Pachysphinctes* Dietrich, 1925.

***Pachysphinctes* cf. *linguiferus* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIII, figs 3-5

cf. 1931. *Pachysphinctes linguiferus* Spath, p. 496, pl. 97, fig. 1, pl. 98, fig. 5.

Material: One specimen (RUC2017 IGD 18) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, evolute, depressed. Whorl section subquadrangular with flattened flanks merging smoothly with broadly convex ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of moderately thick, prorsiradiate, faintly flexuous, distant primary ribs originating just below rounded umbilical shoulder rursiradially, bending forward and branching into three secondary ribs above mid-lateral height, occasionally branching virgatome-like. Secondary ribs much thinner than primary ribs, cross the ventral region without forward-directed sinuosity. Umbilical wall low, steep, nearly vertical.

Remarks: The specimen is a fragment of bodychamber. Its moderately large size, ornamentation, flattened flanks, and wide convex ventral region match *P. linguiferus* Spath (1931, p. 496, pl. 97, fig. 1, pl. 98, fig. 5), but the flexuous aspect of primary ribs and slightly smaller umbilical diameter appear different. The whorl section in the present specimen is more inflated with a wider ventral region than in *P. bathyplocus* Waagen (1875, p. 192, pl. 50, fig. 1). The coiling of the inner whorls, whether looser or tighter than in *P. bathyplocus* cannot be determined due to the fragmentary condition of the present specimen.

P. major Waagen (1875, p. 191, pl. 54; Spath, 1931, p. 489, pl. 75, fig. 1, pl. 78, figs. 1, 2, pl. 87, fig. 3a, b, pl. 89, fig. 6a, b), also has a broad ventral area and triplicate ribs, but this is a large ammonite in contrast to the present specimen which exhibits triplicate ribs on the body chamber. *P. crassus* Spath, 1931 (p. 492, pl. 85, fig. 3a, b) has much coarser ribs.

***Pachysphinctes* gr. *linguiferus*–*symmetricus* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIII, figs 9-11

Material: One specimen (RUC2017 IGD 13) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, whorl section subcircular with flat flanks and broad ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of sharp, distant, varicostate ribs. Primary ribs starting at umbilical suture, running rursiradially across low umbilical wall, bending prorsiradially at umbilical shoulder, bifurcating at or slightly above mid-whorl height on inner whorls. Towards outer part of body chamber ribbing triplicate virgatome. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, occasionally galloping and crossing ventral region either straight or with faint forwardly directed sinuosity.

Remarks: The specimen is fragmentary. The ornamentation and whorl section with broad ventral region match *P. linguiferus* Spath (1931, p. 496, pl. 97, fig. 1, pl. 98, fig. 5), but the whorl height is slightly greater in our specimen. The ornamentation and whorl

height are also comparable to *P. symmetricus*, the ventral region of which is, however, narrow. The whorl thickness is also close to *P. bathyplocus* (Waagen, 1875, p. 192, pl. 1, fig. 1a, b; Spath, 1931, p. 493 pl. 77, fig. 1a, b, pl. 93, figs. 5, 9, pl. 96, fig. 4). According to Spath (1931: 498) there are several “passage forms” between *P. symmetricus* and *P. bathyplocus*, but *P. symmetricus* can be easily differentiated from *P. bathyplocus* by its “more rounded whorl section”, “much lower point of bifurcation of the ribs”, and thus longer secondary ribs.

***Pachysphinctes symmetricus* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIII, figs 6-8

1931. *Pachysphinctes symmetricus* Spath, p. 498, pl. 101, fig. 7a, b.

Material: One specimen (RUC2013 GD 1) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, evolute, depressed, whorl section subquadrangular with flat flanks converging towards narrow ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of sharp, varicostate primary ribs starting at umbilical suture rursiradially, bending at broad umbilical shoulder region, running prorsiradially with slight forward-directed convexity on lower half of flanks, and bifurcating at or below ventro-lateral shoulder. Anterior secondary ribs slightly more forward inclined. On outer part of last whorl, preceding a shallow constriction, two primary ribs appearing to join at umbilical shoulder. Intercalatory ribs also appearing to start just at ventrolateral shoulder. Occasionally single primary ribs present. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity. Constrictions present.

Remarks: The specimen is poorly preserved. The dimensional proportions are as in *Katrolliceras subkatrolense* Spath (1931, p. 517, pl. 75, fig. 6a, b), but the presence of single primary ribs and the forwardly directed convexity on the ventral region differentiates the present specimen from that species. The venter is covered with matrix, making difficult to ascertain whether the entire specimen is a phragmocone or whether the outermost part of the whorl is body chamber. The ornamentation on the outer whorl and the section with its narrow ventral region match *P. symmetricus* Spath, 1931.

Distribution: Spath (1931, p. 498) recorded *P. symmetricus* of the Smith collection from “Middle (or Upper ?) Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Group)” strata at Fakirwadi, and two additional specimens are either from Fakirwadi or from Ler.

***Pachysphinctes major* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIV, figs 1-3, 10

1875. *Perisphinctes torquatus* Sowerby – Waagen, p. 191, pl. 54 (according to Spath 1931, p. 489).

1931. *Pachysphinctes major* Spath, p. 489, pl. 75, fig. 1, pl. 78, figs. 1, 2, pl. 87, fig. 3a, b, pl. 89, fig. 6a, b.

1959. *Pachysphinctes major* Spath – Collignon, pl. 119, fig. 449.

Material: Two specimens (RUC2017I GD 182, 183) from units 20 and 21 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, whorl section sub-square to subcircular, with flattened flanks, broadly rounded ventral region, maximum thickness just above umbilical shoulder. Ornamentation consisting of prorsiradiate ribs. Primary ribs thin, sharp, straight, distant, bifurcating slightly below ventrolateral shoulder. Occasionally single primary ribs joining as secondary rib on the other side, occasionally showing gallops. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity. Inner whorls with constrictions.

Remarks: The specimens are inner whorls. Suture lines are poorly to well preserved. The sub-square whorl section, broad ventral region and ornamentation match *Pachysphinctes major* Spath, 1931 (pl. 75, fig. 1, pl. 78, figs. 1, 2, pl. 87, fig. 3a, b, pl. 89, fig. 6a, b). The specimen RUC2013 GD 01 described above as *P. symmetricus* Spath shows a very similar ornamentation, but at a similar diameter the shell is the body chamber.

P. cf. major figured by Fatmi & Zeiss (1999, p. 61, pl. 13, fig. 1, pl. 16, fig. 1, pl. 57, figs. 2, 5) from Sembar Formation (Belemnite shales), Windar Nai, Pakistan differs from *P. major* in having compressed whorl section and wider umbilicus.

***Pachysphinctes cf. major* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIV, figs 4-9, 11-17

Material: Three specimens (RUC2015 GD 41, RUC2015 JH 17, RUC2016 IJH 11) from unit 20 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation; and from units 13 and 15 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, whorl section depressed, suboval to subcircular, maximum thickness above umbilical shoulder. Ornamentation of inner whorls consisting of variocostate, prorsiradiate ribs. Primary ribs thin, sharp, long, feebly flexuous, bifurcating below ventro-lateral shoulder. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity (most of anterior secondary ribs). On the outer

whorl ornamentation consisting of distant, thick, prorsiradiate primary ribs, trifurcating slightly above mid-lateral height. Secondary ribs thinner, crossing ventral region either straight (mostly posterior secondary rib of triplets) or with faint forwardly directed sinuosity (mostly anterior secondary rib of triplets). Constrictions on inner whorls slightly forwardly inclined.

Remarks: The specimen RUC2016 IJH 11 is a juvenile with half to two-thirds of the last whorl being the body chamber. The ornamentation and whorl section are very well-preserved. The broad ventral region, ornamentation, and whorl section of this specimen match the innermost whorls of *P. major*. The other specimens RUC2015 GD 41, RUC2015 JH 17 are fragments representing parts of phragmocones of large shells. The subcircular whorl section, broad venter, and ornamentation also match *P. major*, but due to their fragmentary condition the specimens are only tentatively assigned to that species.

***Pachysphinctes aff. major* Spath, 1931 [M]**

Pl. XV, figs 1-8

Material. Two specimens (RUC2018 JH 1, RUC2015 JH 14) from units 13 and 15 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Phragmocone large ($D > 190$ mm), evolute, depressed, whorl section suboval with arched flanks and moderately rounded ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of thin, sharp, prorsiradiate, bifurcating ribs, branching between mid-lateral and two-thirds height of whorl, mostly just below ventrolateral shoulder. Constrictions numbering two to three in each whorl, forwardly inclined. Single primary ribs occasionally associated with constrictions. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity. Folds rounded, distant, well-developed on outer part of phragmocone.

Remarks: The specimens are incomplete, lacking the body chamber, but folds are developed on the outer whorl of the phragmocone. The exact diameter at which the change of ribbing from thin, sharp, bifurcating ribs to well-developed folds takes place is not clear. The dimensional proportions match *Katroliceras katrolensis* (Waagen) in Spath (1931: 518, pl. 76, figs. 2, 3, pl. 93, fig. 3). However, the typical ornamentation of *Katroliceras* on inner whorls and on the outer whorl is not observed, and the rather slightly finer ornamentation and flattish flanks match *Pachysphinctes major*. As the specimens differ from that species in having a smaller umbilical diameter, they are identified as *Pachysphinctes aff. major* Spath.

Genus *Katroliceras* Spath, 1924

Type species: *Ammonites pottingeri* J. de C. Sowerby, 1840

Remarks: The specimens described here are small to large (~ 200 mm in diameter), evolute, with depressed whorls and coarse, sharp, and distant ribbing on the outer part of the phragmocone and body chamber. The ribs are thin, dense, bifurcating on inner whorls, increasingly trifurcate anteriorly, and abruptly change to thick distant, trifurcating folds with free secondary ribs.

***Katroliceras katrolensis* (Waagen, 1875)**

Pl. XVI, figs 1-5

1875. *Perisphinctes katrolensis* Waagen, p. 184, pl. 53.

1931. *Katroliceras katrolensis* (Waagen) – Spath, p. 518, pl. 76, figs. 2, 3, pl. 93, fig. 3.

Material: Two specimens (RUC2015 GD 15, 28) from unit 35 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell large, evolute, depressed, whorl section subquadrangular to semi-circular with rounded umbilical shoulder and arched flanks merging smoothly with convex ventral region. Maximum thickness of inner whorls just above umbilical shoulder. Ornamentation consisting of moderately thick, varicostate ribs. Primary ribs short, starting just below rounded umbilical shoulder rursiradially, bending forward and bifurcating above mid-whorl height on inner whorls and showing virgatome triplicate splitting towards outer part of phragmocone. Secondary ribs slightly thinner, crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity. Umbilical wall low, steeply inclined, smooth. Ornamentation of body chamber consisting of extremely coarse, short, increasingly distant primary ribs, branching just after umbilical shoulder into three prorsiradially flaring secondary ribs, which cross ventral region with faint or no forwardly directed sinuosity. One free secondary rib between adjacent triplets. Inter-rib distance in first quarter of body chamber remaining same as in last part of phragmocone. From there, inter-rib distance gradually increasing to a maximum of approximately 20 mm at beginning of last quarter of body chamber.

Remarks: The smaller specimen consists of a phragmocone. The ornamentation matches *K. katrolensis*. The inner whorls of the large specimen are not visible. The large size of the specimen, convex ventral region, thick, short, distant primary ribs confined to the umbilical shoulder region and long secondary ribs on the body chamber closely match the features of *K. katrolensis*. This latter species differs from other species of *Katroliceras* by its large size, convex ventral region, and short primary ribs. *P. major*, which is the more commonly occurring species in Kachchh, differs in having a less wide umbilicus, denser

ribs, and a higher whorl section or a slightly higher point of bifurcation.

Katroliceras subkatrolense* Spath, 1931, var. *splendens

Pl. XVII, figs 1-6, Pl. XVIII, figs 6-8

1931. *Katroliceras subkatrolense* Spath, var. *splendens*, p. 517, pl. 75, fig. 6a, b, pl. 85, fig. 5 (non pl. 85, fig. 6, pl. 87, fig. 7a, b).

Material: Four specimens (RUC2015 GD 4, 23A, 42, RUC2017 IGD 15) from unit 35 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, evolute, depressed, whorl section sub-rounded to subquadrangular with acutely rounded umbilical shoulder, flanks flat to slightly arched merging smoothly with convex ventral region. Ornamentation varicostate, prorsiradial, moderately thick, starting from umbilical suture rursiradially, bending forward at umbilical shoulder region, continuing prorsiradially with slight forwardly directed concavity on lower half of flat flanks, bifurcating just below the ventro-lateral shoulder. Anterior secondary ribs a little more forwardly inclined, occasionally single ribs present (on inner whorls). Extremely coarse, increasingly distant primary ribs, first branching above umbilical shoulder on body chamber, second branching below ventro-lateral shoulder. A free secondary rib rarely occurring between bifurcating or trifurcating ribs. Secondary ribs crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity in anteriormost secondary rib, no sinuosity in middle secondary rib and forwardly directed concavity in posterior most secondary rib. Constrictions present.

Remarks: The specimen RUC2015 GD 23A is well-preserved with the major part of the body chamber preserved. There is no sudden change in ornamentation at the onset of the body chamber. Later on, the ornamentation gradually coarsens, and ribs become distant and triplicate. The triplicates start after the first quarter of the body chamber. The inter-rib distance on the body chamber gradually increases (varicostation) up to the last quarter. On the three-fourths of the body chamber preserved there are 22 primary ribs. The inner whorls are hidden underneath the hard rock matrix. Specimen RUC2015 GD 4 consists of part of the body chamber and the phragmocone. The triplets start at the end of the third quarter of the body chamber. Inter-ribs distance on the body chamber gradually increases (varicostate) up to beginning of its third quarter. Within three-fourths of the body chamber there are 30 primary ribs. Comparing different specimens, the density of ribs within species varies. The whorl-shape, ornamentation, and whorl height-thickness ratio match *K. subkatrolense* and the specimens are consequently placed in this species. The ornamentation on the inner part of the

outer whorl and the whorl section also match *P. symmetricus* but the outer part of the body chamber is like in *Katrolicerias*. The present specimens differ from *K. katrolensis* (Waagen, 1875) discussed above in their small size and lower point of branching.

***Katrolicerias waageni* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**

Pl. XVIII, figs 1-5

1875. *Perisphinctes pottingeri* Sowerby – Waagen, p. 183, pl. 51, fig. 1a, b

1931. *Katrolicerias waageni* Spath, p. 508.

Material: Two specimens; one microconch (RUC2017 IGD 11) and one macroconch (RUC2017 IGD 14) from unit 35 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member, Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, depressed, whorl section semi-circular with slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with faintly arched to flat ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of thin, variocostate ribs on inner whorls, gradually becoming moderately thick, distant. Primary ribs bifurcating slightly above mid-lateral height into secondary ribs of same thickness. Primary ribs sudden increase in thickness on last quarter in the case of microconch and on second quarter in the case of macroconch of body chamber and become fold-like, increasingly more distant, branching at the ventro-lateral shoulder into two or three short, thinner secondary ribs. Additional one or two secondary ribs between two adjacent branching primary ribs remain free.

Remarks: The specimens are rather poorly preserved, embedded in a concretion of fine-grained sandstone. The inner whorls are either recrystallised or mostly eroded and crushed, so that in most cases the whorl shape cannot be reconstructed, but at places the ornamentation of the innermost whorls is preserved. The outer whorl in the smaller specimen (RUC2017 IGD 11) represents a small part of the phragmocone and the nearly complete body chamber. The larger specimen (RUC2017 IGD 14) has poorly preserved, unrecoverable inner whorls but a well-preserved body chamber with an ornamentation pattern similar to that of the smaller specimen. The possibility that the two specimens represent a micro- and macroconch cannot be ruled out. The ornamentation on the outer whorl is as in *K. pottingeri*, but that species differs chiefly in having coarser ribs on the earlier whorls (Futterer 1894, pl. 1 figs. 1-2; specimen from Mombasa is refigured by Spath 1931, p. 505, pl. 102, fig. 5a-d). *K. waageni* differs from *K. sowerbyi* in having a more depressed whorl section and less flattened flanks. In addition, the secondary ribs on the body chamber are thinner and more numerous. According to Spath (1931: 509), *K. sowerbyi* differs in having more “*bathyplocus*-like inner whorls, and in page 510 mentioned *K. sowerbyi* as characterised by “*pottingeri*-like” outer whorl that

greatly resemble those of *Torquatisphinctes*. Moreover, the difference in ornamentation between early whorls of *Torquatisphinctes* and *Pachysphinctes* cannot be judged easily. In the former, single ribs are common, but occasionally present in the latter. Such differences cannot be considered as intraspecific variation. Moreover, as mentioned above and by Spath (1931), the inner whorls in such *Katrolicerias* species are rarely well preserved.

***Katrolicerias sowerbyi* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XIX, figs 1-8

1931. *Katrolicerias sowerbyi* Spath, p. 509, pl. 99, fig. 7a, b.

Material: Two fragmentary specimens (RUC2015 GD 20, RUC2017IGD 17) from unit 35 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian *Katrolensis* Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell evolute, depressed, whorl section subquadrangular with flat to slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with convex ventral region. On phragmocone, ornamentation consisting of slightly prorsiradiate, moderately thick primary ribs, bifurcating slightly below ventro-lateral shoulder, having secondary ribs of same thickness, crossing the ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity. Occasionally, secondary ribs galloping. On body chamber, primary ribs stand out at umbilical shoulder, extremely coarse, fold-like, becoming increasingly more distant, branching below ventro-lateral shoulder into thinner secondary ribs. A single free secondary rib between bifurcating pairs. Umbilical wall steep.

Remarks: The ornamentation of the phragmocone in the specimen RUC2015 GD 20 matches that of *Pachysphinctes* and not of *Torquatisphinctes*. The outer whorl of this specimen is the outer part of the body chamber with the inter-rib distance in the last part changing from 21 to 40 mm. In the best preserved specimen the bifurcation of primary ribs occurs slightly below the ventro-lateral shoulder. The specimen RUC2017 IGD 17 represents an early part of the body chamber. The ornamentation of this specimen is similar to that of the outer part of the phragmocone of specimen RUC2015 GD 20. The ornamentation on the outer whorl is as in *K. pottingeri*, but the secondary ribs are longer in the present specimens. In addition, the ornamentation on the inner whorls is thinner and denser as in *K. waageni* described above, which differs in having a greater number of secondary ribs on outer whorls. In addition, the present specimens show a higher H/T than *K. waageni*.

***Katrolicerias* sp.**

Pl. XIX, figs 9-11, Pl. XX, figs 1-8

Material: Seven specimens (RUC2016 IKH 01–06, 51) from the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

Description: Small, incomplete phragmocones, evolute, whorl section depressed, subcircular to subquadrangular with broad ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of thin, prorsiradiate, varicostate, closely spaced ribs on the inner whorls, becoming gradually sparse towards middle whorls (RUC2016 IKH 5), bifurcating at or just below ventrolateral shoulder. Occasionally single ribs present. Secondary ribs crossing uninterrupted over broad ventral region with straight or slight forwardly directed convexity. Three or more constrictions per whorl.

Remarks: The specimens are inner whorls of large individuals. The depressed whorl sections with broad ventral region, thin closely spaced ribs bifurcating at the ventrolateral shoulder, and three constrictions per whorl match *K. zitteli* Spath (1931, pl. 87, fig. 6a, b, pl. 97, figs. 4, 6), *K. aff. depressum* Spath (1931, pl. 89, fig. 4), *Katrolicer* ? sp. juv. (Spath, 1931, pl. 89, fig. 5a, b), *Katrolicer* sp. juv. (Spath, 1931, pl. 89, fig. 8), *K. depressum* Spath (1931, pl. 89, fig. 9), and *Pachyplanulites irregularis* Spath (1931, pl. 95, fig. 8a, b). In *P. irregularis* the thickness of the whorl increases rapidly, which is just the opposite in the present specimens. According to Spath (1931, p. 513, pl. 87, fig. 6a, b) “less oblique constrictions and the straight ventral ribbing of *Katrolicer* *zitteli* are also important distinguishing features”; therefore, the present specimens are also close to *K. zitteli*. The ornamentation of a small specimen of *K. subkatrolense* figured by Spath (1931, pl. 87, fig. 7a, b) is comparable (e.g., RUC2016 IKH 5), but its whorl section and its moderately rounded ventral region differs from the broad ventral region of the present specimens. *K. lerense* Spath, 1931 (p. 511, pl. 88, fig. 5; pl. 89, fig. 1) co-occurring in the same section has ribs bifurcating below the ventrolateral shoulder, and in this respect specimen RUC2016 IKH 51 is quite close. The dimensional proportions in all the forms of *Katrolicer* mentioned above are comparable except for the umbilical diameter which is smaller in the present specimens. In fact, the inner whorls of all forms of *Katrolicer* are quite comparable and it is difficult to separate them. In addition, there are some transitional forms, such as between *K. zitteli* and *K. depressum*. In lack of information on the outer whorls, the present specimens are only assigned at the generic level.

***Katrolicer* *lerense* Spath, 1931**

Pl. XX, figs 9-12

1931. *Katrolicer* *lerense* Spath, p. 511, pl. 88, fig. 5; pl. 89, fig. 1.

2017. *Katrolicer* *lerense* Spath – Prasad *et al.*, p. 4, fig. 2A.

Material: One specimen (RUC2016 IKH 01) from the Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

Description: Shell almost complete, moderately large, evolute, depressed, whorl section subcircular to subquadrangular with moderately distinct umbilical shoulder, slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with broad, moderately arched ventral region. Ornamentation consisting of prorsiradiate, thin, dense ribs, on inner whorls, moderately distant and thick on middle whorls and very thick and distant on outer part of bodychamber. Ribs on inner whorls starting faintly near umbilical suture, soon becoming sharp and running rursiradially, bending forward at umbilical shoulder region, crossing lower half of arched flanks prorsiradially with faint forwardly directed concavity, bifurcating just below ventrolateral shoulder. Anterior secondary rib slightly more forwardly inclined than posterior one. Additional single rib seen on last part of phragmocone, joining primary rib. Virgatome ornamentation on early part of the body chamber, occasionally with four secondary ribs. Outer part of body chamber with smooth umbilical wall, very thick, distant primary ribs branching into two or three virgatome secondary ribs at ventrolateral shoulder. Between bi- and trifurcating ribs, rarely one free secondary rib occurs. Ribs crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity. Constrictions present.

Remarks: The present specimen consists of both phragmocone and body chamber. The branching with a third secondary rib and widening of inter-rib distance start at the beginning of the body chamber. The last preserved inter-rib distance is 30 mm. The whorl section, ornamentation, and dimensional proportions closely match *K. lerense* Spath (1931, pl. 88, fig. 5, pl. 89, fig. 1).

Superfamily Aspidoceratoidea Zittel, 1895

Remarks: Parent *et al.* (2020), based on several unique and different characters in aspidoceratid ammonites, which are not found in the Superfamily Perisphinctoidea, raised the Family Aspidoceratidae Zittel, 1895 to the rank of superfamily. This superfamily ranges in age from the earliest Late Callovian to the Early Berriasian Jacobi Zone. The new superfamily includes two families: Aspidoceratidae Zittel, 1895 and Peltoceratidae Spath, 1924.

Family Aspidoceratidae Zittel, 1895

Remarks: Arkell *et al.* (1957, p. L335) distinguished three subfamilies; viz. Peltoceratinae Spath, 1924, Aspidoceratinae Zittel, 1895, and Simoceratinae Spath, 1924 within the family Aspidoceratidae (see also Spath, 1924, 1931). Spath (1931, p. 551) assumed these taxa to be derived from “different stocks of Perisphinctids,

perhaps replenished by independent offshoots of the fundamental Phylloceratids and Lytoceratids". Recently, Parent *et al.* (2020), revised the status of family Aspidoceratidae Zittel, 1895 and proposed four subfamilies in family Aspidoceratidae (Aspidoceratinae, Euaspidoceratinae, Epipeltoceratinae and Hybonoticeratinae). Parent *et al.* (2020) further contradicted the earlier understanding that aspidoceratids evolved successively from perisphinctids from the Callovian to Berriasian, by developing bi-tuberculations at various stages of growth (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b; Krishna, 2017).

Subfamily Aspidoceratinae Zittel, 1895

Genus *Aspidoceras* Zittel, 1868

Type species: *Ammonites rogoznicensis* Zeuschner, 1846.

Remarks: As mentioned earlier (Pandey *et al.*, 2013b) the genus *Aspidoceras* ranges from the Early Kimmeridgian (Bimammatum Zone) to the Lower Berriasian (Jacobi Zone) with its maximum development during Kimmeridgian times. Bituberculate aspidoceratines within Indo-East-African faunal province have been recorded from Kachchh, Madagascar, Spiti, Nepal, and Pakistan (Waagen, 1875; Spath, 1933; Collignon, 1959; Krishna *et al.*, 1994; Énay, 2009; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b).

Spath (1931, p. 552-553) discussed in great detail the history of the genus *Aspidoceras* and referred the type species *Ammonites rogoznicensis* Zeuschner to the lineage of *Euaspidoceras perarmatum* (Sowerby, 1822). Parent *et al.* (2020) also mentioned *Euaspidoceras* appears to be the root of the other main lineages of the Aspidoceratinae in the Bimammatum Zone, whose earliest representatives are known from the Submediterranean Province and the western Tethys.

Taxonomically, all the species of *Aspidoceras* recorded from Kimmeridgian strata of the Kachchh Basin have been defined on the basis of the distribution pattern of tubercles in two rows (uniform or irregular, appearance and disappearance, distance between the two rows, location of outer row more internally or marginally), number of tubercles per whorl, size of tubercles, whorl shape, and umbilical diameter. The tubercles of the two rows show various combinations of even or uneven distribution, and their size can be smaller to larger in comparison to each other (e.g., tubercles of both rows are evenly distributed and forming pairs, or tubercles of the outer row are evenly distributed whereas those of the inner, umbilical row are less regular, or vice versa). Inner tubercles may be stronger than outer ones as in *Aspidoceras intermedium* Bruder (1885, pl. 2, fig. 4a-c), or vice versa as, for example, in *Aspidoceras lerense* Spath (1931, p. 633). In fact, in some cases it appears that these irregularities are not characteristic of a particular species, but simply ecophenotypic features. In addition, the tubercles in the specimens from the

Kachchh Basin described and illustrated in earlier works (Waagen, 1873-1875; Spath, 1931; Krishna *et al.*, 1994; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b) are mostly broken, and their size based on the diameter of the scars can be misleading. This is because the diameter of the scars may little correspond to their height. In this situation, subjectivity in the specific assignment cannot be ruled out.

Waagen (1873-1875), Spath (1931), Krishna *et al.* (1994), and Pandey *et al.* (2013b) recognised the following taxa of *Aspidoceras* in the Kachchh Basin:

1. *Aspidoceras* aff. *acanthicum* (Oppel, 1863) in Spath (1931, p. 624, pl. 123, fig. 7a, b) is characterised by a narrow venter, small tubercles arranged in two close rows (lateral and periumbilical), loss of tubercles of the lateral row at an early growth stage, and twelve lateral tubercles, corresponding to the same number of umbilical spines that persist unchanged. The ventral region is narrower than that of all closely comparable species, such as *A. asymmetricum* Spath, 1931 (coarsely bi-tuberculate and more involute) and *Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen, 1875 (fewer and much coarser tubercles).

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Lower Katrol Beds), Lodai (Spath 1931, p. 624), equivalent to the Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section. Index and guide species of the early Late Kimmeridgian for the North and South Tethyan margins (Cariou and Hantzpergue, 1997; Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009b, 2011).

2. *Aspidoceras* aff. *sesquinosum* (Fontannes, 1876) in Spath (1931, pl. 119, fig. 5, pl. 122, fig. 6.) is characterized by the small size, more rounded venter, blunt irregular tubercles, and loss of outer tubercles at an early growth stage. The closest comparable species is the more inflated *A. asymmetricum*. The inner whorls of *Aspidoceras pseudomicroplum* Burckhardt (1912) in Spath (1931, pl 118, fig. 8) are more evolute.

Stratigraphic distribution. Lower Kimmeridgian (Lower Katrol beds), Ler (Spath, 1931, p. 627).

3. *Aspidoceras* aff. *bispinosum* (Zieten, 1830) in Spath, (1931, p. 627) is regularly bi-tuberculate up to a diameter of 75 mm. On the inner whorls, the outer spines are more prominent than the inner ones. On the last half-whorl, the outer tubercles become more spaced (but do not disappear), whereas the umbilical spines (thirteen per whorl) persist unchanged. The whorl section is somewhat compressed (slightly crushed); originally it may have been circular.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Belemnite Marls-Lower Katrol Group), "North Joorun" Spath (1931, p. 628) (= Jhuran River Member), Alterneplicatus Zone. Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation at Lodai section.

4. *Aspidoceras* aff. *pseudomicroplum* Burckhardt, 1912 in Spath, 1931 (p. 628, pl 118, fig. 8) is represented by

small shells (D about 30 mm), the outer row of tubercles is distinct only on the innermost whorls and then more or less lost due to weathering. According to Burckhardt (1912), *A. pseudomicroplum* is characterised by a small, moderately evolute shell. The whorl section is sub-circular with slightly arched to flattened flanks. The umbilical wall is vertical and relatively high, merging imperceptibly into the flanks. The inner whorls are depressed, then become less depressed, while height-thickness ratio of the outer whorl is one. Around the umbilicus, a series of little pronounced internal tubercles of the inner whorls is seen. External tubercles, approximately halfway up the flanks, are very low, joined with the corresponding internal tubercles by feeble ribs. Very fine, dense growth lines exist.

Stratigraphic distribution. Lower Kimmeridgian (Lower Katrol Beds) (= Shivparas Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), Ler (Spath, 1931, p. 629). In Mexico, *A. pseudomicroplum* has been recorded in association with *A. acanthicum* (Burckhardt, 1912, p. 79). A comparable species, *Acanthosphaerites* aff. *deaki* (Herbich) in Spath (1930, p. 60, pl. 8, fig. 3), has also been recorded from the Acanthicum Zone in Széklerland, Romania (also see Herbich, 1886; Pavlow, 1886).

5. *Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath (1931, pl. 103, fig. 2, pl. 118, fig. 3a, b, pl. 119, fig. 3, pl. 123, fig. 3; see also Pandey *et al.* 2013b, p. 121, pl. 6: 4; fig. 10A) is characterised by almost perpendicular umbilical walls, a rounded umbilical shoulder, and innermost whorls that are rather globose and comparatively coarsely bi-tuberculate. Twelve lateral tubercles, corresponding to the same number of umbilical spines persist unchanged. The species was first compared with *A. binodiferum* and *A. aff. bispinosum*, from the same locality (Jhuran). *A. asymmetricum* is, however, more involute and more inflated than the latter and therefore closer to *A. binodiferum*. In *A. binodiferum*, in contrast, which is also considerably more inflated, there are few but much coarser tubercles.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Belemnite Marls-Lower Katrol Group) (= Jhuran River Member (Alterneplicatus Zone, Jhuran River section), "Joorun" (Spath 1931, p. 630; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b). Lower part of the Lothia Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River Section and the Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

6. *Aspidoceras* sp. nov.? aff. *longispinum* (J. de C. Sowerby) in Spath (1931, p. 630, pl. 119, fig. 4) is a large specimen. The whorl section is more inflated than in *A. acanthicum*, but the tubercles on inner whorls are similar.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Katrol Beds) (= Shivparas Member, Jhuran Formation), Ler (Spath, 1931, p. 632).

7. *Aspidoceras caroli* Spath (1931, figs. 2a, b, 7a, b.) is characterised by a compressed shell with blunt tubercles. The comparable species is *A. acanthicum*, see Neumayr (1873: 195, pl. 41, fig. 1), which differs in having a less compressed shell at larger diameter. *A. caroli* exhibits larger and fewer tubercles in the two rows.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian, Lower Katrol Beds (= Shivparas Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), Ler and Fakirwadi (Spath, 1931, p. 632).

8. *Aspidoceras lerense* Spath, 1931 (pl. 122, fig. 1a, b) is depressed and evolute. It has elongate tubercles, the outer ones more prominent than the inner ones. At a diameter of 125 mm, the cast is still entirely smooth, and the lateral tubercles seem to be farther away from the umbilical spines than on the inner whorls. This way the species somewhat resembles *Aspidoceras wynnei* Waagen (1875, pl. 22), but it is difficult to evaluate exactly to which extent the reconstruction of the figure of Waagen (1875) corresponds to the facts. In any case, its inner tubercles are more prominent, and is more inflated than *A. lerense*.

Stratigraphic distribution. "Kimmeridgian, Katrol Beds Middle ?" (=Tapkeshwari Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), Ler (Spath 1931, p. 634).

9. *Aspidoceras* aff. *hoplisum* (Oppel, 1863) in Spath (1931, pl. 118, figs. 1a, b.) is characterised by involute and globose inner whorls with closely spaced pairs of tubercles arranged in two rows. Tubercles of the inner row are small, slightly elongated, oriented at right angle to the direction of coiling, whereas tubercles of the outer row are large, circular in outline. The corresponding tubercles are comparatively close to each other and joining with thick ribs.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (=Tapkeshwari Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), "East Ler" (Spath, 1931, p. 635).

10. *Aspidoceras iphiceroides* Waagen (1875, pl. 23, figs. 1-2; Spath, 1931, p. 635, pl. 123, fig. 8a, b) is large and has a thick, rounded whorl section similar to *A. wynnei*, but carries irregular granules and can be distinguished from *A. binodiferum* by less strong, less numerous, more irregular tubercles.

Stratigraphic distribution. "Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds)" (=Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, North of Dhosa, and Charwar range (=Tapkeshwari Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), south of Bhuj (Waagen, 1875, p. 103; Spath, 1931, p. 636).

11. *Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen (1875, pl. 24; Spath, 1931: 636, pl. 118, fig. 4) is characterised by very coarse, irregularly placed tuberculation, in comparison to less coarse tubercles in *A. binodum* and *A. iphioeroides*.

Stratigraphic distribution. Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (=Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, North of Dhosa (Waagen, 1875, p. 105; Spath, 1931, p. 636).

12. *Aspidoceras* cf. *binodum* Oppel (1863), see Spath (1931, pl. 119, fig. 2a, b). It is characterised by a depressed whorl section with broad ventral region and very narrow flanks and indistinct umbilical shoulder. It is more depressed than *A. binodiferum*.

Stratigraphic distribution. Lower Kimmeridgian (Lower Katrol Beds) (=Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, “East” Ler, Fakirwadi and Samatra (Spath, 1931, p. 638).

13. *Aspidoceras wynnei* Waagen (1875, pl. 22; Spath, 1931, p. 638, pl. 124, fig. 7) is characterized by a large shell with thick whorl section, more inflated than *A. lerense* and carries large tubercles, the outer row of which is placed more marginally. “Twelve outer tubercles probably were originally all of the same size” (Spath, 1931, p. 639), umbilical tubercles are less prominent. This species is close to the less inflated forms such as *A. sp. nov. ? aff. longispinum* and to *A. lerense*.

Stratigraphic distribution. Middle Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (= Tapkeshwari Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, East of Ler, “Ler-Hamundra-Ellipse” “Jadura”, Katrol Range, and “Moondan Group” (= Green Ammonite Member (Lower Tithonian), Jhuran Formation (Waagen, 1875, p. 105; Spath, 1931, p. 639).

14. *Aspidoceras subwynnei* Spath, 1931 is characterized by a large shell with thick whorl section and large tubercles. This species resembles *A. wynnei* but carries blunter and more prominent outer tubercles, set closer to the feeble, though large scars of tubercles of the inner row, and has a more inflated whorl section.

Stratigraphic distribution. Middle Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (= Tapkeshwari Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, East of Ler and Walakhavas (Spath, 1931, p. 640).

15. *Aspidoceras* cf. *taverai* Checa, 1985 in Krishna *et al.* (1994, pl. 1, figs. 1a, b, 2a, b) is characterized by uneven size of tubercles, moderately evolute shells with rounded depressed whorl section, convex flanks and broad ventral region. Umbilical shoulder rounded, wall vertical or slightly inclined. Tubercles rounded, not very regular in distribution, those of the inner row smaller and less in number compared to those those of the outer row nearly at the middle of flank height.

Stratigraphic distribution. Basal Berriasian, South-East and South-West of Ler (Checa, 1985, p. 109; Krishna *et al.*, 1994, p. 332).

***Aspidoceras* cf. *acanthicum* (Oppel, 1863)**

Pl. XXI, figs 1-3

cf. 1863. *Ammonites acanthicum* Oppel, p. 219.

cf. 1873. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Neumayr, p. 195, pl. 41, fig. 1.

cf. 1931. *Aspidoceras* aff. *acanthicum* (Oppel) – Spath, p. 624, pl. 123, fig. 7.

cf. 1959. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Collignon, pl.128, figs. 479, 480.

cf. 1984. *Aspidoceras* aff. *A. acanthicum* (Oppel) – Verma and Westermann, p. 66, pl. 15, fig. 1.

cf. 1994. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Schlegelmilch, p. 126, pl. 68, fig. 3, pl. 71, fig. 4.

cf. 1997. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Cariou and Hantzpergue, pl. 24, fig. 8.

cf. 1999. *Aspidoceras (Aspidoceras) acanthicum acanthicum* (Oppel) – Fatmi & Zeiss, p. 73, pl. 34, fig. 3a, b, pl. 35, fig. 2a, b.

cf. 2011. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Baudouin *et al.*, pl. 11, fig. 6.

cf. 2013. *Physodoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Fözy & Scherzinger, p. 185, pl. 11, fig. 3, pl. 12, fig. 1.

cf. 2021. *Aspidoceras acanthicum* (Oppel) – Bujtor *et al.*, p. 290, fig. 9. D1-D2.

Material: A single specimen (RUC2016 ILOD 8) from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member (early Late Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell small, moderately evolute, inner whorls depressed, becoming less depressed with increasing diameter. Whorl section sub-trigonal with slightly arched flanks merging smoothly with acutely rounded ventral region. Maximum thickness at umbilical shoulder. Outer whorl smooth. Inner whorls ornamented with two rows of small tubercles, one along mid-lateral and the other near umbilical shoulder. On outer whorl, outer lateral row composed of obscured tubercles, whereas tubercles of inner umbilical row almost disappeared. Umbilical walls high, vertical, with distinct, acutely rounded umbilical shoulder.

Remarks: The specimen preserves a small part of the body chamber. The dimensional proportions, whorl section with narrow venter, and small tubercles in the present specimen match *A. aff. acanthicum* in Spath (1931, pl. 123, fig. 7a, b) recorded from the Lower Katrol beds (= Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation) of Lodai. In this specimen the outer tubercles are lost at an early growth stage, which is also the case in the present specimen. The whorl section and ornamentation also match the lectotype of *A. acanthicum* figured by Neumayr (1873, pl. 41). The umbilicus in that specimen is slightly larger, but the percentual width of umbilicus to diameter ratio recorded by Spath (1931, p. 626) for *A. acanthicum* shows a large range (i.e., from 27 to 35). The ornamentation of the present specimen also corresponds to that of *A. asymmetricum* Spath (1931, pl. 103, fig. 2, pl. 118, fig. 3a, b, pl. 119, fig. 3, pl. 123, fig. 3) from the Belemnite

Marls of the lower Katrol beds (= Jhuran River Member) of the Jhuran river section. However, the whorl section of *A. asymmetricum* is more inflated and rounded.

Provenance: According to the biozonation for the South Tethyan margin proposed by Krishna *et al.* (1996, 2009b, 2011) and for the North Tethyan margin by Cariou and Hantzpergue (1997), *A. acanthicum* is a guide ammonite of the early Late Kimmeridgian.

***Aspidoceras aff. bispinosum* (Zieten, 1830)**

Pl. XXI, figs 4-7

aff. 1830. *Ammonites bispinosus* Zieten, p. 22, pl. 16, fig. 4a-c.

aff. 1924. *Physidoceras cf. binodiferum* (Waagen) – Spath, p. 15 (pars)

aff. 1931. *Aspidoceras aff. bispinosum* (Zieten) – Spath, p. 627

Material: A single specimen (RUC2016 ILOD 16) from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Remarks: The specimen is poorly preserved, most of the inner whorls recrystallized. The outermost whorl is body chamber. It carries two rows of small, distant but regularly spaced tubercles. The whorl section is compressed, oval. The whorl section, umbilical diameter, distantly spaced tubercles on the outer whorl, and dimensional proportions of the present specimen are quite close to *A. bispinosum*, which is characterized by a few whorls with two rows of tubercles like *A. longispinus*. Apart from *A. cf. acanthicum*, all taxa of *Aspidoceras* recorded from the Kachchh Basin are depressed and show a round whorl section. The type specimen of *A. bispinosum* is lost and therefore its identification is problematic (see Schairer & Barthel, 1979).

Distribution: Spath recorded this taxon from the Belemnite Marls (= Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation), north of Jhuran. Kutek & Zeiss (1997) recorded this species from the Late Eudoxus Zone, Błogie-Nadzieja, Tuszyn (central Poland).

***Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**

Pl. XXII, figs 1-3

1931. *Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath, p. 629, pl. 118, fig. 3a, b

Material: One microconch (RUC2016 ILOD 5) and one macroconch (RUC2015 JH 26) from unit 9 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation; and from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shells small to moderately large, composed of phragmocone and part of body chamber; moderately evolute and depressed. Whorl section subcircular to suboval with slightly arched flanks passing smoothly into the strongly arched venter; steep but arched umbilical wall and distinct obtusely rounded umbilical shoulder. Maximum thickness within one-fourth of whorl height. Ornamentation consisting of equal, coarse tubercles arranged evenly in two closely associated peri-umbilical and lateral rows.

Remarks: The maximum diameter of specimen RUC2015 NJH 26 is approximately 137 mm. This is a poorly preserved mould, mostly embedded in a hard matrix, but traces of the original shell have been observed. This specimen represents a large phragmocone (macroconch). The second specimen (RUC2016 ILOD 5) is smaller (microconch) and most part of it is crushed. Sutures lines are not visible, most probably the outer whorl represents the body chamber. The outer whorl is crushed because it was not supported by septa. The two specimens are similar in ornamentation, whorl section, and dimensional proportions representing macroconch and microconch, respectively. The whorl section, height-thickness ratio, and closely arranged, coarsely bi-tuberculate ornamentation match *A. asymmetricum*. The size and regular pairing of the two rows of tubercles is close to *A. aff. acanthicum* in Spath (1931, pl. 123, fig. 7a, b), which has a narrower venter, less depressed whorl section, and smaller tubercles, as well as to *A. binodiferum*, which has a broader venter and fewer and coarser tubercles.

Distribution: Kimmeridgian (Belemnite Marls-Lower Katrol Group) (=Jhuran River Member (Alterneplicatus Zone, Jhuran River section), “Joorun” (Spath, 1931, p. 630; Pandey *et al.*, 2013b). Lower part of the Lothia Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River Section and the Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

***Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen, 1875**

Pl. XXII, figs 4-7

1875. *Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen, p. 105, pl. 24
1931. *Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen – Spath, p. 636, pl. 118, fig. 4

Material: Six specimens (RUC2015 JH 18, RUC2016 ILOD 6, 7, 15, 20, 25) from unit 9 of the Jhuran River section, lower part of the Lothia Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation; and from unit 75 of the Lodai section, Jhuran River Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Moderately large internal and composite moulds, moderately evolute, inner whorls depressed, progressively becoming less depressed. Whorl section subrounded to suboval with faintly arched flanks

merging smoothly with moderately arched ventral region. Maximum thickness at or near umbilical shoulder. Ornamentation consisting of very fine, closely spaced growth lines and two rows of moderately distant, occasionally irregularly spaced tubercles. Tubercles gradually fade on body chamber. Periumbilical tubercles appearing smaller than lateral tubercles, the later spinose. Occasionally, very faint rib-like folds may connect periumbilical and lateral tubercles and also showing feeble secondary folds on broad ventral region. Umbilical wall high and steep.

Remarks: The specimens represent both internal and composite moulds. The largest two specimens (RUC2016 ILOD 20, 25) are phragmocones with moderately distinct sutures lines and a small part of the body chamber. The specimens carry two rows of well-preserved tubercles; both peri-umbilical and lateral. The peri-umbilical tubercles are broken. It is, therefore, not known whether originally, they were spinose or simple tubercles. In the smaller one of the two specimens (RUC2016 ILOD 7) the chambers of the inner whorls are filled with calcite, while the outermost whorl is filled with sediment and most probably represents the body chamber. Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 6 also does not show any suture line on the outer most whorl. The present specimens are comparable to *A. binodiferum* in dimensional proportions (at $D = 210$ mm, $H/D = 41$, $T/D = 45$, $U/D = 32$) and in the number of tubercles per whorl. Although the species is known for the very regularly paired rows of tubercles, occasionally, as in specimen RUC2016 ILOD 6, a slight irregularity in the pattern of tubercles can also be seen in the figure given by Waagen (1875).

The distribution of tubercles is as in *A. wynnei*, but this possesses fewer tubercles (9-12) than the specimens RUC2016 ILOD 6, 20 (13-14). The dimensional proportions in this specimen are also like those of *Ammonites iphicerus* Oppel, 1863 (pl. 60, fig. 4a, b), particularly the wide umbilicus, but Neumayr (1873, pl. 42, fig. 1) merged the species with *A. longispinum*, in which the tubercles have an elongated base and are fewer. The whorl section of *A. longispinum* is also more rounded than in the present specimens. In *A. iphiceroides* the tubercle pattern in the two rows is more irregular. It would be important to study whether irregularities, in the distribution pattern of tubercles, are truly a diagnostic feature of the different species.

Distribution: Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (=Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, North of Dhosa (Waagen, 1875, p. 105; Spath, 1931, p. 637).

Aspidoceras iphiceroides Waagen, 1875
Pl. XXII, figs 8-10

1875. *Aspidoceras iphiceroides* Waagen, p. 102, pl. 23.

1931. *Aspidoceras iphiceroides* Waagen – Spath, p. 635, pl. 123, fig. 8a, b.

Material: A single specimen (RUC2017 IGD 1) from unit 14 of the Gangeshwar Dome section, Shivparas Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation.

Description: Shell moderately large, incomplete, moderately evolute, depressed. Whorl section thick, rounded, lateral flanks feebly arched, merging smoothly with broadly arched ventral region. Maximum thickness falling between two rows of tubercles. Ornamentation consisting of two close rows of regularly spaced tubercles confined to lower half of flank, leaving upper half of the flank smooth. Lateral tubercles thick. Occasionally, very faint rib-like folds may connect peri-umbilical and lateral tubercles.

Remarks: The specimen represents only part of the phragmocone. Waagen (1875, p. 102) estimated a diameter of 150 to 180 mm of the fully grown specimens. The dimensional proportions, smooth, high and broad ventral region, and the two closely spaced rows of tubercles match *A. iphiceroides*. Other similar species such as *A. subwynnei* either possess much larger tubercles, or possess a less depressed whorl section such as *A. sesquinodosum* or a greater diameter of the umbilicus such as *A. lerense*. *A. iphiceroides* is a subzonal guide species and represent an early Late Kimmeridgian age.

Distribution: Kimmeridgian (Middle Katrol Beds) (=Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, North of Dhosa, and Charwar range (=Tapkeshwari Member, Acanthicum Zone, Jhuran Formation), south of Bhuj (Waagen, 1875: 103; Spath, 1931: 636).

6. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

The 112 Kimmeridgian ammonites representing 39 taxa that have been collected bed-by-bed from the eastern part of Kachchh Mainland allow several taxonomic and stratigraphic inferences to be drawn. These ammonites belong to 12 genera of the families Phylloceratidae, Oppeliidae, Ataxioceratidae, and Aspidoceratidae. Some of the ammonite species are endemic to the Indo-East-African faunal province, such as *T. alterneplicatus*, *T. intermedius*, *K. katrolensis*, and *A. iphiceroides*. A few ammonites, however, such as *Aspidoceras* cf. *acanthicum* and *P. digitata* are mainly recorded from the Mediterranean and/or Submediterranean faunal provinces. *A. acanthicum* is a guide/index species of the Tethyan ammonite zonation. Dimorphic pairs in some of the endemic taxa, such as *T. alterneplicatus*, *T. alterneplicatus* morph neglecta, *T. intermedius*, *T. acuticostatus*, *K. waageni*, and *A. asymmetricum* have been recognised for the first time. The north Tethyan

ammonites, together with forms endemic to the Indo–East African faunal province, help in refining or corroborating the Kimmeridgian ammonite zonation delineated by earlier workers. The record of *S. cf. lamplughii* in the studied collection suggests that there is no palaeogeographic limit for the genus *Subdichotomoceras*. This is in contrast to the earlier view of its restriction to the Boreal Faunal Realm (Énay, 1972: p. 374; Verma & Westermann, 1984, p. 38; Krishna & Pathak, 1993, p. 232; see also Énay *et al.*, 2014, p. 330).

Several specimens were difficult to assign to *Torquatisphinctes* or *Pachysphinctes*, particularly when the body chamber is not preserved. In the Kachchh specimens, the biplicate ribs are slightly coarse and distant as in early whorls of *Pachysphinctes* but single primary ribs are still common as in *Torquatisphinctes*. Waagen (1875) and Spath (1931) created confusion in their identifications of several species of *Torquatisphinctes*. Unfortunately, all the specimens in their collections were small, and whether they represent only inner whorls of microconchs or macroconchs or juveniles is not always clear. In some of the large specimens of the present collection thick, distant folds on the outer part of the phragmocone of *Torquatisphinctes* have been recorded. Since the inner whorls in all the three genera, i.e. *Torquatisphinctes*, *Pachysphinctes* and *Katrolliceras* show comparable thin, sharp, bifurcating/trifurcating ornamentation, whereas the outer part of the phragmocone shows either, thick rounded smooth folds as in *Torquatisphinctes* (pl. V, figs. 5, 6) and *Pachysphinctes* (pl. XV, figs. 3, 4) or thick, sharp, distant, trifurcate primary ribs with intercalatories as in *Katrolliceras* (pl. XVIII, figs. 1, 2, 4), identification based only on inner whorls becomes difficult. There are some key morphological characters, such as flattish flanks in *Pachysphinctes* and slightly arched flanks in *Katrolliceras*. In general, in *Torquatisphinctes* the primary ribs are thin and after an initially forwardly directed concavity at or near the umbilical shoulder they become straight prorsiradiate. They are slightly coarser and sinuous in *Pachysphinctes*. In *Katrolliceras* they are thinner as in *Torquatisphinctes*, with a straight to slight forwardly directed concavity.

We have found that for the identification of Kimmeridgian ammonites, particularly of the various species of *Torquatisphinctes*, the following points need to be taken into in special consideration:

(1) *Size of the adult*. The adult size of the individuals in a sedimentary basin may change, in response to changes in bathymetry or through phyletic evolution as recorded by Krishna & Pathak (1991; also see Krishna *et al.*, 1996; Krishna, 2017). In some cases when the shell is not complete, the thickness, spacing and orientation of ribs can be confusing, e.g. between *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* and *T. habyensis* and also the immature form of *Pachysphinctes major*. The inner whorls of these species are quite similar and, in some cases, also suggest connecting links (Spath, 1931, p. 484). In the

case of the first two, *T. intermedius* has a larger adult phragmocone: ($D = 121\text{--}184$ mm, $U/D = 46\text{--}51\%$) than *T. habyensis* ($D = 70\text{--}80$ mm, $U/D = 40\text{--}42\%$).

(2) *Constrictions*. To understand the function of constrictions is very significant. In several ammonite genera, constrictions occur in various numbers per whorl. Occasionally, they are regarded diagnostic of a taxon. The question is whether constrictions are a specific morphological character in some species, or they are a structural necessity for the growth of the shell in different environmental settings? Why do not all shells show constrictions? Or why is there an uneven distribution of constrictions in some individuals? Some individuals show deep constrictions, others show shallow ones, still others none. In some cases, constrictions are observed on inner whorls and not on outer whorls. This may be related to ontogeny, recapitulating adult features of the preceding phylogenetic stage. Constrictions can be oblique or parallel to the remaining ornamentation. In some cases, the end part of the body chamber shows quite conspicuous constrictions. Possibly, constrictions document a break in growth due to some physiological changes in the organism. The study of internal structure along the constrictions in various ammonite families indicated continuous growth without any interruption (Radtke & Keupp, 2016). This suggests that constrictions are behavioural response of an organism to environmental or physiological changes. Consequently, number of constrictions per whorl, their orientation and dimensions may not be regarded as diagnostic of a taxon.

Based on first occurrence and on the abundance of endemic *T. alterneplicatus*, *T. intermedius*, *P. bathyplocus*, and *K. katrolensis*, four Kimmeridgian zones, ranging from late Early Kimmeridgian to Late Kimmeridgian, were proposed in the Kachchh Basin: the Alterneplicatus, Intermedius, Bathyplocus, and Katrolensis zones (Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009, 2011; Krishna & Pathak, 1991, 1993; Krishna, 2017). The early Early Kimmeridgian strata could not be recorded in the Mainland part of the Kachchh Basin due to a major stratigraphic gap from the Late Oxfordian to early Early Kimmeridgian (Fig. 2).

The Torquatisphinctinae represent, in the study area, a single lineage from the late Early Kimmeridgian to the end of the Kimmeridgian. A gradual change in ornamentation from the Intermedius Zone to the Katrolensis Zone and individually within the Bathyplocus and Katrolensis zones is observed, which is quite notable. In fact, within the Bathyplocus and Katrolensis zones, several successively younger morphs in increasingly younger horizons have been recognized (see Krishna *et al.*, 1996; Pandey *et al.*, 2010; Krishna 2017). This is based either on the position of the appearance of the first triplicate rib in the body chamber (in the case of Bathyplocus Zone), or the first appearance of the abruptly modified (cuniform, wedge-shaped) primary ribs from the last quarter to the start of the body chamber in successively younger morphs (in

the case of Katrolensis Zone). In addition, a size increase is also observed towards the end of the Katrolensis Zone (Krishna *et al.*, 1996); see also Table 2 this report. These features are very significant for intra-basinal time-correlations. Individually, these Kimmeridgian ammonite zones have been correlated with the Tethyan Kimmeridgian ammonite zones; the *Alterneplicatus* Zone with the *Divisum* Zone, the *Intermedius* Zone with the *Acanthicum* Zone, the *Bathyplocus* Zone with the *Eudoxus* Zone and the *Cavouri* Zone, and the *Katrolensis* Zone with the *Beckeri* Zone.

Surprisingly, earlier workers (Krishna *et al.*, 1996, 2009, 2011; Krishna & Pathak, 1991, 1993; Krishna, 2017) did not use the Tethyan zonal names (Hesselbo *et al.*, 2020), in spite of the record of Tethyan zonal fossils in the Kachchh Basin. For example, *A. acanthicum* (Opper) has been recorded together with *T. intermedius* Spath. *A. acanthicum* is confined to the *Intermedius* Zone, whereas *T. intermedius* continues from the underlying *Alterneplicatus* Zone. For a uniform biostratigraphic framework, identification of the *Acanthicum* Zone in Kachchh would have been more appropriate. Further, the lower four Kimmeridgian Tethyan ammonite zones (*Bimammatum*, *Planula*, *Platynota*, and *Hypselocyclum*) have been recorded in the Wagad Uplift in the eastern part of the Kachchh Basin, albeit without any evidence of guide ammonites. The record of *Orthosphinctes*, *Subnebrodites*, and *Ataxioceras*, and the postulation of a *Bimammatum* to *Hypselocyclum* zones age for the Adhoi Member in the Wagad Uplift of eastern Kachchh (Krishna *et al.*, 2009; also see Alberti *et al.*, 2019) is worth reinvestigating.

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REFERENCES

- Alberti, M., Fürsich, F. T., Pandey, D. K., Mukherjee, D., Andersen, N. & Garbe-Schönberg, D. 2022. Middle to Late Jurassic stable isotopes and element ratios of fossils from western India: Developing a reference temperature curve for northeastern Gondwana. *Global and Planetary Change*, 212: 103795.
- Alberti, M., Fürsich, F. T. & Pandey, D. K. 2019. Sedimentology of a prograding delta complex: The Jurassic succession of the Wagad Uplift in the Kachchh Basin, western India. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 292: 1–24.
- Alberti, M., Pandey, D. K. & Fürsich, F. T. 2011. Ammonites of the genus *Peltoceratoides* Spath, 1924 from the Oxfordian of Kachchh, western India. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 262: 1–18.
- Alberti, M., Pandey, D. K., Hethke, M. & Fürsich, F. T. 2015. Ammonites of the subfamily Mayaitinae Spath, 1928 from the Oxfordian of Kachchh, Western India. *Geobios*, 48: 85–130.
- Ammon, L. v. 1875. *Die Jura-Ablagerungen zwischen Regensburg und Passau*. Theodor Ackermann, München, X+200 p.
- Arkell, W. J. 1940. A monograph on the ammonites of the English Corallian beds. Part VI. *Palaeontographical Society London*, 94: lxxv-lxxii, 191–216, pls. 41–47.
- Arkell, W. J. 1950. A classification of the Jurassic ammonites. *Journal of Paleontology*, 24: 354–364.
- Arkell, W. J. 1953. Seven new genera of Jurassic ammonites. *Geological Magazine*, 90: 36–40.
- Arkell, W. J., Kummel, B. & Wright, C. W. 1957. Mesozoic Ammonoidea. In: Moore, R. C. (Ed.). *Treatise on Invertebrate Paleontology, Part L, Mollusca 4, Cephalopoda, Ammonoidea*. The Geological Society of America and the University of Kansas Press, New York and Lawrence: L80–L437.
- Atrops, F. 1982. La sous-famille des *Ataxioceratinae* (Ammonitina) dans le Kimmeridgien inférieur du sud-est de la France. Systématique, évolution, chronostratigraphie des genres *Orthosphinctes* et *Ataxioceras*. *Travaux et Documents de Laboratoire de Géologie de Lyon*, 83: 1–463.
- Baudouin, C., Boselli, P. & Bert, D. 2011. The Opperliidae of the *Acanthicum* Zone (Upper Kimmeridgian) from Mount Crussol (Ardèche, France): ontogeny, variability and dimorphism of the genera *Taramelliceras* and *Streblites* (Ammonoidea). *Revue de Paléobiologie*, 30: 619–684.
- Benecke, E. W. 1865. Über Trias und Jura in Südalpen. *Geognostische-Paläontologische Beiträge*, 1(1): 1–204.
- Biswas, S. K. 1980. Mesozoic rock-stratigraphy of Kutch, Gujarat. *The Quarterly Journal of the Geological, Mining, and Metallurgical Society of India*, 49: 1–52. (for 1977)
- Biswas, S. K. 2016a. Mesozoic and Tertiary stratigraphy of Kutch (Kachchh) – a review. In: Thakkar, M. G. (Ed.). *Recent studies on the geology of Kachchh*. The Geological Society of India, Special Publication, 6: 1–24.
- Biswas, S. K. 2016b. Tectonic framework, structure and tectonic evolution of Kutch Basin, western India. In: Thakkar, M. G. (Ed.). *Recent studies on the geology of*

- Kachchh. The Geological Society of India, Special Publication*, 6: 129–150.
- Biswas, S. K., Mahender, K. & Chauhan, G. 2022. *Field book of geology of Kutch (Kachchh) Basin, Gujarat, India. Springer Geology Field Guides*. Springer Nature, Cham, 183 p.
- Bruder, G. 1885. Die Fauna der Jura-Ablagerung von Hohnstein in Sachsen. *Denkschriften der kaiserlichen Akademie der Wissenschaften Wien, mathematisch-naturwissenschaftliche Klasse*, 50: 233–283.
- Buckman, S. S. 1909–1930. *Yorkshire Type Ammonites, with indexes by A. Morley Davies*. Wheldon & Wesley, London, volumes 1–7: 790 p.
- Bujtor, L., Albrecht, R., Farkas, C., Mako, M., Maroti, D. & Miklosy, A. 2021. Kimmeridgian and early Tithonian cephalopods from the Kisujbanya Limestone Formation, Zengővarkony (Mecsek Mountains, southern Hungary), their faunal composition, palaeobiogeographic affinities, and taphonomic character. *Carnets de Géologie*, 21, no. 13: 265–314.
- Burckhardt, C. 1912. Faunes Jurassiques et Cretaciques de San Pedro del Gallo, Durango. *Boletín del Instituto de Geología de México*, 29: 1–264.
- Cariou, E., Énay, R., Atrops, F., Hantzpergue, P., Marchand, D. & Rioult, M. 1997. *Oxfordien*. In: Cariou, E. & Hantzpergue, P. (Eds). Groupe français d'étude du Jurassique: Biostratigraphie du Jurassique ouest-européen et méditerranéen: zonations parallèles et distribution des invertébrés et microfossiles. *Bulletin des Centres de Recherche Exploration-Production Elf-Aquitaine, Mémoire*, 17: 79–86.
- Checa, A. 1985. Los aspidoceratiforme en Europa (Ammonitina, Aspidoceratidae: subfamilias Aspidoceratinae y Physodoceratinae). *Tesis doctoral Universidad de Granada*, 413 p.
- Collignon, M. 1956. Ammonites néocrétacées du Menabe (Madagascar) IV. Les Phylloceratidae. V. Les Gaudryceratidae. VI. Les Tetragnostidae. *Annales Géologiques du Service des Mines de Madagascar*, 23: 1–106.
- Collignon, M. 1959. *Atlas des fossiles caractéristiques de Madagascar. 5 (Kimmeridgien)*. République malgache, Service géologique, Tananarive, pls. 96–133.
- Cuvier, G. L. 1797. *Tableau élémentaire de l'Histoire Naturelle des Animaux*. Paris: Baudouin.
- Dietrich, W. O. 1925. Über eine dem mittleren Sauriermergel am Tendaguru äquivalente, rein marine Kimmeridgebildung in Mahokondo, Deutsch-Ostafrika. *Palaeontographica, Supplement*, 7 (2, 1): 1–24.
- d'Orbigny, A. 1842–1851. *Paléontologie Française ; Terrains Oolitiques ou Jurassiques*. I, Céphalopodes. Masson. Paris. 642 p., 234 pl. Pages 1–80 (1842); p. 81–192 (1843); p. 193–312 (1844); p. 313–368 (1845); p. 369–432 (1846); p. 433–464 (1847); p. 465–504 (1848); p. 505–520 (1849); p. 521–632 (1850); p. 633–642 (1851).
- Dumortier, E. & Fontannes, F. 1876. Description de la zone à Ammonites tenuilobatus de Crussol. *Mémoires de l'Académie de Lyon, Classe des Sciences*, 21: 187–342.
- Ebbighausen, V. & Korn, D. 2007. Conch geometry and ontogenetic trajectories in the triangularly coiled Late Devonian ammonoid *Wocklumeria* and related genera. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 244: 9–41.
- Énay, R. & Howarth, M. K. 2019. Treatise on Invertebrate Paleontology, Part L, Volume 3B, Chapter 7: Systematic Descriptions of the Perisphinctoidea. *Treatise Online* 120: 1–184.
- Énay, R. 1972. Paléobiogéographie des Ammonites du Jurassique terminal (Tithonique/Volgien/Portlandien) et mobilité continentale. *Geobios*, 5: 355–407. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-6995\(72\)80013-5](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0016-6995(72)80013-5)
- Énay, R. 2009. Les faunes d'ammonites de l'Oxfordien au Tithonien et la biostratigraphie des Spiti-Shales (Callovien supérieur–Tithonien) de Thakkola, Népal Central. *Travaux et Documents des Laboratoires de Géologie Lyon*, 166: 1–351.
- Énay, R. & Howarth, M. K. 2017. The Upper Oxfordian and Lower Kimmeridgian ammonite genera *Idoceras* Burckhardt, 1906, and *Subnebrodites* Spath, 1925. *Paleontological Contributions*, 17: 1–4.
- Énay, R., Gallois, R. & Etches, S. 2014. Origin of the Kimmeridgian–Tithonian Boreal perisphinctid faunas: migration and descendants of the Tethyan genera *Crussolicerias* and *Garnierisphinctes*. *Revue de Paléobiologie*, 33: 299–377.
- Fatmi, A. N. & Zeiss, A. 1999. First Upper Jurassic and Lower Cretaceous (Berriasian) ammonites from the Sembar Formation (Belemnite shales), Windar Nai, Lasbela – Balochistan, Pakistan. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of Pakistan*, 19: 1–114.
- Főzy, I. & Scherzinger, A. 2013. Systematic descriptions of Kimmeridgian ammonites of the Gerecse and Pilis Mountains, p. 167–206. In: Főzy I. (ed.), Late Jurassic–Early Cretaceous fauna, biostratigraphy, facies and deformation history of the carbonate formations in the Gerecse and Pilis Mountains (Transdanubian Range, Hungary). *GeoLitera Publishing House, Szeged*, 422 p.
- Főzy, I., Scherzinger, A. & Szives, O. 2022. Late Jurassic–Early Cretaceous (Kimmeridgian–Barremian) ammonites of the Bakony Mountains (Transdanubian Range, Hungary), In: Főzy, I. (Ed.). Fauna, biostratigraphy, facies and paleotectonic evolution of the Late Jurassic–Early Cretaceous formations in the Bakony Mountains (Transdanubian Range, Hungary). *GeoLitera Publishing House, Szeged*: 243–360.
- Fürsich, F. T., Alberti, M. & Pandey, D. K. 2013. Stratigraphy and palaeoenvironments of the Jurassic rocks of Kachchh. Field guide. *Beringeria, Special Issue*, 7: 1–174.
- Fürsich, F. T., Alberti, M. & Pandey, D. K. 2023. The Kachchh Rift Basin of western India: Jurassic lithostratigraphy revisited. *The Palaeontological Society of India, Special Publication*, 5: 1–141.
- Fürsich, F. T., Alberti, M., Pandey, D. K., Chaskar, K. & Bhosale, S. 2021. Facies analysis and palaeoecology of the Jurassic Spiti Shale Formation in the Spiti area, northern India. *Journal of Palaeogeography*, 10: 438–462.
- Fürsich, F. T., Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M., Mukherjee, D. & Chauhan, G. 2020. *Stratigraphic architecture and palaeoenvironments in the Kachchh Rift Basin during the Jurassic*. 36th International Geological Congress, Delhi, Field Trip Guide WR010: 142 p.
- Futterer, K. 1894. Beiträge zur Kenntniss des Jura in Ost-Afrika. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen geologischen Gesellschaft*, 46: 1–49.
- Gemmellaro, G.G. 1872. Sopra i Cefalopodi della zona con *Aspidoceras acanthicum* OPP. sp. di Burgilamuni presso Favara, provincia di Girgenti. *Giornale di Scienze Naturali ed Economiche*, VIII: 30–52, 4 pls., Palermo.
- Geyer, O. F. 1961. Monographie der Perisphinctidae des unteren Unterkimmeridgium (Weisser Jura γ , Badenerschichten) im süddeutschen Jura. *Palaeontographica*, A, 117: 1–157.
- Głowniak, E. & Wierzbowski, A. 2007. Taxonomical revision of the perisphinctid ammonites of the Upper Jurassic

- (Plicatilis to Planula zones) described by Józef Siemiradzki (1891) from the Kraków Upland. *Volumina Jurassica*, 5: 27–137.
- Gümbel, C. W. 1864. Die geognostischen Verhältnisse der Fränkischen Alb (Franken-Jura). *Bavaria, Landes- und Volkskunde des Königreichs Bayern*, 3(9): 1–74.
- Gygi, R. A. 2003. Perisphinctacean ammonites of the Late Jurassic in northern Switzerland: A versatile tool to investigate the sedimentary geology of an epicontinental sea. *Schweizerische Paläontologische Abhandlungen*, 123: 1–232.
- Haeckel, E. 1866. *Generelle Morphologie der Organismen. Zweiter Band: Allgemeine Entwicklungsgeschichte der Organismen*. G. Reimer, Berlin: 462 p. <https://doi.org/10.1515/9783110848281>
- Herbich, F. 1878. Das Széklerland mit Berücksichtigung der angrenzenden Landestheile, geologisch und paläontologisch beschrieben. *Jahrbuch der königlichen ungarischen geologischen Anstalt*, 5, no. 2: 111 [93–186 [168]].
- Hesselbo, S. P., Ogg, J. G. & Ruhl, M. with contributions by L. A. Hinnov and C. J. Huang 2020. *The Jurassic Period*. In: Gradstein, F. M., Ogg, J. G., Schmitz, M. D. & Ogg, G. M. (Eds.). *Geologic Time Scale*. Elsevier, Amsterdam: 955–1021. DOI: <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-12-824360-2.00026-7>
- Hyatt, A. 1900. *Cephalopoda*. In: Zittel, K. A. *Textbook of Palaeontology*, 1st English ed., 502–592.
- Joly, B. 2000. Les Juraphyllitidae, Phylloceratidae, Neophylloceratidae (Phyllocerataceae, Phylloceratina, Ammonoidea) de France au Jurassique et au Crétacé. *Geobios*, 33 (Supplement 1): 1–204.
- Kilian, W. 1907–1913. *Unterkreide (Palaeocretacicum)*. In: Frech, F. *Lethaea Geognostica, II, Mesozoicum, Band 3 (Kreide)*, Lief. 1 (1907): 1–168; Lief. 2 (1910): 169–287; Lief. 3 (1913): 289–398.
- Kobayashi, T. & Fukada, A. 1947. On the occurrence of *Katrolliceras* in the Tetori Series. *Japanese Journal of Geology and Geography, Transactions and Abstracts*, 20(2–4): 49–53.
- Krishna, J. & Pathak, D. B. 1993. Late Lower Kimmeridgian – Lower Tithonian virgatosphinctins of India: evolutionary succession and biogeographic implications. *Geobios*, 15: 227–238.
- Krishna, J. 2017. *The Indian Mesozoic chronicle: Sequence stratigraphic approach*. Springer Nature, Singapore: 694 p.
- Krishna, J. & Pathak, D. B. 1991. Ammonoid biochronology of the Upper Jurassic Kimmeridgian stage in Kachchh, India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 36: 1–13.
- Krishna, J., Pandey, B. & Pathak, D. B. 2011. Current status of the ammonoid stratigraphic framework in the India subcontinent with focus on the tectonically controlled regional transgressive-regressive couplets. *Memoir of the Geological Survey of India*, 78: 140–176.
- Krishna, J., Pandey, B., Ojha, J. R. & Pathak, D. B. 2009. Reappraisal of the age framework, correlation, environment and nomenclature of Kachchh Mesozoic lithostratigraphic units in Wagad. *Journal of Scientific Research, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi*, 53: 1–20.
- Krishna, J., Pathak, D. B. & Pandey, B. 1994. New ammonoid evidence on the Jurassic/Cretaceous boundary in Kachchh (India). *Geobios, Mémoire Special*, 17: 327–335.
- Krishna, J., Pathak, D. B. & Pandey, B. 1996. Quantum refinement in the Kimmeridgian ammonoid chronology in Kachchh (India). *GeoResearch Forum*, 1–2: 195–204.
- Lukeneder, A. 2004. Late Valanginian ammonoids: Mediterranean and boreal elements – implications on sea-level controlled migration (Ebenforst Syncline, Northern Calcareous Alps, Upper Austria). *Austrian Journal of Earth Sciences*, 95/96: 46–59.
- Lukeneder, A. 2005. An Early Cretaceous ammonoid association from Upper Austria (Late Valanginian, Northern Calcareous Alps). *Beiträge zur Paläontologie*, 29: 1–13.
- Lukeneder, A. 2015. Chapter 18: Ammonoid habitats and life history. In: Klug, C., Korn, D., De Baets, K., Kruta, I. & Mapes, R. H. (Eds.). *Ammonoid Paleobiology: From Anatomy to Ecology. Topics in Geobiology*, 43: 689–791. DOI 10.1007/978-94-017-9630-9_18.
- Neumayr, M. 1871a. I. Jura Studien. 3. Die Phylloceraten des Dogger und Malm. *Jahrbuch der kaiserlich königlichen geologischen Reichs-Anstalt*, 21: 297–354.
- Neumayr, M. 1871b. I. Jura Studien. 4. Die Verbreitung der Oxford-Gruppe im östlichen Theile der mediterranean Provinz. *Jahrbuch der kaiserlich-königlichen geologischen Reichs-Anstalt*, 21: 355–378.
- Neumayr, M. 1871c. I. Jura Studien. 5. Der penninische Klippenzug. *Jahrbuch der kaiserlich-königlichen geologischen Reichs-Anstalt*, 21: 451–536.
- Neumayr, M. 1873. Die Fauna der Schichten mit *Aspidoceras acanthicum*. *Abhandlungen der kaiserlich-königlichen Geologischen Reichsanstalt*, 5(6): 141–257.
- Oppel, A., 1862–1863. Über jurassische Cephalopoden. Paläontologische Mittheilungen aus dem Königlichen Bayerischen Staates, Stuttgart 3: 127–162, pl. 40–50 (1862); p. 163–266, pl. 51–74 (1863).
- Oppel, A. 1865. Die Tithonische Etage. *Zeitschrift der Deutschen Geologischen Gesellschaft*, 17: 535–558.
- Pandey, B., Krishna, J. & Pathak, D. B. 2010. Review of the subfamily Virgatosphinctinae with special reference to its evolutionary succession in the Indian subcontinent on the Gondwanian margin, *Journal of Scientific Research, Banaras Hindu University* 54(1-2): 1–20.
- Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M. & Fürsich, F. T. 2012. Ammonites of the genus *Perisphinctes* Waagen, 1869 from the Oxfordian of Kachchh, western India. *Revue de Paléobiologie*, 31: 483–587.
- Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M. & Fürsich, F. T. 2013a. Ammonites from the Oxfordian (Bifurcatus Zone) strata of Gangta Bet, Kachchh, western India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 58: 139–174.
- Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M. & Fürsich, F. T. 2015. Ammonites of the genera *Peltoceras* Waagen, 1871, *Metapeltoceras* Spath, 1931, and *Euaspidoceras* Spath, 1931 from the Upper Callovian and Oxfordian of Kachchh, western India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 60: 1–26.
- Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M., Fürsich, F. T., Bhaumik, S. & Ayoub-Hannaa, W. 2016. A review of the Tithonian ammonites from the Kachchh Basin, western India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 61: 141–173.
- Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M., Fürsich, F. T., Główniak, E., Olóriz, F. 2013b. Ammonites from the Oxfordian–Kimmeridgian boundary and the Lower-Upper Kimmeridgian of Kachchh, western India. *Volumina Jurassica*, 11: 97–146.

- Pandey, D. K., Fürsich, F. T., Alberti, M., Das, R. & Olóriz, S. F. 2022. First population-level study of the ammonite genus *Hildoglochiceras* Spath, and the Lower Tithonian record of the *Hildoglochiceras* Horizon in the Kachchh Basin, India. *Zitteliana* 96: 1–49.
- Parent, H., Schweigert, G., Scherzinger, A. 2020. A review of the classification of Jurassic aspidoceratid ammonites – the Superfamily Aspidoceratoidea. *Volumina Jurassica*, 18(1): 47–52.
- Patel, S. J., Joshi, P. N. & Joseph, J. K. 2012. Ammonite zonation of the Jurassic rocks of the Gangta Bet area, Wagad region, eastern Kachchh, India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 57: 129–133.
- Pathak, D. B. 1993. The Kachchh Jurassic Virgatosphinctinae, high resolution evolutionary succession and chronology. Unpublished PhD Thesis, Banaras Hindu University, Varanasi: 473 p.
- Pathak, D. B. 2007. Jurassic/Cretaceous boundary in the Spiti Himalaya, India. *Journal of the Palaeontological Society of India*, 52: 51–57.
- Pavlov, A. 1886. Les Ammonites de la zone à *Aspidoceras acanthicum* de l'Est de la Russie: *Mémoires du Comité Géologique*, 2(3): 1–91.
- Prasad, G. V. R., Pandey, D. K., Alberti, M., Fürsich, F. T., Thakkar, M. G., Chauhan, G. D. 2017. Discovery of the first ichthyosaur from the Jurassic of India: Implications for Gondwanan palaeobiogeography. *PLoS ONE* 12(10): 1–31.
- Quenstedt, F. A. 1845–1849. *Petrefactenkunde Deutschlands. I. Die Cephalopoden*. Ludwig Friedrich Fues, Tübingen: 1–104, pls. 1–6 (1845); 105–184, pl. 7–14 (1846); 185–264, pls. 15–19 (1847); 265–472, pls. 20–29 (1848); 473–580, pls. 30–36 (1849).
- Quenstedt, F. A. 1887–1888: *Die Ammoniten des schwäbischen Jura. III: Der Weisse Jura*. E. Schweizerbart'sche Verlagshandlung, Stuttgart: pp. 818–1140.
- Radtke, G. & Keupp, H. 2016. The internal structure of varices and constrictions in Jurassic and Cretaceous ammonoid shells. *Swiss Journal of Palaeontology*, 135: 109–124.
- Reinecke, I. C. M. 1818. *Maris protogaei Nautilus et Argonautas vulgo Cornua Ammonis in Agro Coburgico et vicino reperiundos etc.* C.A. Ahl, Coburg: 90 p.
- Roy, P., Mandal, S., Sur, S. & Layek, S. 2021. Cosmopolitan Status for *Taramelliceras kachhense* (Waagen) (Ammonoidea) from Kutch, Western India. In: Santanu Banerjee & Subir Sarkar (eds.): *Mesozoic Stratigraphy of India. A Multi-Proxy Approach*, 269–290.
- Schairer, G. & Barthel, K. W. 1979. Die Cephalopoden des Korallenkalks aus dem Oberen Jura von Laisacker bei Neuburg a. d. Donau, IV *Aspidoceras* Ammonoidea. *Mitteilungen der Bayerischen Staatssammlung für Paläontologie und Historische Geologie*, München, vol. 19, p. 13–26.
- Schick, H.W. 2004. Gliederung und Typusprofil der Lacunosamergel Formation (Ober Jura, Schwäbische Alb). *Stuttgarter Beiträge zur Naturkunde*, Serie B, 346: 1–25.
- Scherzinger, A., Schweigert, G. & Fözy, I. 2016. First record of the Mediterranean zonal index *Mesosimoceras cavouri* (Gemmellaro, 1872) in the Upper Jurassic (Pseudomutabilis Zone, semicostatum γ horizon) of SW Germany and its stratigraphical significance *Volumina Jurassica*, 14: 145–154.
- Schlegelmilch, R. 1994. Die Ammoniten des süddeutschen Malms. G. Fischer, Stuttgart: 297 p.
- Schneid, T. 1914. Die Geologie der Fränkischen Alb zwischen Eichstätt und Neuburg a. D. (Erste Hälfte): *Geognostische Jahreshefte*, 27: 59–172.
- Schweigert, G., Krishna, J., Pandey, B. P. & Pathak, D. B. 1996. A new approach to the correlation of the Upper Kimmeridgian Beckeri Zone across the Tethyan sea. *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 202: 345–373.
- Schweigert, G., Zeiss, A. & Westermann, G. E. G. 2012. The *Gravesia* homeomorphs from the latest Kimmeridgian of Mombasa, Kenya. *Revue de Paléobiologie, volume special*, 11: 13–25.
- Seyed-Emami, K., Schairer, G., Raoufian, A. & Shafeizad, M. 2013. Middle and Late Jurassic ammonites from the Dalichai Formation west of Shahrud (East Alborz, North Iran). *Neues Jahrbuch für Geologie und Paläontologie, Abhandlungen*, 267: 43–66.
- Smith, A. G., Smith, D. G. & Funnell, B. M. 1994. *Atlas of Mesozoic and Cenozoic Coastlines*. Cambridge University Press, New York: ix+99 p.
- Sowerby, J. de C. 1825. *The mineral conchology of Great Britain; or coloured figures and descriptions of those remains of testaceous animals or shells, which have been preserved at various times and depths in the earth. Volume 5*. Taylor, London: 168 p., pls. 408–503.
- Sowerby, J. de C. 1840. Description of fossils procured by Capt. Smee and Col. Pottinger in Cutch and the desert to the north-east of Cutch. *Transactions of the Geological Society London*, 5: explanation of plate 61.
- Spath, F. L. 1925. Ammonites and Aptychi. In: Wyllie, B. K. W. & Smellei, W. R. (Eds). *On the collections of fossils and rocks from Somaliland. Part 7. Monograph of the Geological Department of the Hunterian Museum, Glasgow University*, 4: 111–164.
- Spath, L. F. 1924. On the Blake collection of ammonites from Kachh. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India, Palaeontologia Indica, New Series*, 9(1): 1–71.
- Spath, L. F. 1927–1933. Revision of the Jurassic cephalopod fauna of Kachh (Cutch). Parts I–VI. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India, Palaeontologia Indica, new series*, 9, 2: part I, 1–71, pls. 1–7 [1927]; part II, 72–161, pls. 8–19 [1928a]; part III, 162–278, pls. 20–47 [1928b]; part IV, 279–550, pls. 48–102 [1931a]; part V, 551–658, pls. 103–124 [1931b]; part VI, 659–945, pls. 125–130 [1933].
- Steinmann, G. & Döderlein, L. 1890. *Elemente der Paläontologie*. Wilhelm Engelmann, Leipzig: 848 p.
- Tavera, J. M. 1985. Los ammonites del Tithonico superior–Berriasense de la Zona Subbética (Cordilleras Béticas). *Tesis doctoral Universidad de Granada*, 381 p.
- Uhlig, V. 1903. The Fauna of the Spiti Shales. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India, Palaeontologica Indica, series* 15, 4(1): 1–132.
- Uhlig, V. 1910. The Fauna of the Spiti Shales. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India, Palaeontologia Indica, new series*, 4(3), 307–395.
- Verma, H. M. & Westermann, G. E. G. 1984. The Ammonoid Fauna of the Kimmeridgian–Tithonian Boundary Beds of Mombasa, Kenya. *Royal Ontario Museum, Life Science Contributions*, 135: i–iv, 1–124. <https://doi.org/10.5962/bhl.title.52066>
- Waagen, W. 1869. Formenreihe des *Ammonites subradiatus*. Versuch einer paläontologischen Monographie. *Beiträge zur Geologie und Paläontologie*, 2(2): 181–256.
- Waagen, W. 1873–1875. Jurassic fauna of Kutch. The Cephalopoda. *Memoirs of the Geological Survey of India, Palaeontologia Indica, series* 9, 1: part I, 1–22, pls. 1–4

- [1873]; part II, 23–76, pls. 5–14 [1875a]; part III, 77–106, pls. 15–24 [1875b]; part IV, 107–247, pls. 25–60 [1875c].
- Zeuschner, L. 1846. *New and little-known described genera of fossils from the Tatra Mountains*. Author's printing, Warszawa: 32 p. [in Polish]
- Zieten, C. H. v. 1830–1833: *Die Versteinerungen Württembergs*. Schweizerbart, Stuttgart: 102 p.
- Zittel, K. A. 1868. Palaeontologische Studien über die Grenzschichten der Jura- und Kreide-Formation im Gebiete der Karpathen, Alpen und Apenninen. 1, Die Cephalopoden der Stramberger Schichten. *Palaeontologische Mittheilungen der Bayerischen Staatssammlung*, 2: i–vii, 1–118.
- Zittel, K. A. 1884. *Handbuch der Palaeontologie*. I. Abtheilung, II. Band, 3. Classe Cephalopoda. Kopffüßler. R. Oldenburg, München & Leipzig: 329–522.
- Zittel, K. A. v. 1895. *Grundzüge der Paläontologie*. Oldenburg, Munich & Leipzig: VIII +971 p.

Plate I

Figs. 1-3: *Holcophylloceras* cf. *polylocum* (Benecke, 1865)

Specimen RUC2016 IKH 07, Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

- 1: Lateral view of the wholly septate specimen. Note prominent, deep, strongly curved, angled constrictions.
- 2: Ventral view. Note very fine, thread-like ribs preserved along the ventral region.
- 3: Oval whorl section with acutely rounded ventral region drawn at a diameter of 74.5 mm.

Figs. 4-6: *Ptychophylloceras* cf. *ptychoicum* (Quenstedt, 1845)

Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 26, unit 75, Jhuran River Member (Early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

- 4: Lateral view. Note smooth flank and rib-like ridges (arrowed) at regular intervals confined to ventral region.
- 5: Ventral view of the same specimen showing rib-like ridges (arrowed).
- 6: Suboval to subrounded whorl section drawn at a diameter of 103 mm.

Plate II

Figs. 1-6: *Taramelliceras kachhensis* (Waagen, 1875)

Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 IKH 52.

1: Ventral view with broad venter with strong ventro-lateral tubercles on both sides of a median ventral row of smaller nodes.

2: Lateral view showing moderately thick, bifurcating, falcoid ribs.

3-6: Specimen RUC2016 IKH 34

3: Lateral view showing moderately thick, bifurcating, falcoid ribs.

4: Apertural view showing oval whorl section and ventro-lateral tubercles on both sides of a median ventral row of smaller nodes.

5: Ventral view showing broad venter with strong ventro-lateral tubercles on both sides of a median ventral row of smaller nodes.

6: Oval whorl section showing broad dome-shaped ventral region drawn at a diameter of 47 mm.

Figs. 7-13: *Metahaploceras cf. paecoei* Spath, 1928

From the unit 9 and unit 10 of the lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

7-9: Specimen RUC2015 JH 3

7: Lateral view of an almost complete shell showing outer part of phragmocone and body chamber. Ventro-lateral tubercles are indicated by arrows.

8: Ventral view showing pairs of ventro-lateral tubercles (arrowed).

9: Oval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 100 mm.

10: Specimen RUC2015 JH 27, ventral view of body chamber showing pairs of ventro-lateral tubercles (arrowed) and feeble ribs with forwardly directed sinuosity on the ventral region.

11: Specimen RUC2015 JH 28, ventral view of body chamber showing pairs of ventro-lateral tubercles (arrowed).

12-13: Specimen RUC2015 JH 19

12: Ventral view of body chamber showing pairs of ventro-lateral tubercles (arrowed).

13: Oval whorl section drawn at a diameter of approximately 95 mm.

Figs. 14-15: *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen, 1875)

Specimen RUC2015 JH 60, lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

14: Lateral view of an oxyconic phragmocone showing thick but faint falcoid ribs bifurcating at mid-lateral height with slight bulging.

15: Ventral view showing mid-ventral line of serrated keel.

Plate III

Figs. 1-6: *Streblites plicodiscus* (Waagen, 1875)

From the unit 9 and 10 of the lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1-2: Specimen RUC2015 JH 6

1: Ventral view showing acutely rounded ventral region. Note lack of ventro-lateral tubercles.

2: Lateral view of an oxyconic phragmocone and a part of body chamber

3-5: Specimen RUC2015 JH 5

3: Lateral view of phragmocone showing thick but feeble falcooid ribs in early part of last preserved whorl.

4: Whorl section drawn at a diameter of 86 mm showing acutely rounded ventral region.

5: Ventral view showing acutely rounded ventral region with traces of mid-ventral serrated keel. Note lack of ventro-lateral tubercles.

6: Specimen RUC2016 JH 1, lateral view of an oxyconic phragmocone and major part of body chamber showing very thin ornamentation near umbilical region and also secondary ribs at the periphery near early part of the last whorl representing the phragmocone. Note complex suture lines at the end of phragmocone.

Figs. 7-10: *Progeronia digitata* (Schneid, 1915)

Specimen RUC2015 JH 20 from the unit 12, i.e. lower part of the Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone to Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

7: Right lateral view showing ornamentation of body chamber; long, thick, distant prorsiradiate primary ribs and long, fasciculate secondary ribs with at least one free intercalatory rib between two adjacent branching ribs.

8: Left lateral view showing irregularly bi- or trifurcating polygyrate ribs.

9: Oval whorl section drawn at an unknown diameter showing acutely arched ventral region.

10: Ventral view showing thinner secondary ribs crossing ventral region with forwardly directed sinuosity.

Plate IV

Figs. 1-6: *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) [m]

From the unit 9 and 10, i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section; and from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member, Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 23

1: Lateral view of a wholly septate shell showing typical varicostate ornamentation; commonly, after one to three branching pairs, intercalation of a single, undivided primary rib. Note constrictions are moderately distinct.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs with no forwardly directed sinuosity.

3: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 1, subquadrangular whorl section with slightly arched flanks, drawn at a diameter of 85 mm.

4: Specimen RUC2015 JH 11, subquadrangular whorl section with slightly arched flanks, drawn at a diameter of 109 mm.

5-6: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 8

5: Lateral view of a wholly septate shell showing typical varicostate ornamentation; commonly, after one to three branching pairs, intercalation of a single, undivided primary rib.

6: Ventral view showing secondary ribs without or with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

Plate V

Figs. 1-6: *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) [M]

Specimen RUC2016 IJH 6 from the unit 9, i.e. lower part of the Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1: Right lateral view of a wholly septate shell showing ornamentation. Note distinct constrictions.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region without forwardly directed sinuosity.

3: Subtrapezoidal whorl section at a diameter of 200 mm, broken along septum.

4: Suboval/subtriangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 215 mm.

5-6: Left lateral view of a wholly septate shell showing varicostate ornamentation, with a sudden change in the thickness of ribs from closely spaced, prorsiradiate primary ribs to thick, forwardly inclined, distant folds. Note traces of suture lines in enlarged outer part (at a diameter of ~230 mm) of the phragmocone (Fig. 6).

Plate VI

Figs. 1-6: *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) morph neglecta Spath, 1931 [m]

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 14, from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (Intermediate/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

1: Lateral view showing varicostate ornamentation and distinct constrictions.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region almost straight.

3-5: Specimen RUC2015 JH 42, from the unit 9, i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

3: Ventral view; after two branching pairs, a single, undivided primary rib on one side joins a secondary rib on the other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern. Secondary ribs crossing venter without or with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

4: Lateral view of phragmocone and small part of body chamber.

5: Subcircular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 70 mm.

6: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 2, from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section, showing subquadrangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 95 mm.

Figs. 7-10: *Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) morph neglecta Spath, 1931 [M]

Specimen RUC2015 JH 38 from the unit 9, i.e. lower part of the Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

7: Lateral view of poorly preserved phragmocone and almost half of last whorl of body chamber.

8: Ventral view at a small diameter showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

9: Ventral view at a large diameter showing distinct constriction.

10: Suboval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 145 mm.

Plate VII

Figs. 1-8: *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]

From the unit 9, 10 and unit 12, i.e. Lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 15 microconch.

1: Flank showing phragmocone and small part of body chamber.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region almost straight.

3-4: Specimen RUC2015 JH 35, microconch.

3: Flank showing phragmocone, major part of body chamber, and varicostate ornamentation.

4: Ventral view showing a constriction almost parallel to the adjacent ribs, a slight forwardly directed sinuosity in secondary ribs, and single, undivided primary rib on one side joining a secondary rib on the other side, thus creating a zigzag pattern.

5-8: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 9, Macroconch

5: Lateral view of a large, still wholly septate shell, showing prosiradiate primary ribs with slight forwardly directed concavity on the flanks, mostly bifurcating but on the outer part of phragmocone either with free intercalatory secondary rib, a “sub-triplet” (sensu Spath, 1931: 488) or a trifurcating rib.

6: Ventral view showing slight forwardly directed sinuosity in secondary ribs crossing ventral region.

7: Subquadrate to subrounded whorl section drawn at a diameter of 105 mm.

8: Subrounded whorl section drawn at a diameter of 120 mm.

Plate VIII

Figs. 1-2: *Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, 1931 [m]

Specimen RUC2015 JH 34, from the unit 9 i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1: Lateral view showing phragmocone and major part of body chamber, varicostate ornamentation, and prosiradiate primary ribs with forwardly directed concavity on the flank near the inclined constriction.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region either straight (most posterior secondary ribs) or with forwardly directed sinuosity (most anterior secondary ribs).

Figs. 3-5: *Torquatisphinctes torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby, 1840)

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 7 from the unit 14 of the Shivparas Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermediate/Acanthicum zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

3: Lateral view of incomplete shell without body chamber, varicostate ornamentation, and shallow constrictions.

4: Ventral view showing almost straight secondary ribs crossing ventral region.

5: Subquadrangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 100 mm.

Plate IX

Figs. 1-7: *Torquatisphinctes acuticostatus* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]

From the unit 9 i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1-4: Specimen RUC2015 JH 49A, microconch.

1: Right lateral view of body chamber showing varicostate, prorsiradiate, thin, sharp, closely spaced, long, faintly flexuous primary ribs and oblique constrictions.

2: Left lateral view of body chamber.

3: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with faint forwardly directed convexity, occasionally without obvious forwardly directed convexity.

4: Suboval whorl section at unknown diameter.

5-7: Specimens RUC2015 JH 35A, Macroconch.

5: Lateral view showing both phragmocone and body chamber with varicostate, prorsiradiate, thin, sharp, closely spaced, long, primary ribs and constrictions.

6: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with faint forwardly directed convexity. Also note constriction.

7: Suboval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 178 mm.

Figs. 8-10: *Torquatisphinctes* cf. *jurunensis* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2016 IIJH 1 from the unit 9, i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

8: Lateral view of phragmocone showing varicostate, prorsiradiate, sharp, closely spaced primary ribs, becoming increasingly thicker and distant with increasing diameter. Note constrictions oblique to preceding ribs.

9: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing the ventral region without or with faint convexity.

10: Whorl section drawn at a diameter of 133 mm.

Plate X

Figs. 1-6: *Torquatisphinctes* gr. *primus-similis* Spath, 1931

From the unit 9 and unit 10, i.e. lower part of Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1-2: Specimen RUC2015 JH 41

1: Flank showing parts of phragmocone and body chamber. Note thin, varicostate, prorsiradiate ornamentation with long primary ribs and constrictions.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region without or with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

3: Specimen RUC2015 JH 40A, subrectangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 75 mm.

4-6: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 2

4: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region without or with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

5: Flank showing parts of phragmocone and body chamber. Note occasional single primary ribs and constriction near the aperture of the body chamber.

6: Sub-oval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 112 mm.

Plate XI

Figs. 1-3: *Indodichotomoceras inversum* (Spath, 1931) [m]

Specimen RUC2015 GD 1, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 1: Flank of small shell showing both phragmocone and body chamber with strong, sharp, varicostate, regularly biplicate ribs and occasional single rib.
- 2: Ventral view showing thick secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.
- 3: Subcircular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 89.3 mm.

Figs. 4, 8-10: *Indodichotomoceras cf. inversum* (Spath, 1931) [M]

From the units 20 and 21 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

4: Specimen RUC2015 GD 7, ventral view showing thick secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

8-10: Specimen RUC2015 GD 23

8: Flank of large shell (phragmocone and body chamber) with strong, sharp, varicostate, regularly biplicate ribs with occasional intercalation of single rib.

9: Ventral view showing thick secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

10: Subtrigonal whorl section drawn at a diameter of 138 mm.

Figs. 5-7: *Subdichotomoceras cf. lamplughii* Spath, 1925

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 5, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

5: Flank of a small fragment of phragmocone and body whorl showing distantly spaced, strong, sharp, regularly bifurcating ribs. Note a single rib.

6: Ventral view with more forwardly directed convexity in anterior secondary ribs than in posterior ones.

7: Subquadrate whorl section drawn at unknown diameter.

Plate XII

Figs. 1-3: *Pachysphinctes* cf. *robustus* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 12, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 1: Ventral view showing secondary ribs, slightly thinner than primary ribs, that uniformly bifurcate without any galloping and cross the ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.
- 2: Lateral view showing thick, distant, prorsiradiate ribs bifurcating at mid-whorl height on early part of body chamber and showing virgatotome triplicate branching towards end of outer whorl.
- 3: Subquadrangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of ~120 mm.

Figs. 4-5: *Pachysphinctes* sp.

Specimen RUC2015 GD 9, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 4: Lateral view of a fragmentary phragmocone showing thick, distant trifurcating ribs.
- 5: Ventral view showing broad ventral region with straight or slightly forwardly directed sinuosity in secondary ribs.

Figs. 6-7: *Indodichotomoceras predivisum* (Spath, 1931)

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 2, from the unit 14 of the Shivparas Member (Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 6: Lateral view showing almost complete shell with body chamber accounting for more than three-fourths of last whorl. Ornamentation as in other *Indodichotomoceras* species illustrated in Plate XI but denser.
- 7: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region with or without slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

Plate XIII

Figs. 1-2: *Pachysphinctes* sp.

Specimen RUC2018 JH 2, from the unit 12, i.e. lower part of the Lothia Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone to Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

- 1: Lateral view of inner whorls of a large specimen showing moderately thick, dense, strongly prorsiradiate, regularly biplicate and simple ribs.
- 2: Ventral view showing broad ventral region with secondary ribs slightly thinner than primary ribs, crossing ventral region with feeble forwardly directed sinuosity.

Figs. 3-5: *Pachysphinctes* cf. *linguiferus* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 18 from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 3: Lateral view showing moderately thick, prorsiradiate, faintly flexuous, distant primary ribs branching into three secondary ribs above mid-lateral height, branching occasionally virgatotome-like.
- 4: Ventral view showing secondary ribs much thinner than primary ribs, crossing the ventral region without forwardly directed sinuosity.
- 5: Subquadrangular whorl section with flattened flanks at a diameter of ~150 mm.

Figs. 6-8: *Pachysphinctes symmetricus* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2013 GD 1, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 6: Lateral view showing varicostate ornamentation. On outer part of last whorl, preceding a shallow constriction, two primary ribs appear to join at umbilical shoulder and a free secondary rib also appears just at ventro-lateral shoulder.
- 7: Ventral view showing narrow ventral region and secondary ribs crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity.
- 8: Subquadrangular whorl section with flattened flanks converging towards narrow ventral region at a diameter of 100 mm.

Figs. 9-11: *Pachysphinctes* gr. *linguiferus*-*symmetricus* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 13, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

- 9: Lateral view showing sharp, distant, prorsiradiate, varicostate primary ribs with virgatotome triplicate ribs towards outer part of body chamber.
- 10: Ventral view showing slightly thinner secondary ribs crossing ventral region either straight or with faint forwardly directed sinuosity.
- 11: Subcircular whorl section with flat flanks and broad ventral region at a diameter of ~140 mm.

Plate XIV

Figs. 1-3, 10: *Pachysphinctes major* Spath, 1931

From the units 20 and 21 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhurán Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

1-3: Specimen RUC2017 IGD 182

1: Lateral view showing varicostate, prorsiradiate ribs bifurcating slightly below ventro-lateral shoulder and occasionally single primary ribs. Note constrictions on inner whorls.

2: Ventral view showing slightly thinner secondary ribs, crossing ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity. Note galloping.

3: Sub-quadrangular whorl section with flattened flanks and broadly rounded ventral region at a diameter of 56 mm.

10: Specimen RUC2017 IGD 183, ventral view. Note anterior secondary ribs showing faint forwardly directed sinuosity, whereas posterior ribs are almost straight.

Figs. 4-9, 11-17: *Pachysphinctes cf. major* Spath, 1931

4-9: Specimen RUC2016 IJH 11, from the unit 13 of the lower part of the Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhurán Formation, Jhurán River section.

4: Lateral view showing feebly flexuous ribs, bifurcating below ventro-lateral shoulder and slightly forward-inclined constrictions.

5: Ventral view showing faint forwardly directed sinuosity of most anterior secondary ribs.

6: Subcircular whorl section with maximum thickness above umbilical shoulder at a diameter of ~48 mm.

7: Lateral view of inner whorls.

8: Ventral view showing broad ventral region.

9: Apertural view showing subcircular whorl section.

11—13: Specimen RUC2015 JH 17, from the unit 15 of the lower part of the Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhurán Formation, Jhurán River section.

11: Lateral view of part of phragmocone showing distant, thick, prorsiradiate primary ribs, trifurcating slightly above mid-lateral height.

12: Ventral view showing complex suture lines.

13: Suboval whorl section drawn at unknown diameter.

14—17: Specimen RUC2015 GD 41, from the unit 20 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhurán Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

14: Ventral view with secondary ribs crossing ventral region either straight (most posterior secondary ribs of triplets) or with faint forwardly directed sinuosity (most anterior secondary ribs of triplets).

15: Right lateral view of part of phragmocone showing thick, distant, prorsiradiate, primary ribs, trifurcating slightly above mid-lateral height.

16: Subcircular whorl section drawn at unknown diameter.

17: Left lateral view of part of phragmocone showing thick, distant, prorsiradiate, primary ribs, trifurcating slightly above mid-lateral height.

Plate XV

Figs. 1-8: *Pachysphinctes* aff. *major* Spath, 1931 [M]

From the units 13 and 15 of the lower part of the Lothia Member (Late Kimmeridgian Bathyplocus Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River section.

1-5: Specimen RUC2018 JH 1

- 1: Right lateral view of large phragmocone showing thin, sharp, prorsiradiate, bifurcating ribs.
 - 2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.
 - 3: Left lateral side showing thick, distant primary ribs on the outermost preserved whorl of phragmocone.
 - 4: Enlarged lateral view of part of the outer whorl showing folds and suture lines.
 - 5: Suboval whorl section with arched flanks at a diameter of 147 mm.
- 6-8: Specimen RUC2015 JH 14
- 6: Lateral view showing thin, sharp, prorsiradiate, bifurcating ribs.
 - 7: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.
 - 8: Suboval whorl section with arched flanks drawn at a diameter of 69 mm.

Plate XVI

Figs. 1-5: *Katroliceras katrolensis* (Waagen, 1875)

From the unit 35 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

1-2: Specimen RUC2015 GD 15

1: Lateral view of large shell with phragmocone and body chamber, the latter showing extremely coarse, short, increasingly distant primary ribs that branch after the umbilical shoulder into flaring secondary ribs. Note gradually increasing inter-rib distances at the beginning of the last quarter where ribs are approximately 20 mm apart.

2: Ventral view showing thin and closely spaced secondary ribs with or without slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

3-5: Specimen RUC2015 GD 28

3: Lateral view of phragmocone showing gradual thickening of primary ribs.

4: Ventral view showing slight forwardly directed sinuosity in secondary ribs crossing the ventral region.

5: Semicircular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 121 mm.

Plate XVII

Figs. 1-6: *Katroliceras subkatrolense* Spath, 1931

From the unit 35 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.
1-3: Specimen RUC2015 GD 23A

1: Lateral view showing phragmocone and body chamber.

2: Ventral view of broad ventral region showing triplets on body chamber. Note forwardly directed sinuosity in anterior-most secondary ribs, no sinuosity in middle secondary ribs and forwardly directed concavity in posterior-most secondary ribs.

3: Subquadrangular whorl section drawn at a diameter of 144 mm.

4-6: Specimen RUC2015 GD 4

4: Lateral view of phragmocone and body chamber.

5: Ventral view showing bifurcations on phragmocone with or without forwardly directed convexity of anterior secondary ribs and forwardly directed concavity of posterior secondary ribs.

6: Subquadrangular whorl section with acutely rounded umbilical shoulder at a diameter of 140 mm.

Plate XVIII

Figs. 1-5: *Katroliceras waageni* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]

From the unit 35 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

1-3: Specimen RUC2017 IGD 11 [m]

1: Ventral view showing broad ventral region with triplets and free secondary ribs inbetween triplets.

2: Side view of small shell with phragmocone and body chamber showing sudden widening of inter-rib space at the start of the last quarter of the body chamber.

3: Semi-circular whorl section with slightly arched flanks at a diameter of 111 mm.

4-5: Specimen RUC2017 IGD 14 [M]

4: Side view of body chamber showing sudden widening of inter-rib space at the beginning of its second quarter.

5: Ventral view showing broad ventral region with triplets and free secondary ribs inbetween triplets. Note one of the free secondary ribs joining other secondary rib in the central part of the ventral region. This is not in tune with the regular ornamentation of the species.

Figs. 6-8: *Katroliceras subkatrolense* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2015 GD 42, from the unit 35 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

6: Lateral view of body chamber showing moderately thick, prorsiradiate, primary ribs with gradually widening inter-rib spaces.

7: Ventral view showing triplets and free secondary ribs.

8: Subrounded whorl section at a diameter of 100 mm.

Plate XIX

Figs. 1-8: *Katroliceras sowerbyi* Spath, 1931

From the unit 35 of the Tapkeshwari Member (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

1-4: Specimen RUC2017 IGD 17

1: Right lateral view showing early part of body chamber ornamented with moderately thick, prorsiradiate primary ribs bifurcating slightly below ventro-lateral shoulder.

2: Left lateral view.

3: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity. Note galloping of secondary ribs.

4: Subquadrangular whorl section with slightly arched flanks at unknown diameter.

5-8: Specimen RUC2015 GD 20

5: Lateral view showing phragmocone and outer part of body chamber. Body chamber ornamented with coarse, folds-like primary ribs, becoming increasingly more distant, branching below ventro-lateral shoulder into thinner secondary ribs.

6: Ventral view.

7: Subquadrangular whorl section with slightly arched flanks at a diameter of 125 mm.

8: Subquadrangular whorl section at a diameter of ~155 mm.

Figs. 9-11: *Katroliceras* sp.

Specimen RUC2016 IKH 51, Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

9: Lateral view of inner whorls of large specimen showing thin, closely spaced, prorsiradiate, varicostate ribs bifurcating below ventro-lateral shoulder. Note presence of constrictions.

10: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing uninterrupted broad ventral region straight or with slight forwardly directed convexity.

11: Subquadrangular whorl section with broad venter drawn at a diameter of 54 mm.

Plate XX

Figs. 1-8: *Katroliceras* sp.

Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 IKH 02

1: Lateral view of inner whorls showing thin, closely spaced, prorsiradiate bifurcating ribs and occasionally single ribs. Note presence of constrictions.

2: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing ventral region with forwardly directed sinuosity.

3-5: Specimen RUC2016 IKH 04

3: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing broad ventral region with forwardly directed sinuosity.

4: Apertural view showing subcircular whorl section.

5: Lateral view of inner whorls showing, thin closely spaced, prorsiradiate, bifurcating ribs and occasionally single ribs. Note presence of constrictions.

6-8: Specimen RUC2016 IKH 05

6: Lateral view of inner whorls showing thin, closely spaced, prorsiradiate, bifurcating ribs and occasionally single ribs. Note presence of constrictions.

7: Apertural view showing subcircular whorl section.

8: Part of ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing broad ventral region with slight forwardly directed sinuosity.

Figs. 9-12: *Katroliceras lerense* Spath, 1931

Specimen RUC2016 IKH 01, Lothia Member, Jhuran Formation (Late Kimmeridgian Katrolensis Zone), Kas Hill section, near Lodai Dam.

9: Lateral view of phragmocone with thin, bifurcating rib, and body chamber with moderately spaced, moderately thick, bifurcating ribs. Free secondary ribs at the beginning of body chamber and thick, widely spaced, bifurcating and free secondary ribs at the end of preserved part of body chamber. Note presence of constrictions.

10: Ventral view showing secondary ribs crossing the ventral region with faint forwardly directed sinuosity.

11: Subquadrangular whorl section at broken surface at a diameter of 92 mm.

12: Subcircular whorl section drawn along inter-rib area at a diameter of 131 mm.

Plate XXI

Figs. 1-3: *Aspidoceras* cf. *acanthicum* (Oppel, 1863)

Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 8, from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (early Late Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

1: Lateral view of phragmocone and part of body chamber. Note two rows of obscure tubercles marked with circles, otherwise smooth outer whorl, and two rows of small tubercles on inner whorls.

2: Ventral view.

3: Sub-trigonal whorl section with slightly arched flanks and acutely rounded umbilical shoulder at a diameter of 84 mm.

Figs. 4-7: *Aspidoceras* aff. *bispinosum* (Zieten, 1830)

Specimen RUC2016 II LOD 16, from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (early Late Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

4: Lateral view of body chamber showing two rows of small, distant, but regularly spaced tubercles marked with circles.

5: Ventral view of body chamber showing convex ventral region.

6: Suboval whorl section drawn at unknown diameter.

7: Suboval whorl section drawn at unknown diameter.

Plate XXII

Figs. 1-3: *Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]

1-2: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 5, microconch, from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (early Late Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

1: Lateral view of outer whorl representing body chamber, ornamented with equal-sized, coarse tubercles arranged evenly in two closely associated peri-umbilical and lateral rows.

2: Subcircular/suboval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 94 mm.

3: Specimen RUC2015 JH 26, Macroconch, lower part of Lothia Member, Jhuran River Member (Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Jhuran River Section; subcircular whorl section of large phragmocone drawn at unknown diameter.

Figs. 4-7: *Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen, 1875

from the unit 75 of the Jhuran River Member (early Late Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Lodai section.

4: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 6, lateral view showing very fine, closely spaced growth lines and two rows of moderately distant, occasionally irregularly spaced tubercles on body chamber.

5-7: Specimen RUC2016 ILOD 20

5: Lateral view of phragmocone and small part of body chamber showing two rows of moderately distant, occasionally irregularly spaced tubercles.

6: Ventral view showing feeble secondary folds on broad ventral region.

7: Subrounded/suboval whorl section drawn at a diameter of 153 mm.

Figs. 8-10: *Aspidoceras iphiceroides* Waagen, 1875

Specimen RUC2017 IGD 1, from the unit 14 of the Shivparas Member (early Late Kimmeridgian Intermedius/Acanthicum Zone), Jhuran Formation, Gangeshwar Dome section.

8: Lateral view of phragmocone showing two close rows of regularly spaced tubercles confined to inner half of lateral flank, leaving upper half of flank smooth. Note very faint rib-like folds connecting peri-umbilical and lateral tubercles.

9: Ventral view of phragmocone showing broad ventral region.

10: Apertural view of phragmocone showing rounded whorl section at broken surface with maximum thickness between the two rows of tubercles.

Appendix 1. Dimensions of the studied ammonites and comparison with literature data. Dimensions in millimetres; percentual ratios between brackets.

***Holcophylloceras cf. polyolcum* (Benecke, 1865) and *Holcophylloceras zignodianum* (d'Orbigny, 1848)**

specimen	D	H (H/D)	W (W/D)	U (U/D)	H/W
RUC2016 IKH 07	69.0	36.0 (52)	22.5 (33)	9.5 (14)	1.6
<i>Holcophylloceras</i> aff. <i>polyolcum</i> (Benecke) in Spath (1927, pl. 6, fig. 1)	125.0	66.2 (53)	42.5 (34)	16.2 (13)	1.6
<i>Holcophylloceras</i> aff. <i>polyolcum</i> (Benecke) in Spath (1927, pl. 6, fig. 2c)	67.0	36.0 (53)	20.0 (30)	8.7 (13)	1.8
<i>Holcophylloceras</i> aff. <i>polyolcum</i> (Benecke) in Spath (1927, pl. 6, fig. 2d)	68.0	36.0 (53)	21.0 (31)	8.8 (13)	1.1
<i>Holcophylloceras zignodianum</i> (d'Orbigny, 1848) in Seyed-Emami (2013, fig. 4a-b)	98.0	55.0 (56)	-	10.0 (10)	-

***Ptychophylloceras cf. ptychoicum* (Quenstedt, 1845)**

specimen	D	H (H/D)	W (W/D)	U (U/D)	H/W
RUC2016 ILOD 26	102.0	57.0 (56)	50.0 (49)	~12 (11)	1.1
	82.0	44.0 (53)	38.0 (46)	~11 (13)	1.1
<i>P. ptychoicum</i> in Waagen (1875, pl. 7, fig. 2a-c)	90.0	53.0 (59)	39.0 (43)	7.0 (8)	1.4
<i>P. ptychoicum</i> in Pandey et al. (2013b, pl. 1, fig. 2)	70.9	41.5 (59)	32.5 (46)	6.6 (9)	1.3
<i>P. ptychoicum</i> in Joly (2000, pl. 31, pl. 39, fig. 6)	62.0	36.0 (58)	28.6 (46)	6.0 (10)	1.3

***Taramelliceras kachhensis* (Waagen, 1875)**

specimen	D	H (H/D)	W (W/D)	U (U/D)	H/W
RUC2016 IKH 52	38.0	18.0 (47)	14.5 (38)	9.0 (24)	1.2
RUC2016 IKH 34	47.0	24.0 (51)	16.5 (35)	10.0 (21)	1.4
Waagen (1875, pl. 10, fig. 4a, b)	84.0	46 (55)	26 (31)	12 (14)	1.8

***Torquatisphinctes alterneplicatus* (Waagen, 1875) and *T. jurunensis* Spath, 1931**

specimen	D	H (H/D)	W (W/D)	U (U/D)	H/W
RUC2016 IJH 23 (>85 ribs in venter in outer whorl)	75.0	26.0 (35)	25.0 (33)	31.0 (41)	1.0
RUC2016 ILOD 1 (48 ribs in venter in half whorl at D = 67 mm)	85.0	25.0 (29)	26.5 (31)	39.7 (47)	0.9
RUC2015 JH 11 (65 ribs at 104 mm diameter at half whorl)	109.0	30.7 (28)	34.4 (32)	55.5 (51)	0.9
<i>Perisphinctes alterneplicatus</i> Waagen, 1875 (p. 199, pl. 50, fig. 2), holotype	115.0	38.0 (33)	34.0 (29)	54.0 (47)	1.1
RUC2016 IJH 6	215.0	69 (32)	~64 (30)	100 (47)	1.1
<i>T. jurunensis</i> Spath, 1931 (p. 488, pl. 76, fig. 1a, b)	212.0	57.2 (27)	50.8 (24)	114.4 (54)	1.1
Waagen (1875: pl. 50, fig. 2a, b)	115.0	38.0 (33)	34.0 (30)	54.0 (47)	1.1
RUC2015 JH 30	97.5	27.5 (28)			0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 2	97.0	26.0 (27)	29.0 (30)	49.0 (51)	0.9
RUC2015 JH 21	92.2	30.0 (32)	33 (36)	42.2 (46)	0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 3	81.3	23.5 (29)	27.7 (34)	40.0 (49)	0.8
RUC2015 JH 42	72.0	21.0 (29)	22.0 (30)	36.0 (50)	0.9

RUC2016 ILOD 4	65.6	20.0 (30)	23.0 (35)	29 (44.2)	0.9
RUC2016 GD 3	47.8	14.6 (31)	21.5 (45)	20.6 (43)	0.9
RUC2016 IIJH 25	~ 46.0	19.0 (41)	21.0 (46)	15.0 (33)	0.9
	37.0	12.4 (34)	20.4 (55)	12.4 (34)	0.6
Spath (1931, pl. 84, fig. 3)	61.0	20.1 (33)	23.7 (39)	27.4 (45)	0.8
RUC2015 JH 38	148.0	40.6 (27)	42 (28)	76 (51)	0.96

***Torquatisphinctes intermedius* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
	184.0	54.0 (29)	54.0 (29)	84.0 (46)	1.0
RUC2016 IJH 9	180.0	53.4 (30)	54.2 (30)	85.4 (47)	0.98
	~146.0	45.0 (31)	46.0 (32)	-	0.97
	70.0	21.0 (30)	27.0 (39)	-	0.8
RUC2015 JH 34 Phragmocone + body chamber (59 ribs at the periphery in outer half whorl)	135.2	38.9 (29)	-	69.0 (51)	-
	118.0	34.0 (29)	~36.0 (31)	59.3 (50)	0.9
RUC2015 JH 35 Phragmocone + body chamber (59 ribs at the periphery in outer half whorl)	~135.0	40.0 (29)	-	69.0 (51)	-
	101.0	27.0 (27)	~32.0 (32)	51.5 (51)	0.8
RUC2016 IIJH 7 Phragmocone + body chamber (59 ribs at the periphery in outer half whorl)	121.5	37.0 (30)	33.5 (28)	57.7 (47)	1.1
RUC2015 JH 57 Phragmocone	102.0	~31.5 (30)	32.0 (31)	46.4 (45)	0.98
RUC2015 JH 37	80.0	22.0 (28)	27.0 (34)	40.6 (51)	0.8
RUC2015 GD 31 Phragmocone + body chamber	89.4	26.0 (29)	30.0 (34)	43.0 (48)	0.9
RUC2016 IJH 15 (82 ribs at the periphery in outer whorl)	57.0	19.0 (33)	22.0 (39)	29.0 (51)	0.9
<i>T. intermedius</i> Spath, 1931 (p. 482, pl. 81, fig. 3)	124.0	34.7 (28)	40.9 (33)	60.7 (49)	0.8
<i>T. intermedius</i> Spath, 1931 (p. 482, pl. 82, fig. 6) (58 ribs at the periphery in outer half whorl)	80.0	24.8 (31)	29.6 (37)	36.8 (46)	0.8

***Torquatisphinctes torquatus* (J. de C. Sowerby, 1840)**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
	105.7	34.3 (32)	37.5 (35)	42.9 (47)	0.9
	102.0	30.0 (29)	35.0 (34)	45.6 (45)	0.8
RUC2017 IGD 7	98.4	29.3 (30)	33.6 (34)	44.5 (45)	0.9
	78.4	27.0 (34)	28.8 (37)	33.0 (42)	0.9
	31.6	11.4 (36)	16.3 (52)	11.7 (37)	0.7
<i>T. torquatus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 76, fig. 4a, b)	64.0	21.7 (34)	22.4 (35)	27.5 (43)	0.96
<i>T. torquatus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 92, fig. 6a, b)	50.0	15.0 (30)	15.0 (30)	23.5 (47)	1.0

***Torquatisphinctes* cf. *jurunensis* Spath, 1931 and *T. intermedius* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 IIJH 1	133.0	37.0 (28)	38.0 (29)	68.0 (51)	1.0
RUC2017 IGD 9	144.5	~39.0 (27)	~43 (30)	71.6 (50)	0.9
<i>T. jurunensis</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 76, fig. 1a, b)	212.0	57.2 (27)	50.8 (24)	114.4 (54)	1.1
<i>T. intermedius</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 81, fig. 3)	124	34.7 (28)	40.9 (33)	60.7 (49)	0.8

***Torquatisphinctes acuticostatus* Spath, 1931 and *Torquatisphinctes?* *lunulaticus* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
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RUC2015 JH 35A	178.0	49.0 (28)	46.7 (26)	90.4 (51)	1.0
RUC2015 JH 32	140.0	40.0 (28)	38.0 (27)	68.8 (49)	1.0
RUC2015 JH 49A	123.0	37.5 (30)	33.7 (27)	59.0	1.1
<i>T. acuticostatus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 88, figs. 2, 10a-c)	84.0	26.8 (32)	26.0(31)	37.8 (45)	1.0
	55.0	18.7 (34)	19.8 (36)	23.1 (42)	0.9
<i>T. ? lunulaplicatus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 95, fig. 9a, b)	80.0	28.0 (35)	26.4 (33)	36.0 (45)	1.0

***Torquatisphinctes* gr. *primus-similis* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 JH 41	114.5	31.0 (27)	30.5 (27)	59.3 (52)	1.0
	112.0	34.4 (31)	34.4 (31)	57.0 (51)	1.0
RUC2016 IJH 2	-	32.5	32.8	-	0.99
	-	17.6	19.0	-	0.9
RUC2016 IJH 24	94.7	26.8 (28)	-	47.6 (50)	-
RUC2016 IJH 10	76.7	21.6 (28)	22.0 (29)	37.3 (50)	0.98
<i>T. primus</i> (Spath 1931, pl. 88, fig. 6a, b), holotype	88.0	29.4 (33)	27.2 (31)	40.4 (46)	1.1
<i>T. primus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 88, fig. 7a, b), paratype	66.0	21.1 (32)	23.7 (36)	30.3 (46)	0.9
<i>T. similis</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 78, fig. 3)	97.0	31.0 (32)	31.0 (32)	47.5 (49)	1.0
<i>T. similis</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 92, fig. 6a, b)	85.0	25.5 (30)	26.3 (31)	42.5 (50)	0.96

***Indodichotomoceras* cf. *inversum* (Spath, 1931)**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 GD 23	138.8	41.0 (30)	-	68.3 (49)	-
	123.0	38.0 (31)	-	61.0 (50)	-
<i>S. inversum</i> (Spath, 1931, p. 521), holotype	108.0	31.3 (29)	34.5 (32)	55.1(51)	0.9

***Indodichotomoceras inversum* (Spath, 1931) [m] and *Subdichotomoceras simplex* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 GD 1	89.3	22.8 (26)	25.4 (28)	48.9 (55)	0.9
<i>Subdichotomoceras inversum</i> , holotype	108.0	31.3 (29)	34.5 (32)	55.9 (51)	0.9
<i>Subdichotomoceras simplex</i> Spath, 1931	117.0	30.4 (26)	35.1 (30)	62.0 (53)	0.9

***Indodichotomoceras predivisum* (Spath, 1931), *Pachysphinctes symmetricus* Spath, 1931 and *Subdich. simplex* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 2	126.7	32.5 (26)	35.2 (28)	67.0 (53)	0.9
<i>D. predivisum</i> , holotype	98.0	29.0 (30)	31.0 (32)	47.0 (48)	0.9
<i>D. predivisum</i> , paratype	96.0	26.8 (28)	28.8 (30)	49.9 (52)	0.9
<i>D. predivisum</i> Spath (1931, p. 422)	123.0	36.9 (30)	33.2 (27)	21.5 (50)	1.1
<i>P. symmetricus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 101, fig. 7a, b)	122.0	30.5 (25)	34.1 (28)	64.6 (53)	0.9
<i>S. simplex</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 83, fig. 8a, b)	117.0	30.4 (26)	35.1 (30)	62.0 (53)	0.9

***Pachysphinctes* cf. *robustus* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 12	-	34.5	37.5	-	0.9
<i>Pachysphinctes robustus</i> Spath (1931, p. 491)	150	43.5 (29)	49.5 (33)	70.5 (47)	0.9

***Pachysphinctes* sp. and *Pachysphinctes irregularis* Spath, 1931.**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2018 JH 2	49.0	15.0 (31)	23.0 (47)	26.5 (54)	0.7
<i>P. irregularis</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 95, fig. 8a, b)	78.0	21.8 (28)	31.2 (40)	39.0 (50)	0.7
<i>Pachysphinctes cf. linguiferus</i> Spath, 1931.					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 18	-	41.5	48.3	-	0.9
<i>P. linguiferus</i> , holotype	170.0	52.7 (31)	62.9 (37)	85.0 (50)	0.8
<i>Pachysphinctes</i> gr. <i>linguiferus-symmetricus</i> Spath, 1931 and <i>Pachysphinctes bathyplocus</i> (Waagen, 1875)					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 13	156.0	40 (26)	50 (32)	84.5 (54)	0.8
<i>P. linguiferus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 97: 1, pl. 98: 5)	170.0	52.7 (31)	62.9 (37)	85 (50)	0.8
<i>P. symmetricus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 101, fig. 7a, b)	122.0	30.5 (25)	34.1 (28)	64.6 (53)	0.9
<i>P. bathyplocus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 77, fig. 1)	137.0	35.6 (26)	42.4 (31)	73.9 (54)	0.8
<i>P. bathyplocus</i> (Waagen, 1875, pl. 1, fig. 1a, b)	210.0	56.7 (27)	73.5 (35)	102.9 (49)	0.8
<i>Pachysphinctes symmetricus</i> Spath, 1931					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2013 GD 01	100.0	27.0 (27)	35.0 (35)	48.0 (48)	0.8
<i>P. symmetricus</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 101, fig. 7)	122.0	30.5 (25)	34.1 (28)	64.6 (53)	0.9
<i>Pachysphinctes major</i> Spath, 1931					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 182	56.0	20.0 (36)	23.0 (41)	25.0 (45)	0.9
<i>P. major</i> (Spath 1931, p. 489)	71.0	19.0 (27)	28.0 (39)	29.0 (40)	0.7
<i>Pachysphinctes cf. major</i> Spath, 1931					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 IJH 11	48.2	15.6 (32)	18.4 (38)	20.5 (43)	0.9
<i>Pachysphinctes</i> aff. <i>major</i> Spath, 1931 [M] and <i>Katrolicerias katrolensis</i> (Waagen, 1875)					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 JH 14	69.0	24.0 (35)	24.0 (35)	30.0 (43)	1.0
RUC2018 JH 1	147.0	44.0 (30)	~54.0 (37)	66.0 (45)	0.8
<i>P. major</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 75, fig. 1a, b)	157.0	42.0 (26)	45.0 (28)	79.0 (50)	0.9
<i>Katrolicerias katrolensis</i> (Waagen, 1875)					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
<i>Perisphinctes katrolensis</i> (Waagen, 1875, pl. 53)	195.0	43.0 (22)	56.0 (28)	115.0 (58.9)	0.8
RUC2015 GD 28	123.7	32.6 (26)	34.7 (28)	64.4 (52)	0.9
RUC2015 GD 15	184.0	45.0 (24)	64.0 (34)	106.0 (58)	0.7
<i>Katrolicerias subkatrolense</i> Spath, 1931					
specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 GD 23A	148.0	41.0 (27)	48.0 (32)	81.0 (54)	0.9

RUC2015 GD 42	~147.0	39.0 (26)	44.0 (29)	-	0.9
RUC2015 GD 4	144.0	36.0 (25)	~42.0 (29)	-	0.9
Holotype (Spath, 1931, pl. 85, fig. 6)	103.0	30.9 (30)	36.0 (35)	48.4 (47)	0.9

***Katroliceras waageni* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 IGD 11	102.0	27.0 (26)	34.0 (33)	51.0 (50)	0.7 0.8
RUC2017 IGD 14	163.5	39.3 (24)	46.3 (28)	-	0.7 0.8
<i>Perisphinctes pottingeri</i> (Waagen, 1875, pl. 51, fig. 1a, b)	92.0	20.0 (22)	30.0 (33)	47.0 (51)	0.7
	120.0	29.0 (24)	46.0 (38)	65.0 (54)	0.6
	150.0	33.0 (22)	60.0 (40)	78.0 (52)	0.6

***Katroliceras sowerbyi* Spath, 1931 and *Katroliceras pottingeri* (J. de C. Sowerby, 1840)**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 GD 20	-	47.0	52.0	-	0.9
	-	36.0	38.0	-	0.9
RUC2017 IGD 17	-	40.0	38.0	-	1.1
<i>Katroliceras sowerbyi</i> (Spath, 1931, 509)	110.0	33.0 (30)	46.0 (42)	56.0 (51)	0.7
<i>Katroliceras pottingeri</i> (Spath, 505), holotype	113.0	29.3 (26)	43.0 (38)	61.0 (54)	0.7

***Katroliceras* sp. and related taxa**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 IKH 4	36.0	12.0 (33)	16.0 (44)	17.0 (47)	0.8
RUC2016 IKH 2	37.0	13.0 (35)	16.0 (43)	16.5 (45)	0.8
RUC2016 IKH 51	54.0	20.0 (37)	21.0 (39)	23 (43)	0.95
RUC2016 IKH 5	58.0	19.0 (33)	23.0 (40)	27.0 (46)	0.8
RUC2016 IKH 3	64.0	18.0 (28)	21.0 (33)	26.5 (41)	0.9

***Katroliceras lerense* Spath, 1931 and *Katroliceras subkatrolense* Spath, 1931**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 KH 01	119.3	33.2 (28)	41.4 (35)	57.5 (48)	0.8
	149.7	38.5 (26)	46.5 (31)	77.6 (52)	0.8
<i>K. lerense</i> Spath (1931, pl. 88, fig. 5; pl. 89, fig. 1)	170.0	42.5 (25)	47.6 (28)	95.2 (56)	0.9
<i>K. subkatrolense</i> Spath (1931, pl. 75, fig. 6a, b)	103.0	30.9 (30)	36 (35)	48.4 (47)	0.9

***Aspidoceras* cf. *acanthicum* (Opper, 1863)**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 ILOD 8	92.0	38.2 (42)	38.2 (42)	27.0 (29)	1.0
<i>A. aff. acanthicum</i> (Spath, 1931, pl. 123, fig. 7)	57.0	23.9 (42)	25.6 (45)	17.7 (31)	0.9
<i>A. acanthicum</i> (Neumayr, 1873, pl. 41, fig. 1)	170.0	64.6 (38)	64.6 (38)	57.8 (34)	1.0

***Aspidoceras* aff. *bispinosum* (Zieten, 1830)**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2016 ILOD 16	155.0	65.0 (42)	60.0 (39)	56.0 (36)	1.1
<i>A. aff. bispinosum</i> (Spath, 1931, p. 627)	100.0	38.0 (38)	?36.0 (36)	26.0 (36)	1.0

***Aspidoceras asymmetricum* Spath, 1931 [m] & [M]**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 NJH 26	at 111.0	ca 49.0 (44)	ca 53.6 (48)	-	0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 5	at 93.1	40.0 (43)	45.0 (48)	26.8 (29)	0.9
Holotype (Spath, 1931, pl. 118, fig. 3a, b)	65.0	27.3 (42)	29.9 (46)	20.8 (32)	0.9

***Aspidoceras binodiferum* Waagen, 1875**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2015 JH 18	at 85.8	32.0 (37)	35.0 (41)	33.0 (39)	0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 15	111.0	42.0 (38)	49.0 (44)	39.0 (35)	0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 6	at 115.3	41.0 (36)	50.0 (43)	40.3 (35)	0.8
RUC2016 ILOD 25	140.0	53.0 (38)	58.0 (41)	48.0 (34)	0.9
RUC2016 ILOD 20	144.4	58.5 (40)	60.3 (42)	47.7 (33)	0.97

***Aspidoceras iphiceroides* Waagen, 1875**

specimen	<i>D</i>	<i>H (H/D)</i>	<i>W (W/D)</i>	<i>U (U/D)</i>	<i>H/W</i>
RUC2017 GD 1	98.0	39.0 (40)	54.0 (55)	31.0 (32)	0.7
<i>A. iphiceroides</i> (Waagen, 1875, 103)	41.0	18.0 (44)	22.5 (55)	10.0 (24)	0.8
<i>A. iphiceroides</i> (Waagen, 1875, 103)	82.0	37.0 (45)	47.0 (57)	23.0 (28)	0.8
<i>A. iphiceroides</i> (Waagen, 1875, 103)	142.0	66.0 (46)	73.0 (51)	42.0 (30)	0.9